

Supplementary Information

This file contains the Supplementary Information that is referenced in the paper, An Electromagnetic Calculation of Ionospheric Conductance that seems to Override the Field Line Integrated Conductivity [Cosgrove, 2022].

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S.1 The Matrix H_{5ES}

The matrix H_{5ES} is shown in detail in Figure S.1.

S.2 Parameter Choices

The ionospheric parameters used in the analysis are the same as used by Cosgrove [2016] (see their Appendix B), and are reproduced here for reference. An electron density profile derived from Sondrestrom incoherent scatter radar data, with E region arc and substantial F region, is shown in the top left panel of Figure S.2. However, this profile is used only for the green curve of panel 1, Figure 2. Otherwise the density is kept constant with altitude, with values as identified in the text. A profile for the ion mass is shown in the top right panel of Figure S.2. A collision frequency profile, including ν_{in} , ν_{en} , and ν_{ei} , is shown in the bottom left panel of Figure S.2. The collision frequency profiles up to 1000 km come from the textbook by Gurevich [1978]. However, ν_{ei} is proportional to density, and so the ν_{ei} profile was rescaled to reflect the density profile in Figure S.2, which is slightly different from that assumed by Gurevich [1978]. When used with the various constant vertical density profiles in the text, the ν_{ei} profile is rescaled for each. The neutral collisions, ν_{in} and ν_{en} , are set to zero above 1000 km. The formula

$$\nu_{ei} = 54.5 \frac{n_i Z_i^2}{T_e^{3/2}}, \quad (\text{S.1})$$

from Schunk and Nagy [2000] is used above 1000 km, where T_e is the electron temperature in Kelvin, n_i is the ion density in cm^{-3} , and Z_i is the ion charge number. We assume $n_i = n$, $Z_i = 1$, and use the electron temperature profile shown in the middle left panel of Figure S.2. Above 1000 km, the T_e profile is motivated by Abe *et al.* [1997]. In the region below 1000 km, the T_e profile is taken from Gurevich's text [Gurevich, 1978, nighttime], and is incorporated in ν_{en} and ν_{ei} . The temperature in the region below 1000 km is used only to compare the collision frequency equation (S.1) with the values from the text by Gurevich [1978]. The formula (S.1) is found to match exactly the value given by Gurevich [1978] at 1000 km, although (S.1) gives negligibly larger values around the F region peak (323 s^{-1} as compared with 300 s^{-1} , at 315 km). Another formula, $\nu_{ei} = [34 + 4.18 \ln(T_e^3/n)] n T_e^{-3/2}$, appears in [Kelley, 1989], where it is attributed to Nicolet [1953]; it gives nearly identical results to equation (S.1).

Figure S.2: Ion mass, electron temperature, geomagnetic field, and collision frequencies used in all calculations, along with the associated Farley factor. A density profile is also shown, but is used only for the green curve of panel 1, Figure 2. Otherwise the density is kept constant with altitude, with values as identified in the text. This figure is reproduced from *Cosgrove* [2016].

We have favored the *Gurevich* [1978] results only because that text seems to have a complete treatment that is possible to follow without too much difficulty. *Gurevich* [1978] expands the electron distribution function in terms of Legendre polynomials and solves the Boltzmann equation with the Boltzmann collision integral and the Rutherford scattering cross section. *Schunk and Nagy* [2000] explain that their collision frequency formula is derived from a 13-moment velocity distribution, which arises from an expansion in Hermite polynomials about a Gaussian. They reference Chapman and Cowling [1970] for the Chapman-Cowling collision integral, derived for a general inverse power force law. We have compared the results from these two methods and find that they are essentially identical, for our example.

S.3 Additional Commentary on Energy Conservation

Because these are plasma waves, with degrees of freedom and modes of energy storage beyond the electromagnetic, the landscape for energy conservation is more complex than for the usual TL theory.¹ Consider a source with an internal admittance that is positive-real, attached to a TL section with characteristic admittance Y_0 . For the usual case where Y_0 is positive-real, it is easy to understand that when there is no back reflected wave in the TL section, the system absorbs energy by carrying it away, and the input admittance ($Y_{inMatched}$) may be matched to the source. And when there is a back reflected wave the energy is returned, which is consistent with the fact that the input admittance (Y_{inOC}) becomes imaginary, and so is no longer matched to the source.

However, the situation is somewhat different for the ionosphere. For the ionosphere Y_0 is imaginary, and so if there is no back-reflected wave in the TL section the input admittance ($Y_{inMatched}$) is imaginary, and so not well matched to the source. The mismatch means that the energy is returned, but in this case it is not returned from within the TL section. Rather, the energy never makes it into the TL section at all, that is, the wave amplitudes in the TL section are very small.

On the other hand, when Y_0 is imaginary and there *is* a back-reflected wave in the TL section, the input admittance (Y_{inOC}) is real and so may be matched to the source. In this case the energy may be absorbed even though there is a back-reflected wave within the TL section. How is this possible without wave dissipation, which is not needed for the admittance calculation? In this case the amplitude of the reflected wave may be reduced by nonlinear interaction with the incident wave, with associated heating. Since the heating terms decrease with the square of the wave amplitudes, the fractional reduction of the reflected wave decreases with the wave amplitudes, even as energy conservation is maintained.

And finally we have the case where Y_0 is imaginary and there is a back-reflected wave in the TL section, but the input admittance (Y_{inOC}) becomes negative-real, instead of positive-real. In this case the source and TL section are severely mismatched, and so the net Poynting flux may actually be into the source. Where is this energy coming from? In this case we must appeal to energy conversion. From the analysis surrounding Table 3 in *Cosgrove* [2016], it appears that kinetic energy may be converted into electromagnetic energy [also see *Vasyliunas and Song*, 2005], and so this may supply the energy that is needed to support a negative ionospheric conductance. If so, this is a feature that distinguishes collisional plasma waves, where the mass of the charge carriers may be significant.

S.4 Analytic Dependence for Polarization Vectors

Here we provide details on the method for approximating the eigenvector k_2 -dependence by an analytic function. The eigenvectors, \vec{h}_j , which make up the columns of the matrix U , are, by convention, constrained to have a complex modulus of one. Hence, variations of the eigenvectors occur through transformations under the 16-dimensional special unitary group, $SU(16)$. It is well known that special unitary transformations can be parameterized about the identity by $\vec{\theta} \in \mathbb{R}^{16^2-1}$ (in the 16-dimensional case), where the transformation

¹In this work we consider the case where the neutral wind is zero, and so the ionosphere is not a source of energy. Wave amplitudes decrease with time. But when the wind is nonzero it is possible for the ionosphere to be a source of energy, which would manifest as wave amplitudes that increase with time, that is, unstable waves. In this case there is likely no steady state for the system, and so the steady state treatment is not applicable, and neither is the concept of admittance (or conductance). It is necessary to use a time-domain description, and to limit the time horizon such that wave amplitudes remain small, or otherwise to include their non-linear interactions.

is realized by multiplication by the matrix $e^{-i\vec{\theta}\cdot\mathbf{J}}$, and \mathbf{J} is a vector of matrices, which are the $16^2 - 1$ generators of $SU(16)$ [e.g., *Mathews and Walker*, 1970; *Tung*, 1985]. Although we cannot be sure that the dependence of θ on k_z is analytic, we can obtain an analytic function that approximates the eigenvector transformation over the contributing part of the peaked integrand by linearizing the dependence of $\vec{\theta}$ on k_z , that is, $\vec{\theta} \cong (k_z - k_{0z}) \left. \frac{\partial \vec{\theta}}{\partial k_z} \right|_{k_z=k_{0z}}$. Therefore, we will approximate the eigenvector evolution operator by,

$$\Theta(k_z - k_{0z}) = e^{-i(k_z - k_{0z}) \left. \frac{\partial \vec{\theta}}{\partial k_z} \right|_{k_z=k_{0z}} \cdot \mathbf{J}}. \quad (\text{S.2})$$

The only problem is that it is not completely clear if this exponential function will allow the boundary terms associated with the residue theorem to vanish. However, using again our assumption that the main contribution to the integral can be localized around $k_z = k_{0z}$, there is no harm in multiplying the integrand by an analytic function such as $e^{\pm i(k_z^3 - k_{0z}^3)/\sigma^3}$, and choosing σ to be sufficiently large that the integral is not affected. Choosing the \pm sign to give exponential decay, the k_z^3 dependence will dwarf any exponential growth that might possibly come from (S.2), regardless of the choice for σ . Thus, we can assume σ is sufficiently large that the integral is not affected, apply the residue theorem, and the residue will not be affected either.

Note that introduction of the form (S.2) is really a formality, so that we can apply the residue theorem and then later argue that $\Theta \cong I$, based on numerical evaluation of the integrals. Hence we need never actually specify the derivatives $\left. \frac{\partial \vec{\theta}}{\partial k_z} \right|_{k_z=k_{0z}}$.

S.5 Validation Figures and Elaboration

Figures S.3-S.5 show comparisons of the exact (i.e., obtained by numerical integration) and eigenmode results at the four corners of the modeling domain, which domain is described in Section 7. While there is some numerical scatter in the integration results, they nevertheless provide a pretty strong indication of convergence to the simple wave-packet interpretation, without corrections. However, there are some anomalies that we discuss in this supplementary section. At this time it is difficult to tell if these anomalies represent actual predictions, numerical inadequacies such as aliasing or windowing, or the result of a failure of our assumption that the source (10) possesses a far zone (which would be a failure of the validation method, and not necessarily an invalidation).

Results for the wavelength and dissipation scale length are shown in Figure S.3, for both modes. Results are shown separately for E_y , B_x , E_x , and B_z , since these are all integrated separately. For reference, the ratio of the dissipation scale to the wavelength is also shown in the bottom row, as it obtains from the simple wavepacket interpretation. With respect to the wavelength, it is evident that the results agree almost exactly in all cases. The only caveat is that it was impossible to obtain results at the lowest altitude (100 km) for one of the four corners, specifically at the corner with transverse wavelength 1000 km and density 10^{11} m^{-3} . This combination of altitude, transverse wavelength, and density produces the lowest ratio of dissipation scale length to parallel wavelength (bottom right panel of Figure S.3), where in this case we mean the dissipation scale length derived from the group velocity. The dissipation scale length for the Whistler mode is about equal to its wavelength, while for the Alfvén mode it is much less, under these conditions. This situation might be expected to pose a challenge to our method of fitting a damped sinusoidal wave to the output from the numerical integration, since the signal may not look like a wave; it may not extend far enough to display oscillation, and it may not extend past the near zone.

It is interesting, however, that in less severe cases it is still possible to fit the Alfvén mode, even though the dissipation length predicted from the group velocity is quite a bit less than the wavelength. In these cases it is still possible to see the Alfvén mode oscillating like a wave, as though it had a much longer dissipation scale: the fits succeed with a reasonable visual appeal, and the dissipation length for the Alfvén mode comes out much longer than that predicted from the group velocity, as can be seen in the low-altitude region of the three right-most columns in Figure S.3. It is entirely possible that this represents a real prediction, and that we should be using a somewhat longer dissipation scale length at the bottom of the E region (for the Alfvén mode). The group velocity is itself difficult for us to calculate, since it requires a finite difference evaluation of the derivative of ω_{jr} (see jittery trace in the bottom right panel of Figure S.3). The fairly-low frequencies that we are evaluating are associated with k_z very close to the value where ω_{jr} becomes zero (for the Alfvén

Figure S.3: Validation of parallel wavelength and dissipation scale length. The transverse-wavelength and density are shown at the tops of the columns. For reference, the ratio of dissipation scale length to parallel wavelength under the wavepacket interpretation is shown in the bottom row, for the four modes of Section 6.

wave), and ω_{jr} is very sensitive to k_z in this area. Concern about this close proximity was actually the major reason we decided it necessary to perform the numerical integrations, as a rigorous test. However, it is not clear which of the two results is more reliable, because the bandwidth and sampling requirements for the bottom of the E region were difficult to realize for the numerical precision (double precision) and number of processors (11) that were available. Also, it may be that we are seeing only a near-zone effect.

Results for the polarization vectors are shown in Figures S.4 and S.5, for the Alfvén and Whistler modes, respectively. Since the polarization vector is arbitrary up to normalization, it is represented by plotting the ratio B_x/B_z , along with the two admittances $B_x/(\mu_0 E_y)$ and $B_x/(\mu_0 E_x)$, where μ_0 is the permeability of free space. Both magnitude and angle are shown for these complex numbers.

For the case of magnitude the agreement is really quite good, with the only exception being, again, the Alfvén mode in the lower E region when the transverse wavelength is 1000 km, and the density 10^{11} m^{-3} . For the case of phase, however, the anomalies in the lower E region extend to the other three cases, and the Whistler wave is also involved. For the most part these anomalies have a scattered appearance, suggesting that they are due either to the numerical limitations mentioned above, or to highly-variable near-zone effects. The regions where this scatter is pronounced generally exhibit evidence of either aliasing (in the case of the Whistler wave), or of a situation where the near zone extends too far from the source, such that the signal does not look completely wavelike (in the case of the Alfvén mode).

Nevertheless, some of the anomalies appear sufficiently consistent as to be worthy of comment. Looking at Figure S.4, in the lower E -region, for the 1000 km wavelength cases, the admittance $B_x/(\mu_0 E_x)$ and the ratio B_x/B_z are negated for the Alfvén wave. This is the area, also noted above, where the dissipation scale length computed from the group velocity is quite a bit less than the wavelength (bottom row of Figure S.3), and also quite a bit less than that calculated by numerical integration. Since the results seem to be consistent in the region below 115 km in altitude it is possible that this represents a real correction to the results obtained from the eigenmodes. However, we do not feel comfortable to implement these corrections until it is possible to verify them with a higher sampling density and wider bandwidth. Also, it may again be that we are seeing a near-zone effect.

Another anomaly concerns the Whistler mode in the altitude regime where, as discussed in the paper, it is probably more analogous to the fast magnetosonic wave than to the usual whistler wave. In this regime the numerical integrations are producing negative phase velocities and admittances that are conjugates of those found from the eigenvectors. These conjugations have been reversed before plotting, since the effect seemed quite clear, and so cannot be seen in the figures. We have tested these possible corrections in the model calculation by applying the conjugations and negating the wavevector over the appropriate altitude regime, and found that the effect is almost unnoticeable. Although we would like to test these results with a higher sampling density and wider bandwidth, it appears that they are not of any consequence.

We have also tested the effect of lengthening the dissipation scale length in the model calculation, since there was an altitude range where the dissipation scale length computed from the group velocity was short enough to have an effect on the Alfvén wave, in the lower E region. In this case we do find a modest effect for the case when the tangent function signature is in evidence, which is the shortest wavelength case. The tangent function signature is somewhat sharpened. The wavelength for the Alfvén wave is very short in the lower E -region, and lengthening the dissipation scale allows this very-short-wavelength mode to participate more in the dynamics. However, the effect at the top of the ionosphere is quite modest, in our testing. And there was no noticeable effect at any altitude for the other three cases, when the tangent function signature was not in evidence.

In the body of the paper we have explained that the anomalies seen in the lower E region may be simply near-zone effects that are particularly associated with the $\delta(z)$ in the source (10), and not relevant to the response of the plasma to radiation-zone waves incident from above. To resolve this matter we would like perform the calculations using a much larger number of processors, and with quadruple precision arithmetic. This would allow us to verify that the computed signal remains unchanged when the sampling density and bandwidth are increased. However, if near-zone effects are actually the culprit then numerical improvements are not going to solve the problem, and it may be necessary to appeal to a time-domain approach for validation and/or correction. But since such a time-domain simulation has not, to our knowledge, been done before, it may be that there are significant obstacles (some of which were mentioned in Section 2). Hence, it may be quite difficult to fully validate (or correct) the eigenvectors and dissipation scale lengths in the lower E region, and it may even be that circuit-theory concepts like conductivity and conductance are not really

Figure S.4: Validation of the Alfvén wave polarization vectors. The transverse-wavelength and density are shown at the tops of the columns.

Figure S.5: Validation of the Whistler wave polarization vectors. The transverse-wavelength and density are shown at the tops of the columns.

applicable there, due to a high degree of source-dependency.

However, since the ionospheric conductance is used and will likely continue to be used for quite some time, we have to do something. Therefore, it seems appropriate that for the time being we should content ourselves with the arguments given in Section 4, that radiation-zone waves traveling into the E region from above will not excite the near-zone effects that the $\delta(z)$ in the source (10) excites, and will instead excite other radiation-zone waves, which may be characterized by the eigenvectors and eigenvalues, and by the usual wave-packet interpretation.

In conclusion, although there are some possible corrections indicated from our attempts at an exact analysis (i.e., the numerical integration of equation (12)), we both do not find the corrections to be sufficiently reliable, and we do not find that the corrections would have a large effect. The altitude regime where the corrections would apply is below the transition region that has been found to block electric field penetration, and this is one likely reason that the effects do not appear very dramatic for a signal entering from above. Another is that the model calculation naturally excludes the Alfvén mode, and favors the Whistler mode, at the bottom of the E region. As long as this exclusion is a correct prediction, the behavior should not be very sensitive to the properties of the Alfvén mode at the bottom of the E region. And one thing seems almost certain, implementing corrections like these is not going to enhance conformance with electrostatic theory in any way. Thus we feel it most appropriate to implement the eigenmode-based model in its pure form, using the usual wave-packet interpretation. This model is a baseline electromagnetic model that is the most natural extension of the current electrostatic baseline.

S.6 Reviews of this and Predecessor Papers, with Replies

Reviewer/Referee = black

RBC = blue

S.6.1 Reviews of [*Cosgrove, 2016*], “Does a localized plasma disturbance in the ionosphere evolve to electrostatic equilibrium? Evidence to the contrary,” published in JGR.

S.6.1.1 Reviewer #1:

Reviewer #1 Evaluations:

Recommendation: Return to author for major revisions

Significant: There are major errors or gaps in the paper but it could still become significant with major changes, revisions, and/or additional data.

Supported: Mostly yes, but some further information and/or data are needed.

Referencing: Yes

Quality: Yes, it is well-written, logically organized, and the figures and tables are appropriate.

Data: Yes

Accurate Key Points: Yes

Reviewer #1 (Formal Review for Authors (shown to authors)): This work is worth consideration for publication if questions are addressed. The implications of this work can affect nearly the whole field of ionospheric plasma physics. Attached is my full review.

Overall impression:

- Challenging the ubiquitous electrostatics in ionospheric plasma community, this paper is exciting and engaging. Whether electromagnetic dynamics actually settle to the electrostatic state is question unanswered worth exploring. It can potentially affect most of ionospheric plasma physics. However, I have some major questions, as well as minor suggestions.

Major Questions:

(1) Section 4 (Distribution of effects around the source). Comparison to the Farley distance using plane-wave analysis may have a flaw. Going back to the heart of the Farley factor, Farley points out that by going

into a coordinate system where the z-dimension is squished by a Farley factor, one can work with Poisson's equation. The problem is in the coordinate transformation; because the z dimension is squished, everything along the z dimension is effectively brought closer to each other, where one might need to consider near-field effects. Like how ray-tracing cannot describe near-field effects, the plane wave analysis cannot fully model near-field effects. Can you rule out near-field-like effects providing the mechanism to reach the electrostatic state? Granted you are in a regime that is traditionally considered far field, and the Farley factor/coordinate-system is built derived from electrostatics, but can you address this concern?

The short answer is that near-zone effects almost certainly depend on the specific source that is driving the region of interest, and, of course, also depend on how close the source is to the region of interest. As discussed in Section 4 under the heading "Validating the Steady-State Solution," the concept of admittance arises in the context of a source-independent characterization of the system. Admittance (and other circuit quantities) are descriptions of those aspect of the system that are independent of the specific source, and so involve an inherent assumption that the source is sufficiently far away that near-zone effects can be ignored. If near-zone effects were required to produce conformance with electrostatic theory, that would be a major modification of the current understanding of electrostatic theory, and would cast severe doubt on its use when the source is in the magnetosphere.

This referee was reviewing the 2016 article [Cosgrove, 2016], where the source was in the E region. Their comment is not relevant to the 2022 paper where it is specifically stated that we are deriving the admittance of the ionosphere as seen from above. By studying the admittance we are inherently omitting near-zone effects. And, this seems physically appropriate when the source is in the magnetosphere.

However, even with respect to the 2016 article where the source was in the E region, it should be noted that near-zone effects are generally a phenomena associated with sources localized in three dimensions. These kinds of problems are normally treated by expanding the solution to Maxwell's equations as a sum of spherical harmonics, to describe the two angular dimensions. The spherical harmonics are used because they are eigenfunctions of the Laplacian, which reduces the equations to linear ones for the two angular dimensions. Substituting this expansion results in a non-linear equation for a radial function describing the variation in the third (radial) dimension, with solution that is a sum of spherical and Bessel functions: the *near zone* is the region where the Bessel function dominates, and the *far zone* is the region where the spherical function dominates.

By contrast, in both the 2016 and 2022 papers I am considering an infinite planar source, because I am deriving the Fourier components of the response. This (different) geometry calls for expanding the solution to Maxwell's equations as a sum of plane waves. Like the spherical harmonics, the plane waves are eigenfunctions of the Laplacian. Unlike the spherical harmonics, the plane waves are three-dimensional functions (not 2D), and substituting the sum of plane waves into Maxwell's equations results in a completely linear problem; there is no non-linear "radial" equation remaining to be solved. So actually the issue of near-zone and far-zone does not arise, at least not with the usual meaning. Even for the E region source in the 2016 paper, the effects that might be described by the term "near zone" effects are just that there is a possibility of the source coupling to non-propagating modes, which might be able to transport energy over short distances. This is actually the referee's next question, although as already explained, it is not relevant to the 2022 paper.

(2) The discrepancy between Alfvén wave dispersion and the electrostatic state is certainly convincing. However, can one rule out the other modes contributing to a superposition where the electrostatic state is met? One can imagine energy being siphoned out of the transmission line via coupling to modes perpendicular to B_0 . Examination of the numerical model described by Dao [2013], electric fields are not strictly confined on field lines hooked up parallel to the dynamo. It seems that the parallel-propagating Alfvén waves couple to transverse E/M waves, that couple into anti-parallel waves that send some Poynting flux, outside of the transmission line, back towards the dynamo [Figure 7.1 in Dao Thesis]. By focusing strictly on Alfvén waves that propagate along B_0 , you may have thrown away the dynamics that lead to an electrostatic state.

At least for the 2022 paper, there is no assumption that any of the waves propagate "along magnetic field lines" in any sense of the term. In equation (12) of the 2022 paper we have given the general (linearized) solution for a homogeneous plasma, and in equations (14) and (B.3) we have given approximate solutions that omit near-zone effects, and which apply to the two modes that were found capable of propagating any significant distance (at the frequencies relevant to ionospheric science). Hence, to the extent that electrostatic

theory might be produced in the ionosphere without invoking near-zone effects, the solution in terms of these two waves should be able to model it. This applies also to the solution for the vertically inhomogeneous ionosphere found in Section 5, since the only additional approximation is to model the ionosphere as a stack of thin homogeneous slabs. I have already explained, above, that in seeking to characterize the ionosphere by an admittance we have a license to omit near-zone effects.

As far as the effects seen in Figure 7.1 from the Dao thesis, to the extent they are not near-zone effects, or effects from coupling to non-propagating modes, or nonlinear effects, or artifacts from some of the modeling limitations described in Section 2 of the 2022 paper, it should be possible to produce them with the two-wave description of the 2022 paper. However, doing this would require modeling the response to a source that is localized in the transverse dimension, and this must be done by superposing a sufficiently-broad transverse spectrum of waves. While doing this is a long-term goal, that capability has not yet been developed. Also, if the effects come from coupling to non-propagating modes then they are highly dissipative, and so would tend to prevent the electric field from “mapping” through the ionosphere; so there does not seem to be any chance that they could help to establish electrostatic equilibrium. The results from Dao [2013] are very interesting and demand further investigation, but they are not directly relevant to the paper under discussion here.

By the way, since equation (12) is the general (linearized) solution for a homogeneous plasma, the near-zone effects that are omitted in the model can in principle be derived from a numerical evaluation of the integrals in equation (12). The results of an initial attempt at doing this have been described in Section S.5 of the Supplementary Information. For the particular source that was employed, it was found that near-zone effects are not in evidence, except in the lower E region. And with the source above the ionosphere, the model finds that energy does not make it down to these altitudes. Also, the source that was employed was localized in a thin sheet, whereas in the real world the source seems better thought of as a wave carrying energy into the region, which would seem less subject to near-zone effects.

In concluding this response, it should be noted that the generally accepted idea is that Alfvén waves mediate the transition to the electrostatic state. Some of the referees to follow do not seem to accept this idea, but nevertheless it is the standard idea. So it is valuable and important to show that it is not the case, even if there are possibly other ways to reach electrostatic equilibrium, that is, other ways that somehow defy the logical analysis attempted above.

(3) Figures 9-12: For most cases, the dissipation lengths were near or exceeded the Farley length. Can one rule out coupling to other modes as a means of unaccounted dissipation? However, supporting your claim, it seems that mode coupling cannot explain how the Farley length can exceed the dissipation length.

This comment is only relevant to one aspect of the comparison to electrostatic theory, concerning the dissipation scale length. And, as the referee explains, only applies to the specific cases where the dissipation length was found to exceed the Farley mapping distance, whereas sometimes the reverse is found. And regardless of any of this, in the 2022 paper the dissipation scale length was found sufficiently long that its specific value does not affect the results.

(4) Going back to the root of electrostatics. At an electromagnetic steady state, do you expect nonzero dE/dt and dB/dt ? There seems to be a disconnect between an electromagnetic steady state and an electrostatic state that is difficult to reconcile.

In the model from the 2022 paper, the solution is the driven steady-state solution, which oscillates at the source frequency ω_0 . In the mathematics it is possible for ω_0 to be zero, and the Alfvén wave is capable of propagating at zero frequency. However, perfectly frozen systems do not exist in reality, and so the most idealized case appropriate for consideration is the limit $\omega_0 \rightarrow 0$. To be fully rigorous, the answer to the referees question lies in determining if this limit is well behaved. However, since realistically the system is never perfectly frozen, we avoid this question and evaluate the model at finite ω_0 , which is chosen to be a realistic operating point for ionospheric phenomena. This is done in the 2022 paper by assuming a transverse drift (relative to the field lines) of 40 m/s, and then calculating the frequency from the transverse wavelength chosen for analysis.

In the 2016 paper we also use other transverse drift velocities, and observe without proof that the limit $\omega_0 \rightarrow 0$ appears to be well behaved. However, ω_0 is the real part of the frequency, which also has an imaginary part that remains both finite and sizable as $\omega_0 \rightarrow 0$. This imaginary part is not included in any electrostatic description, which would seem to say that electrostatic theory is different from the $\omega_0 \rightarrow 0$ limit.

(5) Do you expect a limit where the electrostatics is valid? By showing there is some limit where electrostatics work will give credibility to calculations as a sanity check.

In the context of the 2022 paper this issue is addressed by showing that the model would reproduce electrostatic theory exactly if the waves had the “right” properties (see column a of Figure 3), but that this requires artificial modification of the waves. We have not found any combination of plasma conditions and wavelength that cause the waves to have the needed properties. However, the electrostatic input admittance (i.e., the field line integrated conductivity) is reproduced very closely in some cases (see panels a1 and a2 of Figure 4), even though the electric field does not map in the expected way.

Minor Suggestions:

Figure 3: Instead of component numbers (1-12), label the ticks with actual parameters (‘Vex’, ‘Vey’, ‘Vez’, ...). Perhaps also label what the modes are (Alfven, O, X, fast, etc.); this will enable the figure to stand alone for ease of the reader. A line plot doesn’t seem appropriate, since linear interpolation (connecting the dots) between the 12 components has no physical meaning. A stem plot may keep components separate and clearly illustrate which components is zero or non-zero.

All of these suggestion have been implemented. The stem plot was a good idea.

Figure 6. The stippled areas aren’t physical, nor do they have meaning. You may just want to “white out” or “cross hatch” these areas to make clear that stippled areas show nothing meaningful.

I could not figure out a good way to “white out” or “cross hatch” the stippled area, since it’s boundary is a curve, and thresholding could not work. So I decided to leave the stippled area as is, since the description “stippled” does seem to work to identify it.

Figure 9-14: A 1 to 1 reference line where ratio of lengths are equal will aid the reader determining the difference between the Farley and dissipative lengths.

The reference lines have been added, as suggested.

Line 36: “Horizontal” is ambiguous. Horizontal at the magnetic pole is different from horizontal at the equator. Somehow make clear that B is vertical in your paper.

The paragraph has been reworded to make it clear that \vec{B}_0 is perpendicular and vertical.

Line 191: Typo? “to be written” to be followed by “as”?

The word “as” has been added, as suggested.

(13) **Reviewer comment:** Line 376. “In this case” should precede a comma.

A comma has been added, as suggested.

Line 407: Section “7 8”?

The word “and” has been added between the 7 and the 8.

Line 630: “be seen my comparing”; typo at “my”?

The word “my” has been changed to “by”, as it was supposed to be.

Line 908: “components in ‘X’”. What is X?

The reference to X has been removed, as it wasn’t needed and apparently didn’t help with clarity.

S.6.1.2 Reviewer #2:

Reviewer #2 Evaluations:

Recommendation: Publish in present form

Significant: Yes, the science is at the forefront of the discipline.

Supported: Yes

Referencing: Yes

Quality: Yes, it is well-written, logically organized, and the figures and tables are appropriate.

Data: Yes

Accurate Key Points: Yes

Reviewer #2 (Formal Review for Authors (shown to authors)):

Review of manuscript #2015JA021672: Does a localized plasma disturbance in the ionosphere evolve to electrostatic equilibrium? Evidence to the contrary, by Russell B. Cosgrove

In reviewing this manuscript I find myself in a strange position. Throughout my professional life I have considered the ionosphere (in contrast to the solar chromosphere) under dc or electrostatic aspects, whereas this paper introduces me to the ac aspects. Thus I was quite fascinated by what I read and tried to absorb. However, for a really critical evaluation I am lacking familiarity with subject and willingness to invest the time I would need for checking the derivations and results beyond plausibility. The scenario of the paper is rather special. An E region dynamo, narrow in height extent, and the allowance for short wavelengths and high winds require consideration of spatial and temporal scales that are outside most of the constellations of M-I coupling. The questions are the excitation and propagation of electromagnetic perturbations in the Alfvén or other modes under inclusion of collisions, the related energy transport, and whether electrostatic equilibrium can be reached. The paper is of high quality. Every step in deriving solutions of the full set of wave equations in a collisional medium has been described in a transparent and physically understandable way. The difference between the classical Alfvén wave admittance and the real one in the ionosphere has been very clearly elaborated. Key is the matching condition between the dynamo and the adjacent ionosphere. The comparison of the real admittance, calculated from eigenvector solutions, with the electrostatic values in Table 2 offers valuable insights. The same is true for the quantitative solutions using wavelet integrals (equation 21) laid down in Figures 9 to 14. Although the more typical application of the magnetospheric/ionospheric physicist is to consider a high-altitude generator and waves impinging from above with time scales orders of magnitude longer than treated here and to treat the ionospheric damping in electrostatic approximation, I do see the high educational value of studying the submitted manuscript. Furthermore, I realize that there are more directly applicable physical situations like ionospheric modification experiments. In summary and realizing my shortage of real competence I recommend the paper for publication in JGRA in the submitted form.

Thank you very much for agreeing to review this paper! By giving this work your scrutiny you have helped me to feel much more confident that the results are correct. You say that you are not an expert in the ionosphere, but you seem to have the expertise necessary to understand this work: I am buoyed by the degree to which you seemed to understand my main points and single them out for emphasis. I think that wave-analysis is not so common for ionospheric specialists, but is maybe much more common in other areas of space plasmas, so maybe that is what was required.

S.6.2 Reviews of “Failure of the Electrostatic Assumption via an Exact Solution for the Linear Waves of the Electromagnetic 5-Moment Fluid Equations, plus 150 km Echoes,” submitted to JGR in 2018. This was the first version of the 2022 paper.

This is the first version of the paper that eventually became the final, 2022 paper. This first version did not derive the rigorous solutions given in later versions. The solution for the eigenvectors/eigenvalues was described, but they were not assembled into a full solution for homogenous plasma. Instead, the wavepacket interpretation was described for each wave mode, as in Cosgrove [2016]. The full solution was added to later versions to address some of the difficulties of the reviewers, who were not aware that the electrostatic solution should be derivable from the “waves” (which really just means working in the Fourier domain). Also, this version included only an abbreviated description of how the results could be extended to a model for the vertically inhomogeneous ionosphere, which was described as future research. The main result was found by integrating the wavevector over altitude, to show that there was over 90° of phase rotation even for a 100 km transverse wavelength.

S.6.2.1 Reviewer #1

Reviewer #1 (Formal Review for Authors (shown to authors)):

I do not recommend publication of this paper in its present form. There are several misunderstandings of basic principles, and much unnecessary polemic against a confusing concept the author calls "the electrostatic assumption". There is also a serious mistake of physics.

The above text is a summary that does not identify any specific criticisms, except that the reviewer had a hard timing understanding my explanation of the topic. The reviewer also indicates his/her basic unhappiness about the situation. In using the word "polemic," the reviewer says that my language is too strong and is offensive to them. In using strong language like "several misunderstandings of basic principles" and "serious mistake of physics" the reviewer says that they are very unhappy about the results in the paper, and really do not want them to be true. To the extent that the review explains the reasons for using these terms, I refute them completely below.

1. There are at least three different things that may be called "electrostatic assumption":

(a) The electrostatic assumption proper, as in "Electrostatics" chapters of elementary textbooks: $\text{curl } \mathbf{E} = 0$, hence \mathbf{E} given by electric potential, governed by Poisson's equation; no magnetic field, current \mathbf{J} (if any) has $\text{curl } \mathbf{J} = 0$ (possible in conducting media only if conductivity is isotropic and either uniform or depending only on electric potential).

(b) What are called "electrostatic waves" in plasma physics: these are electromagnetic waves in which the magnetic perturbation is sufficiently small to be neglected, $\Delta \mathbf{B} \ll \Delta \mathbf{E}$ (Gaussian units), or phase velocity $\ll c$.

(c) The conventional treatment of large-scale ionospheric electrodynamics, in which it is assumed $\text{curl } \mathbf{E} = 0$ but the electric potential is determined, not from Poisson's equation but by relating \mathbf{E} to \mathbf{J} through the ionospheric Ohm's law and requiring $\text{div } \mathbf{J} = 0$; magnetic disturbance field assumed small compared to geomagnetic field (but not zero); time derivatives in momentum equation neglected and plasma flow assumed given by $\mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}$ drift.

The above concerns the Introduction section of the paper. There is no criticism of the paper. The reviewer attempts to give his or her own definitions for the topics in the paper (Case (b) and Case (c) are fairly close, see more below). These provide insight into the nature of the definition that the reviewer would understand. I have used this knowledge to make the Introduction more palatable to readers like the reviewer.

2. The main objective of the paper as well as of a published earlier one by the author [Cosgrove 2016] is to criticize the "electrostatic assumption". The discussion is very confusing: the verbal definition given by the author clearly corresponds to (a), but the arguments seem to be directed against (b) or sometimes (c). To my mind, the criticisms based on wave models are mostly irrelevant. Case (a) does not have any waves (except possibly in some highly contrived situations), and it never really applies in the ionosphere. Case (b) is just an example of terminology not to be taken too literally (there are others, e.g. "magnetosphere" is not a sphere): anybody working in the field knows that "electrostatic waves" are really electromagnetic, and that the validity of neglecting $\Delta \mathbf{B}$ must be verified in every instance. Case (c) invokes assumptions that limit its validity to time scales longer than wave propagation times.

The above concerns the Introduction section of the paper, where the topics are being defined. The reviewer says that it was not clear I was discussing Case (c), as opposed to Case (a) (using the reviewer's categorization for the present). In fact, the first sentence of the paper defines the main topic of the paper, which is pretty close to what the reviewer calls Case (c). Later, the fifth paragraph (Line 62) distinguishes Case (b) as a related but distinct case. However, apparently, the reviewer could not follow the explanations, and so I have rewritten them to be, hopefully, more clear. However, it is very hard for me to understand how the reviewer could have so dramatically misinterpreted the opening sentence as to think it addressed Case (a). The opening sentence reads "The assumption of electrostatic equilibrium in ionospheric plasma physics [Cowling, 1945; Martyn, 1955; Dagg, 1957a, 1957b; Farley, 1959; Farley, 1960; Spreiter and Briggs, 1961] begins with the assumption that setting the time derivatives to zero in the combined Maxwell and

fluid-momentum equations (hereafter, Maxwell/momentum equations) determines a valid approximation for the electric field, which is obtained by solving the resulting elliptic equation for the electric potential.” Note that my sentence reads “in ionospheric physics” and identifies the “fluid-momentum equation,” neither of which are relevant to Case (a). Case (a) has nothing to do with fluid theory or the ionosphere; it involves only the Maxwell equations. Also, the references given all discuss Case (c) and ionospheric physics.

In fact, I think my definition is quite precise. Setting the time derivatives to zero in the Maxwell equations immediately gives $\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{E} = 0$ and $\vec{J} = \vec{\nabla} \times \vec{B} / \mu_0$, so that $\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{J} = \vec{\nabla} \cdot (\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{B}) / \mu_0 = 0$, which are two of the equations given by the reviewer. Setting the time derivatives to zero in the momentum equations gives “steady state” expressions for the ion and electron velocities, which, using a well known procedure, are the equations commonly solved to obtain what the reviewer calls the ionospheric Ohm’s law, $\vec{J} = \overleftarrow{\sigma} \vec{E}$. This is the third equation mentioned by the reviewer. Hence, it should be easy to see that the definition given in the first paragraph of the paper corresponds with what the reviewer called Case (c) (although the reviewer does add one extraneous provision that isn’t normally used, which is that the “plasma” $\vec{E} \times \vec{B}$ drifts). Also, it is well known that combining these three equations gives an elliptic equation for the electric potential, as stated in the paper.

With respect to Case (b), Line 62 of the original submission reads, “A related but distinct concept to that of electrostatic equilibrium is that of electrostatic plasma waves [e.g., Bernstein, 1958, Dougherty and Farley, 1963, Farley, 1963], where the time derivative is set to zero only in Faraday’s law (i.e., $\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{E}$ set to zero), but the other time derivatives are retained.” Setting the time derivative ($\partial \delta \vec{B} / \partial t$) to zero in Faraday’s law essentially requires that $\delta \vec{B}$ is zero (or, sufficiently small), as indicated by the reviewer for Case (b). Line 66 refers the reader to Section 2 for more detail. Beginning on Line 200 of Section 2 there is quite a bit of additional detail, including specific mention of the requirement that $\delta \vec{B} \cong 0$. I do not, however, give the particular inequality given by the reviewer, because I don’t feel that it can be proven to be a sufficient condition. Rather, the validity of “electrostatic waves” (as Case (b) is termed both in the article, and by the reviewer) is examined using the full machinery derived in the paper.

In writing a paper it is appropriate that I give my own definition for the topic, and there is no need for it to correspond with a definition given by a reviewer, which may not be accurate to what I want to discuss. A solution obtained by solving the identified equations with the identified time derivatives set to zero, etc., is the definition of my topic. The reviewer does not say what part of this they do not understand. The reviewer does not identify any error in the paper.

The above also states “. . . criticisms based on wave models are mostly irrelevant.” I will refute this below, where the point is raised again. But let me first mention that the reviewer themselves identified the Case (b) as one of waves, and also said “Case (c) invokes assumptions that limit its validity to time scales longer than wave propagation times.” So the reviewers position against “wave models” seems to be somewhat inconsistent.

3. The discussion of sources and boundary conditions (lines 25-47) contains a misunderstanding. It is true that steady-state solutions of Maxwell’s equations require the presence of sources somewhere, but if one is solving the equations within a limited volume of space only, with boundary conditions specified, it is NOT true that the sources must be WITHIN the volume - they may be outside, indicated by appropriate boundary conditions (e.g., I have a reading lamp that runs on DC from a battery; if I put the lamp inside a large metal box and connect it to the battery outside the box, I can certainly describe the field inside the box by electrostatic equations.)

The above concerns the Introduction section, and only the Introduction section. The purpose of the criticized material was to address a possible objection to the goals of the paper, where some might argue that since the electrostatic solution does solve certain related equations, it must be the physical solution. The material seeks to establish that this argument is not air tight, and thus that it is appropriate to check if the electrostatic solution is the physical one by the more rigorous means employed in the paper. What the reviewer has written is nearly correct, but does not contradict the essential point made in those lines (or anywhere else) of the paper. The key word is “appropriate,” in that the enforced boundary conditions must match very closely to those that would be produced by a real and narrow source that lies almost completely outside the boundary. When boundary conditions are chosen arbitrarily or incompletely, they may not match to any real source, and so a non-physical solution may be obtained. This is the main point

that was made, and it is not contradicted by what the reviewer has written.

I said the reviewer is “nearly” correct because there does remain a minor technical disagreement. In the material referred to by the reviewer, the paper is asserting that the electrostatic solution is (contained in) a solution of the source-free equations of motion, if it is physical (i.e., if it does not have a singularity). This point may be proven simply by noting that any valid solution must be an analytic function, and so a solution of the source free equations (inside some region) can be analytically continued to a solution over all of space. This implies that the solution should decay toward thermal equilibrium (since no sources), and so if it is unchanging it must actually be thermal equilibrium. The only way around this is if the solution is singular, which is therefore the conclusion. The reviewer has not made any argument against this reasoning, and may have read more into the point than was intended.

However, I have decided that this point is rather technical, and does not really say very much about whether electrostatic theory might be useful as an approximation. So I have omitted it in later versions of the paper. The response to the next reviewer question includes a much more compelling reason for testing electrostatic theory.

4. Another misunderstanding is the statement (lines 74-75) that “the wave equations are obtained by performing a Fourier transform in space and a Laplace transform in time”. The wave equation is one with the operator $d^2/dt^2 - V^2 d^2/dx^2$; Fourier and Laplace transforms are simply mathematical techniques for solving equations, useful under certain restricted conditions. Which one to use in which dimension is a question of convenience and has nothing to do with physics. The convention of complex frequency and real wave-number is convenient when solving an initial value problem: given a periodic spatial disturbance at $t=0$, how does the wave evolve in time? The opposite convention of real frequency and complex wave-number is equally convenient when solving a boundary value problem: given a periodic temporal disturbance at a boundary surface (e.g., in Farley 1959 or in the author’s figure 3), how does the wave propagate into the interior? There is nothing unphysical or otherwise wrong with (lines 81-82) “a Fourier transform in time and two dimensions of space, and a Laplace transform in the remaining spatial dimension” if it helps to solve the equation (e.g., Laplace transform in one spatial dimension and Fourier transform in the other two is standard technique for solving Laplace/Poisson equation in three-dimensional planar geometry.)

The above again concerns the Introduction section of the paper. Again, the purpose of the criticized material was to address a possible objection to the goals of the paper, where some might argue that since the electrostatic solution does solve certain related equations, it must be the physical solution. The material seeks to establish that this argument is not air tight, and thus that it is necessary (or reasonable) to check if the electrostatic solution is the physical one by the more direct means employed in the paper. The point in the paper is, again, that an arbitrarily or incompletely specified boundary condition may not correspond to a real source, and so it is possible for electrostatic theory to give an inappropriate answer. This motivates the analysis in the paper where we actually test this question.

In this case there is a much more compelling argument for doubting electrostatic theory, than in the answer to the previous question. The reviewer says, “There is nothing unphysical or otherwise wrong with (lines 81-82) ‘a Fourier transform in time and two dimensions of space, and a Laplace transform in the remaining spatial dimension’ if it helps to solve the equation.” I am in the difficult position of having to say that this approach may sometimes give inappropriate results. I have in fact already said this in *Cosgrove*, and this may have been a difficult thing for the reviewer to hear. The reviewer says that it is a “question of convenience,” whether we solve the equations of motion for the initial value problem, or for a boundary value problem, that it “has nothing to do with physics.” This is in contradiction with what was asserted in the paper, and in *Cosgrove* (Section 7).

To elaborate on the arguments given in the paper, the laws of physics are framed within the causative structure of spacetime, which allows for formulation of the initial value problem: the allowed instantaneous physical states of the system are parameterized by configuration variables, and the equations of motion define how the configuration changes with time. Because the time evolution is unique, the configuration space at any instant of time maps one-to-one to the physical solution space, meaning that any configuration can be chosen, and there corresponds a single, physical time-evolving solution. Here, “instant of time,” is more precisely a space-like surface in spacetime, and specifying the configuration means specifying an analytic function for the distribution of events on that surface. That this is the proper framing of the physical problem is ignored

in solving the boundary value problem that comes from making the electrostatic assumption.

In making the electrostatic assumption there arises a boundary value problem, meaning that it is necessary to specify the events on a time-like surface. But unlike the events on a space-like surface, the set of events on a time-like surface do not map one-to-one to the solution space, because only certain temporal sequences of events are allowed; the sequence of events must be as predicted by the (source-free) equations of motion, which places a constraint on the allowed boundary conditions. In using the electrostatic assumption we ignore this constraint, and specify the boundary condition (which is a sequence of events) without checking to see if the constraint is satisfied. The only way around taking this risk (that we are specifying an unphysical boundary condition) is to actually solve the equations of motion.

In fact it can be seen that the electrostatic boundary condition is not really correct. The boundary condition in electrostatic theory is normally specified by taking the Fourier transform in time, and then solving for a Fourier component. If the frequency is non-zero the boundary condition is oscillation over infinite time, but more commonly the frequency is taken to be zero, so that the boundary condition is no-change over infinite time. It is immediately apparent that this does not match to the boundary condition that arises from the physical initial value problem, where there is initially an undisturbed plasma, until the source turns on, and then the source runs for a finite amount of time, and (we assume) approaches a steady state.

That this difference may be very important can be seen by looking at the general expression for the conductivity, which for example can be found in equation A9 of [Cosgrove 2016]. The conductivity depends on the frequency ω , but it does not depend on the wavevector \vec{k} . Since the Fourier transform has been used ω is a real number, whereas if the Laplace transform had been used as for the initial value problem, ω would be a complex number. This is a serious issue because Figure 16 of [Cosgrove 2016] (right hand column) shows that including the imaginary part of ω dramatically changes the conductivity. The reason for this is exemplified in Figure 8 of [Cosgrove 2016] (left hand column, for the Alfvén wave), which shows that the imaginary part of ω remains large as the real part goes to zero. This occurs because the imaginary part of ω determines the dissipation-rate of the wave, and the dissipation is expected to remain as the real part of frequency goes to zero.

So this shows that there is a very concrete difference between the solutions found through the Laplace-transform/initial-value approach and the Fourier-transform/boundary-value approach. The conductivities will be different, and this means that the conditions satisfied on the boundary may be significantly different not just in the distant past before the source turned on, but at all times.

The difference between the two solutions may be viewed as the difference between two different operating points on the dispersion surface. I have to be careful with terminology because the term “dispersion relation” is generally applied to specific wave modes, whereas by “dispersion surface” I mean all the solutions of the complex-plane-extension of the equation that arises in solving the eigenvalue problem for the linearized equations of motion, which is $\det(\omega I - H_5(\vec{k})) = 0$, where \det indicates the determinant of the matrix, and H_5 is the matrix defined in the paper. In solving the initial value problem ω is complex and \vec{k} real, because the Laplace transform is used for time and the Fourier transform for space. The 16 solutions found in this case give the causal wave modes that enter into the exact initial-value or driven-steady-state solutions of the equations of motion. When sources are absent these modes decay with time according to the imaginary part of ω , and so we say that they are causal.

But if we extend the domain of the determinant equation to include complex values of \vec{k} additional solutions become possible. For example, there are solutions with ω entirely real and k_z complex, which are associated with solving the equations of motion when the Laplace transform has been applied to the z -axis and the Fourier transform to time and the two remaining spatial axes. In Cosgrove [2016] it was explained that when $\omega = 0$ only one of these solutions has all finite components in the eigenvector, and that this is the “usual” electrostatic solution. Specifically this solution was given in equation (19) of Cosgrove [2016]. It decays with the Farley mapping distance and has the “usual,” zero-frequency conductivities found by setting $\omega = 0$ in the conductivity equations (e.g., equations (A9) of *Cosgrove [2016]*). *As already noted, these conductivities are different from those found when solving the initial value problem, where ω has a substantial imaginary part that must be retained. In addition it seems almost certain that the real part of k_z (wavelength) will be different, and that the eigenvectors will be different, and so the plasma configuration should be quite different. These are different solutions that come from very different operating points on the*

dispersion surface, with the electrostatic solution having ω real and k_z complex, and the initial-value (and driven-steady-state) solution having ω complex and k_z real.

Since the solutions are different, they cannot both be the physical solution. By virtue of the arguments based in causality, it is clear that the initial-value and driven-steady-state solutions are the ones guaranteed to be physical. So we must prefer the driven-steady-state solution over the electrostatic solution, and expect that these two may be quite different in some cases. In the event that they are in fact quite different, the reason for the failure of the electrostatic solution can be found in the choice of boundary condition, which did not actually match to the condition that arises from causal evolution. Hence we have a very good reason for testing electrostatic theory, which we do by comparing it to an electromagnetic solution that should contain it, if the electrostatic solution is accurate.

The above is an elaboration on the arguments put forth in the paper, which are also presented in *Cosgrove*. **The reviewer does not counter these arguments in any way. The reviewer does not mention the discussion of causality and the initial value problem that are given in both papers.** While the reviewer is correct that “The opposite convention of real frequency and complex wave-number is equally convenient when solving a boundary value problem,” this is irrelevant to the assertion made in the paper, which is that the electrostatic solution is not guaranteed to be physical, and that therefore it is appropriate to undertake the investigation in the paper. In order to keep other readers from getting side-tracked in this way, in later versions I have significantly reduced the discussion of why electrostatic theory needs to be tested. In the final 2022 version I have essentially eliminated this discussion, and referred to *Cosgrove* for the heavy lifting on this apparently touchy subject. If the electromagnetic answer comes out different from the electrostatic answer than that in-and-of-itself is an important result, and afterward maybe the community will be more interested in hearing how the electrostatic theory could have gone wrong.

The reviewer also makes a semantical objection to the use of the term “wave equations,” which I think I agree with. To address this objection I have changed my terminology generally to refer to “equations of motion,” which also helps to make my point.

5. The serious mistake of physics, which is also present in the previously published paper [Cosgrove 2016] and affects the conclusions of both, is the author’s assumption (lines 224-287 and elsewhere) that an ionospheric wave can couple to a source (e.g., neutral-wind dynamo) ONLY if its wavelength and its transverse phase velocity match the source velocity and wavelength, respectively. The paper does not explain clearly what is “transverse phase velocity”; it is $V_{\text{phase}} k_x / k$ where k_x is the wave-number in the direction of source motion (horizontal in figure 3), but a casual reader might misinterpret it as $V_{\text{phase}} k_x / k$. The assumption is that coupling is possible only for wave modes for which (figure 3 geometry, θ = angle from vertical)

$V_{\text{phase}} = V_{\text{source}} \sin \theta$ where θ is the propagation direction. For Alfvén waves, $V_{\text{phase}} = V_A \cos \theta$ and the coupling condition is

$\tan \theta = V_A / V_{\text{source}}$ which can always be satisfied by choosing θ . For sound waves (a simpler example than the whistler mode waves invoked by the author), $V_{\text{phase}} = V_s$ independent of θ , and the coupling condition is

$$\sin \theta = V_s / V_{\text{source}}$$

which can be satisfied only if $V_s < V_{\text{source}}$. The author’s assumption would imply that an obstacle moving through a fluid can couple to the fluid if it is moving supersonically, but not if it is moving subsonically --- which is obviously absurd.

In the linear approximation it can be proven that “an ionospheric wave can couple to a source (e.g., neutral-wind dynamo) ONLY if its wavelength and its transverse phase velocity match the source velocity and wavelength,” and so what the reviewer has characterized as a “serious mistake of physics” is not any such thing. To make this clear an exact solution to the (linearized) equations of motion has been included in all later versions of the paper. A source is defined that oscillates with frequency ω_0 , and which is a pure sinusoid in the transverse spatial dimension (transverse to the geomagnetic field). The exact solution then finds that the steady-state response oscillates exactly at frequency ω_0 , and is exactly a (matching) pure sinusoid in the transverse spatial dimension. (The source is equation (10), and the solution is equation (12),

in the final 2022 paper.) This is all that there is to the selection criterion that is used in the paper. So there is no assumption like what the reviewer is suggesting, it is proven.

The best way I can understand what the reviewer is saying is that they may be thinking of non-linear effects. But in this paper we analyze the linear case, and why linearization is appropriate has been explained thoroughly in the paper, and has also been explained in the responses to other reviewer questions. So I will not include that material here.

The fallacy lies in the implicit assumption that coupling must be to a single simple wave, overlooking the possibility that coupling can also occur by modification of the entire flow field when the waves propagate sufficiently fast relative to motion of the source. All the conclusions about non-coupling modes, both in this paper and in Cosgrove 2016, are thereby invalidated.

The paper does not assume “that coupling must be to a single simple wave”. All the waves are considered, and four waves are found capable of operating in the frequency/wavelength range relevant to ionospheric phenomena. Of these four only two can transmit energy more than a few kilometers, and these two are included in the analysis using a best-case assumption for energy transfer through the ionosphere (and are both included in the model that is completed in later versions of the paper). Three other radio frequency waves are found to be much too high in frequency, and anyway they do not follow geomagnetic field lines and so could not facilitate the mapping of electric field along geomagnetic field lines. Since there are 16 equations in the electromagnetic five-moment fluid equations, there are 8 potential waves (each wave corresponds to two eigenvectors, one for forward propagation, and one for reverse propagation). This leaves one other possible wave, which was found in the paper to be evanescent, and therefore not capable of transmitting energy. Hence, all the modes have been included in the analysis, and all those capable of transmitting energy are included in the calculations.

Also, the reviewer asserts “. . . overlooking the possibility that coupling can also occur by modification of the entire flow field when the waves propagate sufficiently fast relative to motion of the source.” I am not able to relate this to any kind of physical reasoning. No physical principle is invoked, and no equation is mentioned. The idea of “modification of the entire flow field” sounds non-causal. So the only way I can interpret this statement is as an appeal to non-linearity, in which case it does not deny the results in the paper. The paper analyzes the linear problem and that has been well justified, both in the paper and in these responses.

The paper absolutely allows for wave propagation that is faster (or much faster) than the source velocity. Note that the source has infinite size in two dimensions and does not change its location, so there is no stacking up of waves as in the shock-wave case that the reviewer mentioned; that is a non-linear phenomenon and so is not a suitable analogy. The selection criteria used in the paper has been proven by an exact solution (see previous response), and is also highly intuitive.

The intuition for coupling into the plasma is described in the beginning of Section 4. Basically, think of a source that tickles the edge of a large plasma “pool.” For energy to be transported any significant distance away from the source, propagating modes have to be excited, or otherwise there will be only a near-zone effect. The modes that will be excited are those that match well to the tickling motions, whereas modes that do not match well will be confounded. Expressing the equations of motion in the Fourier domain we see that different Fourier components are coupled only by non-linear terms, and so for a very slight tickling where the source is a pure sinusoid, only the (transverse) wavelength of the source should be excited. The excitations should also match the frequency of the source. If there is more than one propagating mode with this transverse wavelength and frequency, they may both be excited, and these may have different wavelengths in the remaining direction (i.e., the direction away from the source and into the plasma). This is the intuition that applies to the linear domain, that is for small excitations. And this way of thinking is well supported by well accepted physical examples, such as transmission by an antenna and excitation of resonances in a structure or circuit.

The next step is to deal with a smaller “pool” of plasma where the waves may reach the other edge and reflect back. The transmission line theory invoked in the paper allows for analysis of the steady state reached after the waves bounce back and forth as many times as is needed (to reach steady state). Under the traditional MI coupling model, this is the process that is supposed to lead to electrostatic equilibrium, and the reviewer even seems to acknowledge this. So the analysis in the paper tests whether this process

really will lead to electrostatic equilibrium, or whether the steady state may instead be markedly different. How much non-linearities can modify this process is a whole other question, which should not apply for sufficiently small-amplitude disturbances.

6. The only valid results that could be shaped into a publishable paper are the descriptions of various wave properties and modes. The author should delete completely all polemics about electrostatic approaches (anything necessary to be said about them has been said already, at more than sufficient length, in Cosgrove 2016), which includes changing the title and completely rewriting the abstract.

It is odd to use the terms “polemic” and “criticism,” instead of the more even-handed term “analysis.” It is odd to refer to my earlier paper with “anything necessary to be said about them has been said already, at more than sufficient length.” It sounds as though the reviewer is not denying the paper is correct, but never-the-less feels it should not be said.

Almost all the objections were focused on material in the Introduction, which material served only to provide a reason for the analysis (and these objections have all been refuted). Otherwise, the reviewer has stated “All the conclusions about non-coupling modes, both in this paper and in Cosgrove 2016, are thereby invalidated.” But the selection criteria have been proven by an exact solution (see two responses previous). The idea that an antenna transmits waves according to its size and transmitter frequency is well established, and the reviewer cannot criticize it unless they wish to appeal to nonlinear phenomena.

At the beginning of the review, the reviewer states “. . . the criticisms based on wave models are mostly irrelevant.” He/she seems to believe that the “wave model” is somehow incomplete, like there is a separate DC response that is not included. Actually, I have found this to be a common misconception. So I have added material to the paper that demonstrates a complete and general solution to the linearized electromagnetic 5-moment fluid equations. This is the solution that was used above to prove the selection criteria (coupling criteria). Hence, the paper can be understood as an analysis of this exact solution, and deriving from it an approximate calculation for the vertically inhomogeneous ionosphere. The approximations are all carefully documented, so that future researchers may continue to evaluate them.

So the most valid way to interpret the reviewers statements is as an appeal to non-linear phenomena to save electrostatic theory. This is the only way to interpret the otherwise meaningless statement “. . . coupling can also occur by modification of the entire flow field when the waves propagate sufficiently fast relative to motion of the source.” But even if it were the case that nonlinear phenomena create electrostatic equilibrium (highly unlikely!), it would not make either paper wrong; rather, the papers would have shown that linear phenomena cannot produce electrostatic equilibrium, a very interesting and unexpected result, especially considering that electrostatic theory is itself linearized in the same way!

There is something causing a level of emotion in the reviewer, and I think it has to be acknowledged that there is a probable conflict of interest. The reviewer was unable to identify any technical flaws in the paper, but they really cannot accept that the results might be true. So they have attempted to block publication through grandiose condemnations without technical merit.

The following should also be noted:

(a) The terminology for various wave modes now used by the author is totally confusing. It is true that there is not complete unanimity among various subfields on terminology, but this does not give the author a license to redefine established terms according to his whims.

I did my best to use the most common terminology that seemed applicable. The naming of waves is well known to result in a zoo of terminology. Sometimes waves are named for the sources that commonly produce the waves. Sometimes waves are named for the simplifications that go into deriving their dispersion relations. Sometimes waves are named for observational characteristics. Sometimes waves are named for people. Sometimes the same waves are obtained in different approximations, and given different names. Sometimes waves just have different names in different fields. The reviewer did not say which of the waves he/she thought was ill named, nor suggest any names that should be used. In revisiting my naming scheme, I can find nothing to change. Again, the reviewer has used strong language (“totally confusing. . . does not give the author a license to redefine established terms according to his whims”) without sufficient explanation, and thus has revealed an emotional reaction to this paper.

(b) The basic equations (between lines 166 and 167) (credited to Schunk and Nagy 2000, but I cannot find them in their book) are missing some terms: (1) gravity in the momentum equations (can be neglected

only if all motions are horizontal, which manifestly is not the case for several of the wave modes discussed), (2) the term $Q(v_i - v_n)$ in the momentum equations (momentum loading from photoionization).

I did forget to mention that I omitted gravity and photoionization. I have corrected this in the revision. Of course, no one would argue that gravity or photoionization are required to achieve electrostatic equilibrium.

It should be pointed out that all effects of waves on the neutrals are neglected -- neutral equations are not included.

I have added this to the revision, although it's not very relevant. No one would argue that neutral dynamics is needed to achieve electrostatic equilibrium.

I would not consider the thermal equilibrium state of the ionosphere "trivial" (line 174) -- not with gravity included.

The reviewer is correct that including gravity makes the equilibrium non-trivial. But I didn't include gravity, and again, no one would argue that gravity is needed to achieve electrostatic equilibrium.

[end of referee's report]

S.6.2.2 Reviewer #2

This paper investigated a fundamental assumption used extensively in ionospheric physics related to the electrostatic "mapping" of electric field between E and F region. Using the five-moment equations for ionospheric plasma species together with the full Maxwell's equations, the author also tried to test a hypothesis of using electrostatic waves as approximations for electromagnetic waves in ionospheric dynamics. Based on the linearized five-moment equations plus the Maxwell equations, the wave modes are studied using the eigenvectors of the system. Based on the reviewer's understanding, this theoretical study found that 1) for transverse scale larger than 0.1 km, the (linear) electrostatic modes differ significantly from the electromagnetic modes; 2) electric field structures with transverse scale size < 100 km do not map from 400 km to 100 km in altitude; 3) the effective ionospheric admittance (or conductance which is used more commonly in M-I coupling) is a function of transverse scale size. 1) and 2) are not so surprising given the fact of not using an electrostatic assumption, and 3) is quite interesting and may have significant impact on future studies of M-I coupling.

Ionospheric models are almost exclusively electrostatic, and this includes models that operate over the transverse scale range from 1 km to 100 km: so item (1) will (unfortunately) come as an unpleasant surprise to the people who make and use these models. Also, under electrostatic theory, 100 km transverse scale electric fields easily map through the ionosphere, and 10 km transverse scales also map: so item (2) differs from the results under the electrostatic assumption by at least a factor of 10. So I think all three of these results will come as a surprise to those who believe electrostatic theory is reasonably accurate, and there are many such people in the ionospheric community.

The reviewer found this kind of study intriguing, and theoretical studies focusing on basic ionospheric physics should always be encouraged in general. However, there are some major concerns about the clarity of the methodology and the applicability of the theoretical conclusions to complicated ionospheric configurations. In my own opinion, the title, abstract and conclusion should also be improved or adjusted based on proper physical interpretation of the results. Therefore the reviewer does not think the manuscript ready for publish in JGR yet, before a significant amount of improvement/clarification is done.

This study develops methodology that could be applied to more complicated configurations, but we have to walk before we can run. The purpose of this study is to show that electrostatic and electromagnetic theories can sometimes differ in important ways, in order to motivate the much bigger job of executing and testing the model that is proposed (which has been completed in later additions of the paper). If the two theories disagree for the simplest of plasma configurations (a homogeneous plasma), well that has never been shown before, and it gives reason to work more on the topic.

I don't actually find any reference to the conclusion in the reviewers comments below, so I will comment here. The concluding section has been reworked and hopefully is less antagonizing now. But to be clear, I cannot find any problem with the physical interpretation given in the original paper. I hope that the new

Section 2 will provide the needed additional rigor to convince the reviewer that this material should go out to the broader community. It is difficult material with lots of subtlety, and so I can only be so successful in making it easy to understand. But there are now many more equations to back things up, and so the correctness of the physical interpretation should now be connected to the correctness of the mathematical development, which should allow for a more concrete discussion.

Major concerns

The reviewer's major concerns are a) in the abstract, b) in the description related to equation (1) and c) in the derived eigenvectors shown in Figure 4.

a) In the Abstract:

In the abstract, the author said “the electrostatic assumption has not been validated, either observationally or in theory.” This statement is not quite true since observations have already shown the mapping of large-scale magnetospheric electric field to ionospheric reference altitudes (e.g., Figure 2 of Gonzales et al. 1980). The validity of the electrostatic assumption and electric field mapping actually depends on the spatial and temporal scale of the problem of interest. Therefore it is not accurate to say that the electrostatic mapping of electric field has not been seen in datasets, it is more about the limitation of the mapping assumptions.

I have changed the abstract to read “...and observational evidence is weak” in the revision. The Gonzales 1980 paper used an incoherent scatter radar (ISR), and these measure electric field in the F region, well above the E region altitudes where I am finding that mapping can fail. ISR can only be used for E region electric fields through the assumption that there *is* mapping. Also, mapping from the magnetosphere to the F region *is* predicted by the electromagnetic theory; it is predicted because of the very long wavelength of the Alfvén wave. So the Gonzalez 1980 paper, while important for other reasons, does not actually address a case where different results are expected.

I believe this paper is the first time significant deviations between the electrostatic and electromagnetic theories have been found (for the ionosphere). So what is needed now is an observational/experimental validation that addresses cases where the two theories give different results, and this could not have been done before in any definitive way, because the opposing electromagnetic theory (the one from this paper) did not exist before. So this is really what I meant, although I agree that my language could have been misinterpreted, and so the revision is an improvement.

In the abstract “Using an exact solution for the Maxwell..” – the results presented in the manuscript is not an exact solution of the full equation set (are exact solutions to the coupled fluid/Maxwell equations ever exist?), rather, it's only possible to derive the Eigen system of the linearized equations, which is not an exact “solution”.

I have added the word “linearized” to the sentence in question (line 20). (The word “linear” was in the title, by the way, and still is.) I did obtain an exact solution to the linearized equations, and the revised paper has been modified to make this clear (Section 2). (Of course, it is not anything amazing to have an exact solution to a set of linear equations.)

In the abstract “using either electrostatic waves or the electrostatic assumption can lead to results that are not just quantitatively wrong, but also qualitatively wrong—such as failure to predict instability”. This statement is likely too strong especially given that no observational evidence is provided in this study. While it is fine to present results which contradict previous studies, the author needs to provide more quantitative evidence to convince potential readers about why all these assumptions are wrong, how much they are off compared to the results presented in this study, etc.

I have removed that sentence from the abstract. However, at the risk of being argumentative, I do want to say that I don't think the observations are all that relevant at this time. From the well accepted laws of fundamental physics, when there is an electromagnetic solution that appears air-tight, it has to be considered above any electrostatic solution, unless there actually exist observations that definitively indicate otherwise.

It is very unlikely that there could have been a paper making such contrary observations, since the results I'm presenting here are new. There are some clear distinctions in the predictions of the two theories. One I will mention is the phase rotation of over 90° , in going from the F region to the E region, for any scale size less than 100 km. (The phase rotation under electrostatic theory is zero for all scale sizes.) Another has to do with the relationship between field-aligned current and transverse electric field in a homogeneous plasma excited by a dynamo on one edge, there is a 90° difference in the predicted phase relationships between these two quantities. These two are both major deviations from electrostatic theory; they are important wave effects, and they are quantitative predictions. And then there are also the differences in conductivity, and in dissipation scale length, which are also quantitative differences that are not minor.

Researchers should try to test these predictions, and if they ever find a case where the electrostatic theory works better than the electromagnetic theory there will be quite a conundrum. But until that happens, I feel it is irresponsible to continue using the electrostatic theory in cases where it gives a different prediction, without at least citing this work. Of course, I understand that this is because I have confidence in my analysis, whereas the rest of the world may not be ready to believe it yet. It is for this reason that the abstract should be somewhat bold. I don't want this paper to be ignored as just another finding that the two theories agree except for very minor differences; there appear to be major differences; so I think the abstract needs to make people take notice and deal with it. My 2016 paper has been ignored so far, even though it shows important differences also.

b) In Equation (1)

Equation (1) is a relative comprehensive set of fluid equations for the dynamic evolution of partially ionized plasmas (without coupling back to neutrals). The author needs to justify why so many terms are needed given that they are different by orders of magnitude when applying to ionospheric plasma. For example, for most ionospheric plasma phenomena of interest, the time derivative terms in the fluid equations are much smaller than the other terms. This is simply seen in the ion velocity equation (the fourth equation), the time derivative term has a magnitude of $1/\tau$, where τ is the response time to a new set of forces, or a time scale of interest. The Lorentz term has a magnitude of Ω_i , which is the ion gyro frequency. Thus for most ionospheric phenomena of interest, $1/\tau \ll \Omega_i$. A similar analysis can be done for the friction term as well since $1/\tau \ll \nu_{in}$. Thus the acceleration term can be neglected. The convective term is also small according to the same rationale, and none of these terms are scale dependent in equation (1). Therefore although the time derivative terms may introduce interesting wave dynamic, are they really dominate the whole solution to equation (1)? Also the electron-ion collision frequency is at least one order of magnitude lower than the electron-neutral and ion neutral frequency across all altitude range in the E and lower F ionosphere, so terms associated with ν_{ie} (ν_{ei}) are also negligible in equation (1).

The reviewer brings up some very interesting questions! However, they are really relevant to different questions than the one I am addressing in this paper, which is whether electrostatic theory really leads to a reasonable approximation for all the cases that we currently think it does. To answer this question, it is certainly permissible and in fact desirable to not make approximations of any kind, to the extent possible. Any approximation I make opens-up a possible objection. The electrostatic theory exists because it is not so easy to refute directly the arguments that go into it. However, if I can show differences using an approach that does not make approximations, then it means that somehow the arguments for the electrostatic theory are subtly wrong. This is a publishable result, whether or not I am able to convincingly refute the usual arguments for electrostatic theory through intellectual discourse. With this goal in mind there is value in using equations that are more accurate than necessary, if it does not prevent their solution. The paper is already very long, and there simply isn't room for such things, even if I were able to word them convincingly.

I also want to mention that the time derivative terms do not only describe the acceleration and convection, they also describe the decay of the disturbance as energy is dissipated. So there is possibly more risk than the reviewer is considering, in setting a time derivative to zero. This is just about being cautious.

A more direct answer that addresses one specific part of the question is as follows: If an equation is linearly coupled to other equations, then before setting a time derivative to zero, it is really necessary to check the sensitivity in the other equations. So to do it properly we should first diagonalize the equations (I'm assuming we are talking about the Fourier transformed and linearized equation set). To do this, let U

be the matrix with the eigenvectors of H_5 as columns. Then the matrix $D = -iU^{-1}H_5U$ is diagonal, and the equation of motion for the j th component becomes,

$$\frac{\partial X'_j}{\partial t} + D_{jj}X'_j = 0, \quad (\text{S.3})$$

where $\vec{X}' = U^{-1}\vec{X}$, and there is one of these scalar equations for each eigenvector (See equation (2) in the revised paper). So X'_j is the amplitude of the j 'th mode, and these are just the same waves discussed in the paper. Now the evolution is completely decoupled, and we can clearly see the effect of setting a time derivative to zero. If we set the j th time derivative to zero, it means that X'_j must be zero, and so there can be no energy in that wave mode. So this allows us to clearly understand the effect of setting a time derivative to zero, and it amounts to discarding the associated wave mode. But if we set a time derivative to zero before diagonalizing, the effect ripples through all the equations, and all the wave modes can be affected. To verify that this is a good approximation it is necessary to evaluate the sensitivity of each important wave mode, because it is possible that a very small change in the terms of the equation where the time derivative was set to zero adds up to a significant change in a wave mode that depends on all the equations coupled together.

The point is that debunking the usual arguments for the electrostatic assumption is likely possible, but that it requires long and subtle arguments that are not likely to convince people. But if by not making approximations I find discrepancies, I effectively prove that such arguments exist. This serves for the purposes of this paper. And since this paper is already very long, I feel that examination of what approximations are actually OK must be left to another paper. Otherwise the bar would be set too high, and it would not be possible to publish these important results.

The author claims that “Linearization is justified by the idea that we are exploring the dynamical evolution of small perturbations (i.e., second order terms negligible) about some equilibrium state, and that these represent characteristic motions of the system about the equilibrium.” This is somewhat inconsistent/confusing with the motivation of this study. For example the equilibrium states are derived by setting all the time derivatives to be zero, which is basically a version of the electrostatic assumption. If such “equilibrium” states are somewhat independent and cannot be described by the linearized equation sets used here, then the theory presented in this manuscript relate is only a modification to the “given” equilibrium state, which is based on the electrostatic assumption.

The reviewer is correct that the equilibrium state being linearized about is a special case of electrostatic equilibrium, known as thermal equilibrium. However, the electrostatic equilibrium solutions (other than thermal equilibrium) are also derived by linearizing the equations about thermal equilibrium. It is true that other background states are sometimes linearized-about to derive electrostatic equilibrium, but this is a heuristic extension, and the paper uses this same heuristic extension to develop the electromagnetic model for an inhomogeneous plasma, in Section 7. But the canonical manifestations for both electrostatic equilibrium and the solutions developed in Section 2 are as linearizations with respect to thermal equilibrium. Both reduce to thermal equilibrium when the excitation is zero, and both apply only to small excitations about thermal equilibrium. So the solutions developed in Section 2 are appropriate for testing electrostatic equilibrium in canonical form, and the model proposed in Section 7 is appropriate for testing the heuristic extension of electrostatic equilibrium to an inhomogeneous background.

Normally authors simply state that non-linear terms are dropped without mentioning the role of the background state, and it is easily forgotten even that there is one. You might say that I have gone above and beyond the call of duty by including so much discussion of the linearization process, and it may have been a source of confusion, especially since I failed to explain that electrostatic equilibrium is linearized in the same way. So the reviewers comment is useful and discussion has been added to the paper.

The author may also need to justify the choice of ignoring important terms such as the neutral wind and density gradient quantitatively, given that the ionosphere is not a localized plasma system but is largely driven by solar radiation and the neutral thermosphere. In other words, when talking about scales above several hundred kilometers, the ionosphere is not only stratified vertically, but also exhibits longitude/latitude variations especially in the equatorial region where interesting phenomena such as plasma instabilities occur.

The reviewer is correct that inhomogeneities and internal sources (like wind) are very important. However, this paper is an early-stages investigation of the theoretical limits of the electrostatic assumption. For this purpose, I feel it is appropriate to consider simple gedanken experiments, in order to understand the breakdown of the assumption in simplest form. We have to correct the theory before we can correct the models. Section 6 of the original submission (Section 7 in the revision), begins the development of a more realistic model, which could be used to analyze a vertically stratified ionosphere. But it is simply not practical to complete and evaluate this model in the present paper (update, the model has been implemented in later versions of the paper, at the expense of making them very long). There needs to be a motivation to pursue a more complex model, and the purpose of the present paper is to provide that motivation. Analyzing the homogeneous case does allow comparison of the electrostatic and electromagnetic theories, when we think they should both apply, and so serves the purpose. The paper does also contain an analysis of electric field mapping through the inhomogeneous ionosphere using a sort of best-case analysis based on the idea of the model in Section 7. This is how the 90° “electrical thickness” was calculated. But it is simply not possible to go further at this time. (Update, I did go much farther in the later editions, and made the whole model, since this paper was not accepted.)

In the linearization process, $v_i = \delta v_i$ and $v_e = \delta v_e$, but in the matrix form shown in Figure 1, additional variables such as V_{i0x} , V_{e0x} occurs in H_5 , which are not defined anywhere in the manuscript, and are not consistent with what’s described in the manuscript. Thus it is unclear how to get the linearized version of equation (1) shown in Figure 1.

Those variables are the zeroth order velocities, which are zero in this application. I noticed I also forgot to define the zeroth order pressures, and \hat{B} . Sentences have been added to define all these variables and explain how they are set (Appendix II). Thank you for actually looking at the messy matrix!

In line 180, the author states that “After the Fourier and Laplace transforms these equations are linear and homogenous”, equation (2) is basically derived from dropping all the non-linear and zeroth-order terms. However, in line 186, the author says “To be clear, H_5 is formed without dropping any terms or making any approximations”. These two statements are inconsistent.

Actually, H_5 (a matrix) was defined as the linear part, and so the statement is technically correct. Although I have retained that sentence, the paragraph is now altered so that I think the reader will not have your question anymore. Also, the zeroth order equations are satisfied, they are not dropped; thermal equilibrium satisfies the zeroth order equations, and then the perturbation terms are determined by the higher order equations (where we drop second order and above).

Specific Clarifications for equation (1):

Variables undefined: Q , ξ , ϵ_0 , μ_0 , K_B .

These variables are the generation rate, the coefficient for the recombination rate, the permittivity of free space, the permeability of free space, and the Boltzmann constant, respectively. I have added their definitions to the text, and mentioned that Q is chosen to balance recombination in zeroth order.

Coordinates system for generating Matrix H_5 undefined: e.g., define the \vec{k} vector and \vec{B}_0 vector.

Sorry there was a typo and I had both \vec{B}_0 and \vec{B}_g for the geomagnetic field. I have also now indicated specifically that \vec{k} is the wavevector for the Fourier transform. The matrix H_5 actually does not assume a coordinate system, but in plotting the eigenvectors I place \vec{B}_0 along \hat{z} and take $k_x = 0$, which I did forget to mention (now said in lines 591-592). These things are corrected in the revision, and I have also added to the figure captions for the eigenvectors, to support the casual reader.

c) The Eigen Vectors

First of all, the x-axis labeled in Figure 4 is not consistent with the definition of state vector X used in equation (2).

I assume the reviewer is referring to the fact that the δ s are missing for some of the variables, which was a mistake. However, adding the δ s requires shrinking the font more than is desirable, so I have decided

to solve the problem by omitting the δs from the definitions of those variables, making the figure correct. Possibly, the reviewer is instead referring to the fact that the figure axis contains all upper case variables. If so, then the reviewer may have missed where some of the lower-case variables were rescaled, with the rescaled variables denoted by upper case. This was done right after equation (2), in line 182 of the original submission, and for the revision it is in Appendix II (lines 1520-1521).

In Figure 4, the author shows examples of four Eigen modes calculated using specific parameters, however, the detailed parameters used for computing the eigenvectors are not provided except for density, altitude and transverse scale. These three alone does not provide enough information about the average state of the ionosphere considered as an example and how the matrix H_5 is generated. The author may want to consider providing a detailed table/list of all the parameters used in matrix H_5 to derive the normalized eigenvectors. The author should also consider provide reasonable validations in order to show that the Eigen system is calculated correctly, if possible.

The figures in the appendix provide the remaining variables as a function of altitude. So providing the altitude does actually provide all the needed information. I have added sentences in a few places referring the reader to the appendix (Appendix I in the revision).

Regarding the correctness of the eigensystem, in Cosgrove [2016] I compared the eigenvalues with the standard, non-collisional dispersion relations for the X-mode, O-mode, Z-mode, whistler mode, fast Alfvén mode, and shear Alfvén mode. The results were very good, with differences arising only in ways that make sense for collisional effects, and considering the relationship between the whistler and fast-mode waves. The “standard” dispersion relations were taken from [Stix, 1992]. In the current paper I have added the continuity and momentum equations, but I have checked the eigenvalues against those from the Cosgrove [2016] version and everything looks good!

I have also checked the numerical accuracy by multiplying H_5 by the eigenvectors and comparing to multiplication by the eigenvalues. The accuracy is generally very close to 15 decimal places.

The eigenvectors shown in Figure 4 are also confusing. For example in the Alfvén mode, there is a non-zero δB_z component in the solution. What does a finite δB_z component mean in the Alfvén mode physically (maybe the reviewer is mis-interpreting the results since no information about the background B field is given. Is it in the z direction?). Why all the electric field components are zero in all the modes shown in Figure 4? What does it mean physically that all the E-field components are zero in the Eigen vector? Also the Ion and Thermal modes are not coupled to any electromagnetic fields, does that mean they should be eliminated in the equations before the calculations in order to simplify the analysis?

With respect to the electric fields, they are not actually zero, for any of the modes; it’s just that they are sufficiently small that they cannot be seen with the linear axes. Using plots with logarithmic axes allows, in some ways, a better comparison, but since these are signed quantities I decided that was not a good solution. Also, it should be understood that all the variables can be rescaled, which changes the relative amplitudes within a single eigenvector; so the electric fields could, arbitrarily, be made the largest components. It was actually quite difficult to choose good relative scalings for the variables, ones that did not seem too arbitrary, and which balanced the components relatively well. The units for electric field are related to those for magnetic field by a factor with units of velocity. The decision was to set this factor equal to the speed of light, which means the plots actually contain magnetic field in Gaussian units. As we can see by referring to Figure 3 of the Cosgrove [2016] paper, this choice makes the electric field dominate for the radio frequency modes, but for the lower phase velocity modes the magnetic field takes over. This is consistent with the idea that the “displacement current” is negligible in the ionosphere, where there is an assumption that the radio frequency waves are not relevant. However, I think your point is well taken in the sense that since I am not showing the radio frequency modes, I should have used a different normalization for this plot that allows electric field to be seen.

By the way, the rescaling freedom does not affect the eigenvalues, or any of the physical quantities such as conductivity; it is a sort of gauge freedom. The purpose of these figures is to compare one mode to another, for example, to see that the Whistler wave has a larger magnetic perturbation than the Alfvén wave. This purpose remains valid even with the rescaling ambiguity. I have added a sentence explaining about this

rescaling ambiguity, and I'm sorry it did not appear in the original submission. The figure caption has also been modified. I think maybe this is one of the things the reviewer meant about the physical interpretation not being clear, which I can understand. That was an important point, where my explanation was insufficient, but nothing actually wrong. Due to the difficulty in explaining so much material I have decided to omit these kinds of plots in the final 2022 version of the paper.

With respect to δB_z for the Alfvén wave, the prototype Alfvén wave is derived in a collisionless low-frequency approximation that finds three modes, the shear mode, fast mode, and slow mode. The fast mode wave transitions into the whistler wave, when moving to the high frequency regime, and so they correspond to the same eigenvector [Cosgrove 2016]. The shear mode is the one normally just called the Alfvén wave by ionospheric physicists. The slow mode is the one normally called the ion-acoustic wave by ionospheric physicists. The fast mode normally has a δB_z component, but the shear mode does not. So the existence of a δB_z component for the collisional (shear) Alfvén wave does not seem so surprising, it just means that full inclusion of collisions mixes somewhat the properties of the collisionless fast and shear modes. Beyond this it's not clear what kind of answer is desired. One could attempt to simplify the equations and to figure out precisely which terms control δB_z in the collisional Alfvén mode, but that is a very big job that is not very relevant to this study. If the question is actually whether there could be a mistake in the matrix H_5 , that is why I have shown that matrix in all its gory detail. The δB_z component also shows in the Cosgrove [2016] paper, which constitutes a completely separate derivation of the (very similar) equations and also implementation in Matlab instead of Python. So while I hope there will some day be an independent derivation, I think the matrix H_5 is correct.

Also, the Ion (i.e., ion-acoustic) and Thermal waves are electromagnetic waves that are well approximated by electrostatic waves. I did not show that they were completely decoupled, only that they can't transmit energy very far. As far as whether there should be simplifications that somehow eliminate them, the purpose of this work is best satisfied by avoiding approximations except when necessary. Making approximations opens-up the possibility that the solution could be wrong, and I want to squash that possibility. Actually, I think the best way to remove the Ion and Thermal waves (when desired) is to first solve for the eigenvectors/eigenvalues exactly, and then just drop the associated eigenvectors/eigenvalues.

Minor concerns/Clarifications

The key points 1 and 2 are too broad, key point 3 does not provide useful information as well. The key points should convey the main points and conclusions of the article.

Agreed, I have made the key points more informative.

The author may also consider make the title more focused and specific. "plus 150km echoes" seems less related to the first part of the title.

Agreed, I have changed the title for the revision, and removed the subject of 150 km echoes entirely. It will have to go in another paper.

Line 25, what kind of sources? Please specify. Line 27-31, the reviewer is not quite clear about what these descriptions mean without examples or qualitative analysis.

I have added a couple of sentences to the Introduction defining the term "source" (lines 102-107). But since the Introduction is now changed quite a bit, the reviewer may have to give me additional feedback on the current state of clarity. The other reviewer seemed to be triggered by that material, and so I wanted to de-emphasize it, rather than go into it more. This relates to my point above about the subtlety involved in debunking the usual arguments for the electrostatic assumption; they perhaps read as technical objections. (Although, I think the point about the imaginary part of frequency being omitted is quite clear and convincing.)

Line 112: "the usual dynamo theory [e.g., Richmond, 1973; Kelley, 2009] needs to be reworked, in order to correctly account for the loading effects of the surrounding plasma." The dynamo theory applies to a magnetized plasma system driven by the neutral thermosphere, which is also determined by the spatial variations (e.g., gradient) of ionospheric plasma. None of these factors are included in the analysis, so how does the linear theory presented here apply to the re-work of the usual dynamo theory? Can the author provide more details? For example, does the pre-reversal enhancement phenomenon need to be revised?

Actually, the effects from back-reflection associated with “spatial variations” are fully included in the model for a vertically inhomogeneous ionosphere, which was described in the section “Modeling the Ionospheric Admittance.” And this model has been implemented in later versions of the paper and is now the main focus. Also, the effects from back-reflection were discussed in Section 6 of [Cosgrove 2016], where it was shown that they do produce a more normal, real-valued conductance. So the reviewer is correct that these effects do allow for producing a more normal dynamo loading effect, but is not correct that they are not included in the analysis. The original version of the paper began by discussing a homogeneous plasma, and then only at the end discussed the more general case with back reflection. But that discussion comes much earlier in the final, 2022 version.

Note that the reviewer is commenting on the discussion of the material from my previous 2016 paper; line 112 is in the section (of the original submission) titled “Previous Work” and provides a summary of [Cosgrove 2016]. I agree that the summary was inadequate, and in all later versions of the paper is added a section called “gedanken experiment” that describes the relationship between cases with and without back reflection. I think that this section may better highlight the importance of back-reflection, compared with what was actually said in [Cosgrove 2016], although the “wave-Pedersen conductivity” was originally developed there.

The pre-reversal enhancement is definitely something I would like to look at, since the interplay between the E and F regions may be important there, although I’m not sure about scale.

By the way, dynamos are normally treated using electrostatic theory, which is also derived from the linearized equations. So using the linearized equations does not limit the ability to test electrostatic theory, for dynamos or otherwise.

Line 138: please define the physical meaning of the term “electric thickness.” Line 150: please define the physical meaning of the term “electric length”

The electrical thickness of a region, with respect to a particular wave, is the amount of phase rotation suffered by the wave in traversing the region. In this case the region is the ionosphere. So the two terms are related in that the “electrical thickness” of the ionosphere is the “electrical length” from the “top” of the ionosphere to the “bottom,” where 400 km and 100 km are the examples used for top and bottom, respectively, in the paper. Sentences have been added to later versions.

Line 229: “the dynamo layer will move relative to the geomagnetic field lines at approximately the wind velocity” This statement is generally true for the F-region dynamo but not for the E- region dynamo.

I have modified this by adding “ignoring polarization electric fields, which will depend on the detailed configuration” within the sentence mentioned. I believe this makes the statement true, and here is why. Ignoring diffusion, the ion and electron velocities derived from the steady-state momentum equations may be written,

$$\begin{aligned}\vec{v}_i &= \frac{\rho_i}{1 + \rho_i^2} \left(\frac{\vec{E}_\perp}{B} + \vec{u} \times \hat{b} \right) + \frac{\vec{E}_\parallel}{\rho_i B} + \frac{1}{1 + \rho_i^2} \left(\frac{\vec{E}_\perp}{B} + \vec{u} \times \hat{b} \right) \times \hat{b} + \vec{u}, \\ \vec{v}_e &= \frac{-\rho_e}{1 + \rho_e^2} \left(\frac{\vec{E}_\perp}{B} + \vec{u} \times \hat{b} \right) - \frac{\vec{E}_\parallel}{\rho_e B} + \frac{1}{1 + \rho_e^2} \left(\frac{\vec{E}_\perp}{B} + \vec{u} \times \hat{b} \right) \times \hat{b} + \vec{u},\end{aligned}$$

where ρ_i is the ratio of the ion-neutral collision frequency to the iono-cyclotron frequency, ρ_e is the ratio of the electron-neutral collision frequency to the electron-cyclotron frequency, \vec{u} is the neutral wind velocity, $\vec{B} = B\hat{b}$ is the geomagnetic field, \vec{E}_\perp is the electric field perpendicular to \vec{B} , and \vec{E}_\parallel is the electric field parallel to \vec{B} [e.g., Cosgrove and Tsunoda, 2003, <https://doi.org/10.1029/2002JA009728>]. The perpendicular electric field (\vec{E}_\perp) is zero in the frame of reference moving with the geomagnetic field lines (because field lines move with the $\vec{E} \times \vec{B}$ velocity). Also, in the lower E region, $\rho_i \gg 1$ and $\rho_e \ll 1$. Using these results the velocities

are approximated by,

$$\begin{aligned}\vec{v}_i &\cong \frac{\vec{E}_{\parallel}}{\rho_i B} + \vec{u}, \\ \vec{v}_e &\cong -\frac{\vec{E}_{\parallel}}{\rho_e B} + \vec{u} \times \hat{b} \times \hat{b} + \vec{u} = -\frac{\vec{E}_{\parallel}}{\rho_e B} + u_{\parallel} \hat{b},\end{aligned}$$

where u_{\parallel} is the component of the wind along the geomagnetic field. Since \vec{E}_{\parallel} is very small, the ion velocity is equal to \vec{u} , and so this is the layer velocity as claimed in the paper. However, things are not this simple, because the electrons have a different velocity, meaning that there is a current. We can't really discuss the parallel component unless diffusion is included, but maybe we can agree to ignore the parallel phenomena (ambipolar diffusion and the ambipolar electric field). So the question is, will the ion current cause charge buildup and an opposing electric field that stops the ion motion, or will the ion current find a way to close, preventing the formation of the opposing field and allowing the motion to continue? Previous research [e.g., Shalimov et al., JGR, 1998, 103, 11617; Cosgrove and Tsunoda, GRL, 2001, 28(8), 1455] has shown that the answer to this question is highly geometry dependent, depending, for example, on coupling to the F region, which is a potential current closure path.

For a long thin “dynamo” with the wind blowing across it there can be an electrojet-like effect where the polarization field builds up and drives a large Cowling channel current, and when this works really well the polarization field could essentially stop the ion motion, as the reviewer may be suggesting. But this is a relatively specialized effect and there are many ways it can be defeated. For example, if the dynamo is not long enough the strong Cowling channel current will not be able to close completely, and a polarization field will build up opposing it, which will drive a Hall current that closes or partially closes the original wind-driven ion current—so then the ion motion can continue or partially continue. Or, if the dynamo is not thin enough, the initial polarization field may map to the F region and likely find a lot of extra conductivity up there, such that there is closure through the F region and again, the polarization field doesn't get very large and the ion motion can continue. So I would argue that the electrojet case is special and rare, and that the more generic configuration does not allow for a fully formed polarization electric field, and therefore the layer will typically move at or somewhat below the wind velocity.

I think this is sufficient for the purposes of the present paper, where we are just seeking an estimate of the typical layer velocity, in order to characterize the frequencies associated with ionospheric phenomena. All of this is only to justify the 40 m/s layer velocity used in the paper, which could also be justified by observations, for example, ISR.

S.6.3 Reviews of the Revision of “Failure of the Electrostatic Assumption via an Exact Solution for the Linear Waves of the Electromagnetic 5-Moment Fluid Equations, plus 150 km Echoes,” submitted to JGR in 2018. This was the second version of the 2022 paper.

This first revision of the paper was treated as a resubmission by JGR. This revision still did not include implementation of the model for a vertically inhomogeneous ionosphere, although the equations for that model were given with almost the same level of detail as in the final, 2022 paper. Completing the implementation was described as future work. Otherwise, this revision added most of the elements of the final, 2022 paper, including writing down the exact solution, writing down the approximate solution found by complex plane integration, and addition of the gedanken experiment, which was added to better explain the work in [Cosgrove 2016].

S.6.3.1 Reviewer #3:

Reviewer #3 Evaluations:

Recommendation (Required): Reject

Significant (Required): There are major errors or gaps in the paper but it could still become significant with major changes, revisions, and/or additional data.

Supported (Required): No

Referencing (Required): Yes

Quality (Required): The organization of the manuscript and presentation of the data and results need some improvement.

Data (Required): Yes

Accurate Key Points (Required): No

Reviewer #3 (Formal Review for Authors (shown to authors)):

I accepted to review the paper out of curiosity. Once I looked at the paper, I wondered why I had accepted. In the end I am not sure that the paper adds much to the sum of our knowledge. A complicated argument is made about what seems a highly idealized model. Moreover, it seems neither of the first two referees sees a strong reason to publish. It has taken a while for me to understand what the other referees and I find so troubling about the paper. It is in its negative style and rather iconoclastic ethos.

The review does not mention that the paper finds a greater than 90° phase rotation from the top to the bottom of the ionosphere, for a 100 km transverse wavelength. So the electric field does not map! This is absolutely a new and important result!! It is only by omitting this result that the reviewer can pretend that “I am not sure that the paper adds much to the sum of our knowledge.”

Otherwise, the only reason given for rejecting the paper is the style of writing; the paper is said to be “iconoclastic.” Nothing is suggested to be wrong with the methodology or with the results, anywhere in what the reviewer has written.

As far as the analysis being idealized, the paper analyzes a homogeneous plasma with boundary, and explains how the analysis could be extended to a vertically inhomogeneous ionosphere in future work (which has now been completed). Analyzing a homogeneous plasma (with boundary) allows for deriving a very conclusive comparison to electrostatic theory, and since the major conclusion involves the parallel wavelength being short, it is clear that it also applies for inhomogeneous plasma. Especially given that the issue seems to be very contentious, taking a careful step-by-step approach would seem to be the appropriate way to proceed.

Anyway the model for the vertically inhomogeneous ionosphere has now been completed.

Finally, the reviewer says a number of things that seem unfitting. First, the reviewer says, “Once I looked at the paper, I wondered why I had accepted.” In this sentence the reviewer seems to be saying that they don’t want to do the review, and that they aren’t approaching the task with a good attitude. Then, the reviewer says, “It has taken a while for me to understand what the other referees and I find so troubling about the paper. It is in its negative style and rather iconoclastic ethos.” In this sentence the reviewer seems to be saying that their review is not based on the scientific content of the paper.

While one learns that the author finds the electrostatic approach to describing ionospheric equilibrium states limited, one does not see how it should be replaced.

Apparently the reviewer did not read Section 6, which was titled “Modeling the Ionospheric Admittance,” and was about how a practical model could be developed in the future. For example in the first paragraph of Section 6 is the sentence, “We now describe a transmission line analysis methodology that could be used to develop a more quantitative model for the ionospheric input admittance as a function of transverse wavelength and frequency, and which we intend to develop in future work.” This model has now been completed and the results were described in two unpublished version of the paper before the final 2022 version.

I found the authors first principles hard to grasp initially. For example, I could not understand why if curl E is unavoidably not zero, it means a steady state is impossible. I thought it might mean the system was like chaos for example. However, that cannot be so if one can demonstrate the problem with a linearised system. Accordingly, I think that what the author has in mind is that in any final equilibrium state achieved by setting up a perturbation to a previously static system there would be a departure in the magnetic field from its original state as well as a time-stationary electric field. I don’t find this unduly controversial but nor does it seem revolutionary.

Above is the reviewers main commentary on the nature and importance of the results. It seems that the reviewer did not read the section titled “Summary of Results,” because in the first paragraph of that section the paper states,

“... it is found that electric fields with transverse scale sizes of 100 km and below will not map from 400 km to 100 km in altitude, and there is a profound effect on the ionospheric input-admittance. The actual input admittance depends on the transverse scale size, and will be very different from the field-line-integrated ionospheric conductivity when the transverse scale size is less than 100 km.”

The reviewer did not mention this result. Since the reviewer seems to have some knowledge of ionospheric physics, the reviewer would have known that this is a new and unexpected result, if they had read the section “Summary of Results.”

The reviewer has also said “I could not understand why if curl E is unavoidably not zero, it means a steady state is impossible.” But the paper does not say any such thing, and the reviewer does not refer to a line number or even to a specific section. So I am unable to understand how the reviewer developed such a misunderstanding. What the reviewer wrote after “I think that what the author has in mind...” is also not at all correct. In the first sentence the reviewer wrote “I found the authors first principles hard to grasp initially.” So it would appear that the reviewer did not understand the paper. This would be important if the reviewer had given an indication of where they became confused, or challenged any of the reasoning. But since they did not do any of these things, and apparently did not read the section “Summary of Results,” it would appear that the issue is actually that the reviewer did not try very hard to understand the paper.

The obvious example of an initial ionospheric field introduced by a local dynamo effect certainly is very likely to launch an Alfvén wave during an intermediate stage. However, what happens to that signal far away determines how the magnetic disturbance of the wave will evolve. For example, if it propagates through the magnetosphere and ends up in the opposite hemisphere it can bounce back and forth until a steady system of field aligned current is formed. In the final steady state one would then envisage a global structure where there is a global (i.e. common electrostatic field in both hemispheres) and a field aligned current system between hemispheres to even out stress. There would be a magnetostatic field associated with the overall current system as the magnetic field has to shear or twist to provide the field aligned current flow.

The reviewer does not seem to be aware that the paper is denying that there is always a “common electrostatic field in both hemispheres” (where I am speaking of the E regions). Again, it would seem that the reviewer has not read enough of the paper even to know what conclusions are claimed.

The conclusion that was stated, for example, in the section “Summary of Results” (Section 8), was developed in the analysis of Section 5 titled “Modified View of Electric Field Mapping.” In Section 5, the wavelengths of the Alfvén and Whistler waves were used to calculate the phase rotation for a signal traveling from the F region at 400 km to the E-region at 100 km, for a transverse wavelength of 100 km and density of 10^{11} m^{-3} . It was found that in this case there is over 90° of phase rotation just in one direction of travel. With the wavelength being this short it is obvious that there will not be a “common electrostatic field in both hemispheres” for the 100 km altitude. In this case, there is no need to think about the back-reflected wave to make the conclusion. The back-reflected wave will have the same wavelength, and superposing these waves cannot increase the wavelength.

However, a detailed discussion of the importance of the back reflected wave was given in Section 6, where some standard results from transmission line theory were described. It was explained that a 90° phase rotation for one-way travel would result a short circuit input admittance seen looking down from 400 km, if the bottom of the ionosphere is regarded as an open circuit. It was explained that this happens because the back reflected wave returns with 180° of phase rotation, and thus (nearly) cancels the electric field of the incident wave. It was explained how the formulas from transmission line theory allow for treating more complex problems. It would appear that the reviewer did not read any of this material.

The reviewers comments imply that they did not read either Section 5 (Modified View of Electric Field Mapping), Section 6 (Gedanken Experiment), or Section 8 (Summary of Results).

In reading again the responses to referees and rebuttals I found that the comment that I resonated with most was the query about orders of magnitude and the implicit issue of what physical process linked to particular scale lengths where breakdown occurred.

I do not know what “query” the reviewer is referring to. The best I can do is to imagine what question I might ask that would involve similar words. Hence, the “breakdown” referred to in the paper is the breakdown of electrostatic theory that occurs when the parallel wavelength becomes comparable to the thickness of the

ionosphere. The “physical process” that causes the unexpected shortening of the wavelength is the high rate of collisions, which are not included in the dispersion relations for the MHD waves. Another issue is that dispersion relations are often evaluated with ω purely real and \vec{k} complex, and this may produce an artificially long wavelength.

I wrote the preceding paragraph in an attempt to picture how I would have liked to see what the author is talking about.

It seems that the reviewer does not realize that the main results involve the response of the ionosphere to a source placed above it. So the field line above the source, which may (or may not) connect to the other hemisphere, is not part of the system being analyzed. If one likes, one can think of the wave produced by the source as coming from the other hemisphere, but that is not necessary; one can also think of it as coming from the magnetosphere, or wherever. So the reviewers discussion of hemisphere-to-hemisphere propagation is not relevant.

I might have taken this to mean that the discussion was inadequate, if I thought that the reviewer had read the paper. But instead I think that what happened is that the reviewer scanned the figures and noticed one of the figures from the section “Gedanken Experiment,” where the cases with and without a back-reflected wave were compared. Since the reviewer did not read that section they misinterpreted the purpose of the figure.

The author adopts a bracing, even iconoclastic, style. I think that that is alienating to the reader. The issues are not entirely original. Indeed, I found the author’s 2016 paper more amenable in style. However, even better, I would firmly recommend reading the Vasyliunas (2012) paper that is referenced. Vasyliunas is also raising very similar criticisms of traditional theory. The major difference is in the style of presentation and in Vasyliunas’ clear interest in explaining the challenges to electrostatic theory in terms of physical behaviour, even if approximate. Most significant to me is Vasyliunas’ modest but incisive approach to expressing what shortcomings there are in the traditional approximate theories that have been used for half a century or so. The ultimate issue of publication hinges on what new knowledge there is in the paper. I am not clear that I have learnt much but there may be a publication here.

Except for the last two lines, the reviewer is criticizing the writing style, which they feel is not sufficiently humble. Regarding the last two lines, it is apparent that the reviewer did not read the “Summary of Results” section, because the reviewer did not mention the results claimed in the following line:

“...it is found that electric fields with transverse scale sizes of 100 km and below will not map from 400 km to 100 km in altitude, and there is a profound effect on the ionospheric input-admittance. The actual input admittance depends on the transverse scale size, and will be very different from the field-line-integrated ionospheric conductivity when the transverse scale size is less than 100 km.”

Assuming that the reviewer has some knowledge of ionospheric physics, if they had read these lines they could not have said that the paper does not contain “new knowledge,” without pointing to problems with the methodology. The reviewer did not indicate that they thought anything was wrong with the methodology.

However, a much more direct less argumentative style needs to be adopted so one may see where icons may be allowed to stand and where they need replacement.

It appears that the reviewer became angry at the “iconoclastic style” in the Introduction, and decided to review the paper without reading very much of it. The review is almost solely concerned with directing me to be more tactful. The review does not mention the main results, or the methods, not even to challenge them.

Notes by line: Line 8 "contraindicate" is usually a medical term. I could not see what special instance led to its use here. Line 29 and 34 Possible to give physical basis for scale? Line 42 "miss-using" is wrong: "misusing" Line 64 "I-or we, to involve the reader.." This can grate. I'd use "we" (unapologetically) or the passive voice. Line 148 If there is a neutral atmosphere driven dynamo present or magnetospheric motion imposed from above, do the Matthews and Walker constraints on electrostatic solutions apply. I think not.

Rhetorical questions like "So why should we expect to derive an approximation in this way?" are polemical in many people's view. It is more sensible to not ask rhetorical questions especially if there is a risk of an emotional response in the reader.

Line 184 Repetitious?

Line 1441 "Thinking in terms of "Pedersen and Hall currents" and "polarization electric fields" and "efficient mapping along geomagnetic field lines" allows a form of intuition for ionospheric physics based in electrostatic theory. But how reliable is this intuition?" I couldn't really find the answer to this question. Although rhetorical questions may work well in lecturing they do not really suit this sort of work.

It is useful for the reviewer to point out that the rhetorical questions were annoying. Otherwise, the above portion concerns minor details and I will not bother to respond.

S.6.3.2 Reviewer #4:

Reviewer #4 Evaluations:

Recommendation (Required): Return to author for minor revisions

Significant (Required): Yes, the paper is a significant contribution and worthy of prompt publication.

Supported (Required): Yes

Referencing (Required): Yes

Quality (Required): Yes, it is well-written, logically organized, and the figures and tables are appropriate.

Data (Required): Yes

Accurate Key Points (Required): Yes

Basic Comments by A. M. Hamza It is only legitimate to question some of the conventional assumptions used in the space plasma literature. To challenge what one could describe as the 'Electrostatics' Kuhnian paradigm may not be acceptable to many, but if we are to move forward we need to transcend any kind of 'mob psychology' as Paul Feyerabend would have it and test the grounds beyond the 'Electrostatics paradigm.' I believe the paper ought to be published with some corrections as described below.

Corrections

- The actual length of the paper is too long, and the author ought to be able to shorten the paper given the fact that his 2016 paper is already long and published. I will leave it up to the author's judgement to see a reduction in size. The case against the validity of the electrostatic approximation should not be difficult to make concisely.
- The ratio used in the paper to quantify the electrostatic approximation needs to be slightly modified. An analytical treatment can be pushed to check the validity of the numerical integrations for all four cases treated in the paper.

$$r = \frac{|\nabla \times \mathbf{E}|}{|\nabla \cdot \mathbf{E}|} \quad (\text{S.4})$$

In fact this ought to be a comparison of the perpendicular component of the electric field to the parallel one. If we write the electric field in terms of its perpendicular and parallel components to the wave vector \mathbf{k} , respectively, we can easily show that the ratio r ought to be replaced by:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{E} &= E_{\parallel} \hat{\mathbf{k}} + \mathbf{E}_{\perp} = E_{\parallel} \hat{\mathbf{k}} - \hat{\mathbf{k}} \times (\hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \mathbf{E}) \\ r &= \frac{|\mathbf{E}_{\perp}|}{|E_{\parallel}|} \end{aligned}$$

This is easy to establish for a plane wave with $e^{i(\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{x} - \omega t)}$ since the curl becomes a cross product and the divergence a dot-product.

$$r = \frac{|\hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \mathbf{E}|}{|\hat{\mathbf{k}} \cdot \mathbf{E}|} = \frac{|\mathbf{E}_{\perp}|}{|E_{\parallel}|} \quad (\text{S.5})$$

Notice that this ratio is nothing but the tangent of the angle between the electric field and the wave vector, θ_{kE} . A naive suggestion would have $|\tan \theta_{kE}| \ll 1$, which in turn suggest small angles, but how small before violation of the electrostatic approximation.

The next step consists of evaluating the ratio r by determining the dispersion relation, which is done in books, and I will cite the classical book on Plasma Waves by Stix (no need for reference since this is a classic and any student of plasma physics ought to be familiar with its content).

The dispersion relation is obtained from:

$$\nabla \times (\nabla \times \mathbf{E}) + \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{E}}{\partial t^2} = -\frac{4\pi}{c^2} \frac{\partial \mathbf{j}}{\partial t} \quad (\text{S.6})$$

Which can be written as:

$$\underline{\underline{\mathbf{D}}} \cdot \mathbf{E} = 0 \quad (\text{S.7})$$

With

$$D_{ij} = c^2 k_i k_j + (\omega^2 - k^2 c^2) \delta_{ij} + 4\pi i \omega \sigma_{ij} \quad (\text{S.8})$$

Where the induced current has been written in terms of the conductivity σ

$$\mathbf{j} = \underline{\underline{\sigma}}(\omega, \mathbf{k}) \cdot \mathbf{E} \quad (\text{S.9})$$

The electrostatic approximation consists of assuming that the perpendicular component of the electric field is much much smaller than the parallel component, i.e. setting the perpendicular component to zero, to zeroth order, gives us the electrostatic dispersion relation, which then needs to be verified for consistency by calculating the perpendicular component and showing that it is indeed much smaller than the parallel component as assumed.

Let us set $\mathbf{E}_\perp = 0$ in the dispersion relation above

$$\underline{\underline{\mathbf{D}}} \cdot E_\parallel \hat{\mathbf{k}} = 0 \quad (\text{S.10})$$

this leads to

$$\omega^2 \hat{\mathbf{k}} + 4\pi i \omega \underline{\underline{\sigma}} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{k}} = 0 \quad (\text{S.11})$$

which in turn leads to the electrostatic dispersion relation:

$$\omega(\omega + 4\pi i \hat{\mathbf{k}} \cdot \underline{\underline{\sigma}} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{k}}) = 0 \quad (\text{S.12})$$

We now evaluate the first order correction to the perpendicular component of the electric field.

$$[\omega^2 \hat{\mathbf{k}} + 4\pi i \omega \underline{\underline{\sigma}} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{k}}] E_\parallel + (\omega^2 - k^2 c^2) \mathbf{E}_\perp + 4\pi i \omega \underline{\underline{\sigma}} \cdot \mathbf{E}_\perp = 0 \quad (\text{S.13})$$

This can be further simplified using the electrostatic dispersion relation derived above.

$$4\pi i \omega [\underline{\underline{\sigma}} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{k}} - \hat{\mathbf{k}} \cdot \underline{\underline{\sigma}} \hat{\mathbf{k}}] + (\omega^2 - k^2 c^2) \mathbf{E}_\perp + 4\pi i \omega \underline{\underline{\sigma}} \cdot \mathbf{E}_\perp = 0 \quad (\text{S.14})$$

We now use the following identity

$$\underline{\underline{\sigma}} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{k}} - \hat{\mathbf{k}} \underline{\underline{\sigma}} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{k}} = \hat{\mathbf{k}} \times (\underline{\underline{\sigma}} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{k}}) \quad (\text{S.15})$$

The equation for the perpendicular component of the electric field becomes

$$4\pi i \omega \hat{\mathbf{k}} \times (\underline{\underline{\sigma}} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{k}}) E_\parallel + (\omega^2 - k^2 c^2) \mathbf{E}_\perp + 4\pi i \omega \underline{\underline{\sigma}} \cdot \mathbf{E}_\perp = 0 \quad (\text{S.16})$$

Let us compare the ratio of the last two terms, with the perpendicular component of the electric field, in the electrostatic approximation, i.e.,

$$\left. \frac{|4\pi i \omega \underline{\underline{\sigma}} \cdot \mathbf{E}_\perp|}{|(\omega^2 - k^2 c^2) \mathbf{E}_\perp|} \right|_{\omega = -4\pi i \hat{\mathbf{k}} \cdot \underline{\underline{\sigma}} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{k}}} \ll 1 \quad (\text{S.17})$$

This allows us to calculate \mathbf{E}_\perp when the electrostatic dispersion relation is satisfied

$$\mathbf{E}_\perp = -i \frac{4\pi\omega \hat{\mathbf{k}} \times (\underline{\underline{\sigma}} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{k}}) E_\parallel}{(\omega^2 - k^2 c^2)} \Big|_{\omega = -4\pi i \hat{\mathbf{k}} \cdot \underline{\underline{\sigma}} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{k}}} \quad (\text{S.18})$$

Which finally allows us to set the condition for the validity of the electrostatic approximation:

$$\frac{|\mathbf{E}_\perp|}{|E_\parallel|} = \left| \frac{4\pi\omega}{\omega^2 - k^2 c^2} \hat{\mathbf{k}} \times (\underline{\underline{\sigma}} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{k}}) \right|_{\omega = -4\pi i \hat{\mathbf{k}} \cdot \underline{\underline{\sigma}} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{k}}} \ll 1 \quad (\text{S.19})$$

To move forward we need the expressions for the components of the conductivity tensor.

In a reference frame with the geomagnetic field pointing in the z-direction, the conductivity tensor is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_P &= \sigma_{xx} = \sigma_{yy} = \frac{\omega_{pi}^2}{\Omega_i^2 + \nu_{in}^2} \nu_{in} + \frac{\omega_{pe}^2}{\Omega_e^2 + \nu_{en}^2} \nu_{en} \\ \sigma_H &= -\sigma_{xy} = \sigma_{yx} = -\frac{\omega_{pi}^2}{\Omega_i^2 + \nu_{in}^2} \Omega_i + \frac{\omega_{pe}^2}{\Omega_e^2 + \nu_{en}^2} \Omega_e \\ \sigma_\parallel &= \sigma_{zz} = \frac{\omega_{pi}^2}{\nu_{in}} + \frac{\omega_{pe}^2}{\nu_{en}} \\ \sigma_{xz} &= \sigma_{zx} = \sigma_{yz} = \sigma_{zy} = 0 \end{aligned}$$

we next choose the wave vector to be in the (x, z) plane $\mathbf{k} = k(\cos \theta, 0, \sin \theta)$.

The validity condition can be written as:

$$\left| (\hat{\mathbf{k}} \cdot \underline{\underline{\sigma}} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{k}}) [\hat{\mathbf{k}} \times (\underline{\underline{\sigma}} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{k}})] \right| \ll \left| (\hat{\mathbf{k}} \cdot \underline{\underline{\sigma}} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{k}})^2 - \frac{k^2 c^2}{16\pi^2} \right| \quad (\text{S.20})$$

Using the Petersen and Hall conductivities, we can explicitly write the condition for validity of the electrostatic approximation:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\mathbf{k}} \cdot \underline{\underline{\sigma}} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{k}} &= \sigma_P \cos^2 \theta + \sigma_\parallel \sin^2 \theta \\ \left| \hat{\mathbf{k}} \times (\underline{\underline{\sigma}} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{k}}) \right|^2 &= \sigma_H^2 \cos^2 \theta + (\sigma_P - \sigma_\parallel)^2 \sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \theta \end{aligned}$$

For wave propagation along the background geomagnetic field, $\cos \theta \approx 1$, the condition is always satisfied. For small angles, on the other hand, we obtain the following condition:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\mathbf{k}} \cdot \underline{\underline{\sigma}} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{k}} &\approx \sigma_P \\ \left| \hat{\mathbf{k}} \times (\underline{\underline{\sigma}} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{k}}) \right| &\approx \sigma_H \end{aligned}$$

Which leads to the condition:

$$\frac{\sigma_H}{\sigma_P} \ll \left| 1 - \left(\frac{kc}{4\pi\sigma_P} \right)^2 \right| \quad (\text{S.21})$$

Similar results may be obtained and can be verified for all four cases addressed in the paper.

Conclusion I recommend the publication of the paper provided the author verifies that the results are consistent with the argument made in this review.

This reviewer is very positive and asks for only a minor revision. They request one minor change and require only that the results should come out consistently. The reviewer writes “The ratio used in the paper to quantify the electrostatic approximation needs to be slightly modified.” And then they demonstrate the alternative quantity they would prefer to see, and ask me to verify that it comes out consistently. I have

done this now and the results are shown in Figure S.6. They are quite consistent and I thank the reviewer for suggesting this additional validation.

To elaborate, in the paper I used the electromagnetic waves to calculate $|\nabla \times \mathbf{E}| / |\nabla \cdot \mathbf{E}| = \left| \hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \mathbf{E} \right| / \left| \hat{\mathbf{k}} \cdot \mathbf{E} \right|$, which is a quantity that should be small if the electrostatic waves are to agree with the electromagnetic ones. The reviewer instead shows how this quantity can be estimated in first order from the electrostatic waves themselves. It is this quantity that they would prefer to see, which they give in their equation (S.19). This review is uploaded by permission, and the reviewer represents that their derivation either comes from or is equivalent to a derivation from the classical textbook by Stix [Stix, 1992].

Since I did not include either of the quantities in the body of the final 2022 paper, I have plotted the reviewer's quantity (equation (S.19)) in the third row of Figure S.6. The top two rows show the method of comparing the electrostatic and electromagnetic waves that is used in the final 2022 paper. The top row compares the wavelengths parallel to the geomagnetic field and shows that the electrostatic and electromagnetic results diverge as the wavelength perpendicular to the geomagnetic field becomes longer. The second row shows similar results for the dissipation scale length. The left column shows results at 100 km in altitude, and the right column shows results at 145 km in altitude. Note that these are necessary conditions, but they are not sufficient conditions as there exist other important wave properties (e.g., characteristic admittance, etc.).

I believe that the comparisons in the top two rows are more conclusive, because they show that these waves would give different results when used in the TL theory calculation from the paper. Especially in the case of the parallel wavelength, the finding that it can be short enough to produce a resonance is very important, and it appears from Figure S.6 that the electrostatic waves miss this result. For the ratio (S.19), on the other hand, it is not clear exactly how small the ratio has to be for the electrostatic waves to give the same results as the electromagnetic waves.

To compare the different criteria shown in Figure S.6, let us take it one mode at a time. For the Alfvén mode the ratio (S.19) appears to be consistent with the criteria in the top two rows if we take the largest allowed value to be between 0.01 and 0.005, which seems quite reasonable. For the Ion wave, the criteria in the top two rows do not show any difference between the electrostatic and electromagnetic waves. However, these criteria are only necessary criteria, they are not sufficient criteria. Thus it is not inconsistent that for the 145 km altitude (right column), the ratio (S.19) is seen to surpass 1 when the transverse wavelength exceeds 150 km; there may be other wave properties that do not agree so well as the ones shown in the top two rows. And at the 100 km altitude (left column) the ratio (S.19) is everywhere less than 0.08 for the Ion wave. For the Thermal wave, the criteria in the top two rows do not show any difference between the electrostatic and electromagnetic waves, and the ratio (S.19) is everywhere less than 5×10^{-6} . There is no electrostatic counterpart for the Whistler wave and so it does not appear. Hence these results are all consistent.

In addition, in doing this I have also compared the reviewers expression for ω in equations (S.17)-(S.19) with the eigenvalues of the matrix H_{5ES} , and found that they agree. The agreement is shown in the fourth and fifth rows of Figure S.6, where the fourth row shows the imaginary part and the fifth row shows the real part. The real part is just the frequency derived from the (assumed) 40 m/s transverse velocity and the transverse wavelength, and so is the same for all the modes.

This comparison helps to validate both calculations. The expression $\omega = -4\pi i \hat{\mathbf{k}} \cdot \underline{\underline{\sigma}}(\omega) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{k}}$ given by the reviewer (in Gaussian units) is a nonlinear equation in ω , and clearly ω has a large imaginary part, since we expect $\underline{\underline{\sigma}}(\omega)$ to be mostly real. I am able to solve this equation by finding the eigenvalues and eigenvectors of the matrix H_{5ES} , where there are multiple solutions corresponding to the multiple modes of propagation. The conductivity tensor $\underline{\underline{\sigma}}(\omega)$ is calculated from the eigenvectors, and *Cosgrove* showed that this gives the same results as direct evaluation of the conductivity equations with the imaginary part of ω included. The result is very different from the conductivity calculated without including the imaginary part of ω , which is evident from the fact that there are multiple solutions, and we note that the imaginary part is largest for the Alfvén mode. Plots of conductivity that directly demonstrate the importance of the imaginary part of ω may be found in Figure 16 of *Cosgrove* (errata: in the figure caption "equation (1)" should be "equation A9"). This provides a nice additional validation and I thank the reviewer for bringing the analytical results to my attention.

Figure S.6: Comparison of different proposed criteria for validity of electrostatic theory, as a function of the wavelength in the direction perpendicular to the geomagnetic field. The left column is for an altitude of 100 km and the right column is for an altitude of 145 km. Top row: comparison of the wavelength in the direction parallel to the geomagnetic field, for electrostatic waves (dashed lines) and electromagnetic waves (solid lines). Second row: comparison of the dissipation scale lengths for electrostatic waves (dashed lines) and electromagnetic waves (solid lines). Third row: ratio $|\hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \mathbf{E}| / |\hat{\mathbf{k}} \cdot \mathbf{E}|$ computed from a first order correction to electrostatic theory (equation (S.19)). Fourth and fifth rows: comparison of the imaginary and real parts, respectively, of the eigenvalues of the matrix H_{5ES} with the solutions of $\omega = -4\pi i \hat{\mathbf{k}} \cdot \underline{\underline{\sigma}}(\omega) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{k}}$.

S.6.3.3 Decision Letter from JGR

From: jgr-spacephysics@agu.org
Subject: 2018JA026274 (Editor - XXXXX): Decision Letter
Date: XXXX XX, XXXX at 9:44:30 AM PST
To: russell.cosgrove@me.com
Cc: russell.cosgrove@sri.com
Reply-To: jgr-spacephysics@agu.org

Dear Dr. Cosgrove,

Thank you for submitting your manuscript "Breakdown of Electrostatic Theory via Exact Linearization and Solution of the Electromagnetic 5-Moment Fluid Equations" to the Journal of Geophysical Research - Space Physics.

At long last I have received two reviews of your manuscript (see below/attached). One reviewer was particularly tardy despite many reminders from AGU staff and myself. I apologise for the long delay.

Both reviewers raise major concerns with the paper despite very different summary evaluations. The key issues are essentially not enough new science, and far too long. As a result I am declining your manuscript for publication in Journal of Geophysical Research - Space Physics.

I am enclosing the reviews, which you may find helpful if you decide to revise your manuscript. I am sorry that I cannot be more encouraging at this time.

Thank you for your continued support of JGR-Space Physics.

Yours sincerely,

XXXXX
Editor
JGR-Space Physics

Reviewer #2 said the following about the three results they found in the paper: “1) and 2) are not so surprising given the fact of not using an electrostatic assumption, and 3) is quite interesting and may have significant impact on future studies of M-I coupling.”

Reviewer #4 said “To challenge what one could describe as the ‘Electrostatics’ Kuhnian paradigm may not be acceptable to many, but if we are to move forward we need to transcend any kind of ‘mob psychology’ as Paul Feyerabend would have it and test the grounds beyond the ‘Electrostatics paradigm.’ I believe the paper ought to be published with some corrections as described below.”

So clearly two of the four reviewers did not concur with the editors conclusion of “The key issues are essentially not enough new science, and far too long.” *A likely reason for the editors conclusion is that the two negative reviews did not report the results found in the paper.*

What is obvious is that the paper was highly controversial, with strong opinions on both sides. This suggests that the paper could be very important, but that we won’t know until it has been debated by the wider community.

S.6.4 Reviews of “Breakdown of Electrostatic Theory via Exact Linearization and Solution of the Electromagnetic 5-Moment Fluid Equations,” submitted to JASTP in 2019. This was the third version of the 2022 paper.

In this version, the Introduction section was dramatically shortened from the previous version, since that material seemed to be antagonizing the reviewers, who were not really reviewing the principle material in the paper. Otherwise the material was essentially the same, although some language was revised for clarity.

S.6.4.1 Reviewer #1 (the only one)

This manuscript extends the previous work of Cosgrove [2016] and provides some improvements on that previous work, but this manuscript also has a number of problems. The notable improvements on the previous work are:

1. This work adds the continuity and energy equations to the equation set, and includes the effects of additional wave modes that result from these extensions (Ion and Thermal waves).
2. Section 5 demonstrates how limiting the calculations to a finite slab and including reflections results in convergence to the electrostatic result. This resolves one of the most serious deficiencies with the Cosgrove [2016] results. That paper considered an infinite uniform plasma with no reflections, which is a scenario that never exists in nature.

The reviewer does not report the main results found in the paper (that the electric field does not map through the ionosphere, and that the ionospheric conductance is not the field line integrated conductivity, etc). For example, the reviewer does not report the following lines from the first paragraph of the section “Summary of Results and Discussion,”

“...it is found that electric fields with transverse scale sizes of 100 km and below will likely not map from 400 km to 100 km in altitude, with profound effect on the ionospheric input-admittance. The actual input admittance in this case will depend on the transverse scale size, and should be very different from the field-line-integrated ionospheric conductivity...”

A proper review reports all the important results that are claimed, and then if they think there are problems with the methodology, they report on those. Instead, this reviewer ignores the “Summary of Results and Discussion” section and incorrectly states that “no results are presented,” and then says that “This modeling approach could be useful in the future” (see below for these two remarks).

In addition, this reviewer is not accurate in the results that they do report: the paper does not find that “limiting the calculations to a finite slab and including reflections results in convergence to the electrostatic result”. The Abstract does say “...electrostatic predictions can be conditionally recovered...”, but the reviewer has ignored the word “conditionally,” which changes the meaning.

In addition, the reviewer misrepresents the results from [Cosgrove 2016]: item (2) of the “notable improvements” refers (inaccurately) to a summary of the results *from* [Cosgrove 2016], and so that material certainly does not correct any “serious deficiencies” in that paper, since it came from that paper. Section 6 of [Cosgrove 2016] considered the back-reflected wave and derived the same “wave-Pedersen” conductivity that accounts for the back-reflected wave (equation (14) of [Cosgrove 2016], which is equivalent to equation (17) in this paper). The reviewer should have known this because the sentence right before equation (17) reads,

“Making this same comparison, Cosgrove [2016] suggested defining a wave-Pedersen conductivity (their equation (14))...”

Also, it should be noted that the case without a back-reflected wave is relevant to small transverse scales, where the wave may dissipate before meeting with any significant changes in plasma density.

And importantly, although it is of course true that the natural plasma is never entirely uniform, that does not mean it is not very informative to compare the electrostatic and electromagnetic results for a uniform plasma. We expect electrostatic theory to work for a uniform plasma, and so if it does not we have learned that there is a major gap in our understanding.

Section 6 of this manuscript goes on to describe a new model formulation for the ionosphere based on multiple transmission line segments, but this model has not yet been implemented and no results are presented. This modeling approach could be useful in the future, but it seems premature to publish any information on it here since it has not been realized or tested yet.

In saying “This modeling approach could be useful in the future...” the reviewer is acknowledging that the methodology seems to be correct. But the reviewer tries to avoid this by saying “no results are presented,” which is simply not true, as already documented by the lines extracted from the paper that appear just above. The results that the reviewer did not report were those that could be derived from this methodology without a full implementation. The following text from the abstract specifically addresses this matter,

“The model will be fully executed in future work, but an approximate version is used to estimate the phase rotation for electrical signals traversing the ionosphere: our example calculations imply

that this “electrical thickness” generally exceeds $90\circ$ for transverse scale-sizes of 100 km and below...”

The remainder of this review critiques the other portions of the manuscript for which results have been presented. There are several outstanding issues requiring additional examination. This manuscript is also very poorly organized and would be much easier to read with substantial reorganization and removal of superfluous material.

The reviewer is trying to say that the only results presented are those that he frames below, involving an E region source. This is simply not true. The reviewer did not report the main results, which are clearly stated in both the Abstract and in the first paragraph of the section “Summary of Results and Discussion” (and also in the Conclusions section, in a more general way). To prove this I have extracted text from both these sections, which appears above.

Major Scientific Issues 1.

1. The treatment of the E-region wind forcing as a boundary condition at a single surface is not justified. This manuscript repeatedly discusses the E-region wind dynamo as a boundary condition of the form of Equation 6, and refers to “the surface of the dynamo” as an infinitely thin surface. In reality the neutral winds are distributed throughout the E-region. The neutral wind dynamo is being forced by winds distributed throughout the 100 to 130 km region, not by a point layer at 100 km. The wave properties computed in this paper change dramatically over the 100 to 130 km region, so treating the neutral wind source as an infinitely thin layer at one altitude is unjustifiable.

This is not the geometry that the paper addresses. For example see Figure 9, where the main result is derived. The main results were derived for a source outside the ionosphere, such as a source in the magnetosphere, or in the conjugate hemisphere. And in this case it makes sense to begin with the simple case where there are no winds in the ionosphere. What the reviewer is referring to is that it was also explained how a similar analysis could be applied to a localized source in the E region. While this “flipped” geometry is not as realistic, it still provides for a representative calculation where we can assess whether electrostatic theory is working as we expect. It is a very well recognized technique of physics to study relatively simple configurations, in order to understand the essential physics, which then helps us to understand more complex situations. Section 5 is titled “Gedanken Experiment and Breakdown of Electrostatic Theory,” in reference to the technique that Einstein famously applied to discover relativity.

2. The meaning of a “breakdown in electrostatic theory” is poorly defined. There are two different “electrostatic theories,” and a failure of one does not imply a failure of both. The first is the theory of electrostatic waves predicted by the Vlasov-Poisson system of equations (or fluid limits). This is a dynamical theory describing the time evolution of plasma parameters at small scales. This theory is extensively used for the description of small-scale plasma irregularities involved in scintillation, for the Farley-Buneman and other E-region instabilities, and for the derivation of incoherent scatter radar theory. All of these applications are at scales less than 100 m, so the results of this paper showing the electrostatic wave theory is valid at small scales are in agreement with the existing literature. The second is the theory of electrostatic equilibrium, which is a boundary value problem describing steady state solutions with no reference to how the plasma evolved to those solutions. The core point of Vasyliunas [2012] is to describe how electrostatic equilibrium arises even though the proper description of the transient evolution must be electromagnetic. Is the objective of this paper to describe when the electrostatic theory of waves is not valid, or is it to describe when electrostatic equilibrium will not be reached from a given initial condition?

As in previous editions, the paper absolutely explains that there are two versions (or degrees) of electrostatic theory, and that they have to be examined separately. It was explained that the terms “electrostatic theory” and “electrostatic waves” would be used to differentiate between them. These two are separately analyzed in the paper! That the reviewer does not seem to know this suggests that

they didn't read much of the paper.

For example in the second to last paragraph of the Introduction section the paper reads,

"Electrostatic equilibrium is obtained by solving the equations of motion as though they determine the solution to a boundary value problem. By "electrostatic theory," or "full electrostatic theory," for emphasis, we refer to the practice of assuming that this solution is an approximation for the steady state solution found through the Laplace transform. A weaker form of the electrostatic assumption involves the substitution of electrostatic waves for electromagnetic waves. The validity of this assumption is a distinct question from that of electrostatic theory, which does not include wavelike effects. We also analyze this weaker assumption, by substituting the Poisson equation for the Maxwell equations."

I am afraid that the reviewers statement "... so the results of this paper showing the electrostatic wave theory is valid at small scales are in agreement with the existing literature." is not correct. I do not like to incriminate people when it is not necessary, but it seems that the reviewer is not familiar with all the literature. And without publishing this paper it seems likely that the mistake would be made in the future, even though it was not already made. The reviewer did not give a reference to where others have identified the maximum scale. I am aware of results for collisionless waves, but for collisional waves the closest result of which I am aware was actually given by one of the earlier (very positive) reviewers, although they did not indicate a publication. Maybe they are having the same problem I am having.

Finally, I do not agree that the "core point" of the Vasylunas [2012] paper was to show how electrostatic equilibrium arises; I don't believe he made a conclusion on whether it arises. I understood the "core point" of [Vasylunas, 2012] to be that we should employ a causal analysis, in order to test electrostatic theory. And that is exactly what I am doing.

3. The manuscript, and the previous Cosgrove [2016] work, do make an intriguing point about how the existence of a steady state solution does not guarantee that steady state solution is physically reachable from any particular initial condition.

It is nice that the reviewer has found something positive to say.

4. The manuscript does not clearly explain how electrostatic waves are associated with corresponding electromagnetic waves. The discussion of an "electrostatic Alfvén wave" is particularly confusing since Alfvén waves are electromagnetic by definition. The matrix H_5 has 16 eigenvectors, whereas the matrix H_{5ES} has 11. How is the author mapping between the two different sets of eigenvectors, especially since no one-to-one mapping can exist for sets of different sizes?

The third paragraph of Section 4.1 reads,

"Where the electromagnetic and electrostatic waves agree the dashed lines should lie on top of the solid lines. Examining the figures, the Ion and Thermal waves appear to be well described by the corresponding electrostatic waves. However, the Alfvén wave appears to be electrostatic only up to about 100 m in transverse wavelength, and then radically diverges, with the associated electrostatic wave generally having a much longer parallel wavelength. And the Whistler wave appears to have no electrostatic counterpart at all; we could find no comparable electrostatic wave."

The correspondence between electrostatic and electromagnetic waves is found using the basic technique of the paper. First, the eigenvalues/eigenvectors of the matrices H_5 and H_{5ES} are sorted and searched so that all waves capable of operating at the requisite frequency/wavelength are found. Then, the correspondence of the electrostatic and electromagnetic waves is found simply by observing that the wavelengths and dissipation scale lengths are exactly the same, although in the case of the Alfvén wave they are observed to converge to be the same only below about 100 m in transverse scale. This can be clearly seen in the figures (Figures 5, and 6, for parallel wavelength and dissipation scale length), and seems a quite reasonable way to associate the waves. Also, the usual Alfvén wave treatment does not include collisions, and anyway I believe that even for collisionless Alfvén waves (shear mode) it is known that they become electrostatic below some scale. No electrostatic wave was found to correspond to the Whistler wave, and also there is the matter of the radio frequency waves (i.e., X mode, O mode, and Z mode). So the matter of the different number of equations does not suggest of a problem.

5. The manuscript makes no attempt to discuss the relevant observational literature. There has been substantial recent interest in investigating the Alfvén wave dynamics in the ionosphere. This includes C/NOFS observations demonstrating that interhemispheric coupling in MSTIDs is electromagnetic [Burke et al., 2016a, b], and many observations of Alfvén wave dynamics at high-latitudes from Swarm [e.g. Park et al., 2017; Pakhotin et al., 2018; Miles et al., 2018]. All of these publications are already discussing all transport of electromagnetic energy along field lines as being carried by Alfvén waves, not by a “mapping” process, exactly as recommended by Vasylunas [2012]. The manuscript claims their theory predicts different altitudes for the turning between the ion drift direction and the $\mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}$ direction than electrostatic theory (Line 975). The electrostatic prediction of the location of this turning has been thoroughly experimentally verified, most notably during the Joule II sounding rocket campaign where independent measurements of electric field, ion drift, and neutral wind were all performed simultaneously [Sangalli et al., 2009].

The paper was already plenty long and included plenty of material. An observational study would be a whole other study. Since the electromagnetic theory is more general than the electrostatic theory, the former can be used to critique the latter without recourse to data. As far as the turning point, it would depend on scale size and, of course, would depend very strongly on the neutral density profile. Without critiquing the Sangalli et al. study, I note that the reviewer did not say that the neutral density profile was measured. At any rate, the calculation presented here was not tested, because it did not exist.

Minor Scientific Issues

1. The quoted conductivities have the wrong units for conductivities. Figures 5, 6, and 13 present conductivities in milli-mho (mS) where the correct unit of a conductivity should be S/m, not S or mS. The unit of S (mho) should only be used for conductances (integrated conductivities) or admittances. The wave conductivities defined in Equation 17 have units of admittance times wavenumber, which are S/m is the admittance has units of S. 2.

The reviewer is correct, those panels were labeled with the wrong units.

2. The matrix in Figure B2 is missing a row from the top half. This matrix should be 11 by 11, but the top half of the figure only has 10 rows.

The reviewer is NOT correct, all 11 rows of the matrix were present. The reviewer must not have counted very carefully.

Organizational and Presentation Issues

1. Section 2 spends a lot of time on tangential problems that distract from the main thread and confuse the reader. Section 2 could be made much shorter and much more clear by removing these superfluous tangents. The main thread is from Equations 1, 6, 7, 8, 10, 11, 12, and Appendix C. Equation 1 is the prime equation of interest, Equation 6 defines the driven boundary conditions, Equation 7 is the Laplace transform of 1, Equation 8 is the fully rigorous solution, and then 10, 11, 12, and appendix C all contain approximate forms of 8. All of the discussion around equations 3, 4, 5, and 9 are solutions to different problems from the driven boundary value problem of primary interest that are only tangentially relevant to the rest of the paper. Equation 3 is the transient solution to the initial value problem with no driving, which is a different problem all together. The derivation of 4 and 5 is described by the manuscript as “somewhat heuristic,” and they do not add anything that is not already covered by the fully rigorous solution to Equation 8. Equation 9 is the solution to the driven boundary value problem when the driver abruptly turns off at t_0 , which is a different problem from what Equation 8 solves.

The reviewer has studied the equations and not found anything wrong with them. So the reviewer should not have withheld the results from the editor. I find the additional information helpful for developing an intuitive understanding of the solution, which I think is very important.

2. Many critical details are buried in appendices such that the reader needs to constantly flip back and forth. Appendix B needs to be read nearly in entirety before attempting to understand Section 2. The definition of Ω needed to understand Equation 10 is buried in Appendix C.

I don't understand why this is the case. More details were needed from the reviewer. With respect to Ω , just after equation (10) the paper reads "...where $\Omega(k_z - K_{0z})$ is a parameterization of the 16-dimensional unitary transformations about the identity, with parametric dependence linearized (described more fully in Appendix C)." Except in the case of a very intrepid reader, this seems enough information, especially since Ω was taken to be the identity shortly thereafter.

3. Figures 3 and 4 use a normalization that results in several salient features of the eigenvectors not being visible in the plots. It is impossible to tell which values are small non-zero numbers. The text describes multiple features that cannot be seen in these plots as they are currently presented.

I agree with this comment. Earlier reviewers have also criticized the normalization and I see now that I could have done better. I had used the normalizations from [Cosgrove 2016], but they were not appropriate for the plots in this paper since in this case the X, O, and Z mode waves were not included in the plots. The electric field is very large for these waves, and accommodating it swamps the electric field in the other modes. Anyway I have dropped these kinds of plots entirely from the final 2022 paper. Similar stem plots appeared in Cosgrove [2016], and they seemed to be creating a distraction.

4. The definition of wave conductivity, Equation 17, does not appear until page 16, which is several pages after the first discussion of wave conductivities in Figures 5 and 6 starting on page 13 (line 494).

The wave conductivity was derived in [Cosgrove 2016], and so was not a new thing. Anyway I have moved this section earlier; it now appears right after the Introduction.

S.6.4.2 Decision Letter from JASTP

From: Journal of Atmospheric and Solar-Terrestrial Physics <em@editorialmanager.com>
Subject: Decision on submission to Journal of Atmospheric and Solar-Terrestrial Physics
Date: XXXX XX, XXXX at 12:10:51 PM PST
To: "Russell B. Cosgrove" <russell.cosgrove@me.com>
Reply-To: Journal of Atmospheric and Solar-Terrestrial Physics <atp-eo@elsevier.com>
Manuscript Number: JASTP-D-19-00027

Breakdown of Electrostatic Theory via Exact Linearization and Solution of the Electromagnetic 5-Moment Fluid Equations

Dear Dr. Cosgrove,

Thank you for submitting your manuscript to Journal of Atmospheric and Solar-Terrestrial Physics. I regret to inform you that following review, your manuscript has been rejected for publication in JASTP. I took time to read the manuscript in detail myself, and my own views are in accord with the reviewer. My most specific comment is the lack of discussion and detailed description/justification of how electrostatic waves are associated with corresponding electromagnetic waves. I view this as a major weakness in the study as it stands. We appreciate you submitting your manuscript to Journal of Atmospheric and Solar-Terrestrial Physics and thank you for giving us the opportunity to consider your work.

Kind regards, XXXXXX Editor
Journal of Atmospheric and Solar-Terrestrial Physics

Editor and Reviewer comments:
Reviewer #1: See attached PDF.

The reviewer did not tell the editor about the results claimed in the paper, which are the same as those in the previous JGR submission and can be read in my responses to the reviewer above. Basically, the wavelength of the waves is too short to be consistent with electrostatic equilibrium on the 100 km transverse scale. The reviewer did not mention this result, even though they did not indicate any problems with the methodology that was used to derive it.

Instead, the reviewer reports certain other results that are not in the paper, and criticizes a geometry that is not relevant to the main results from the paper. It does not seem possible that the problem is in the paper's presentation, because the results that the reviewer did not report are stated clearly both in the Abstract, and in the section "Summary of Results and Discussion." These results were derived in Figure 9, which shows clearly that the reviewer's geometry is not the one that was used. Please see the specific responses above.

It is very odd that I should have to write such a thing. I do not like doing it, but the reviewer has left me no choice.

About the correspondence of the waves, I discussed it above, and I repeat that discussion here for reference: First, the eigenvalues/eigenvectors of the matrices H_5 and H_{5ES} are sorted and searched so that all waves capable of operating at the requisite frequency/wavelength are found. Then, the correspondence of the electrostatic and electromagnetic waves was found simply by observing that the wavelengths and dissipation scale lengths were exactly the same, although in the case of the Alfvén wave they were observed to converge to be the same only below about 100 m in transverse scale. This can be clearly seen in the figures (Figures 5, and 6, for parallel wavelength and dissipation scale length), and seems a quite reasonable way to associate the waves. Also, I believe that even for collisionless Alfvén waves it is known that they become electrostatic below some scale. No electrostatic wave was found to correspond to the Whistler wave, and also there is the matter of the radio frequency waves (i.e., X mode, O mode, and Z mode). So the matter of the different number of equations does not suggest of a problem. It would not have been hard to revise the description in the paper.

S.6.5 Reviews of "The Electromagnetic Ionosphere: a Model," submitted to Phys. Rev E in 2020. This was the fourth version of the 2022 paper.

The implementation of the model for a vertically inhomogeneous ionosphere was added to this version of the paper, and initial results were given. In the previous version the model had been described and the equations given, but it had not been completely implemented. To make room the discussion of the properties of the wave modes was substantially streamlined. The sections were also substantially reorganized, to address criticism from the previous reviewer. The Introduction was modified to address the additional content. With the implementation of the full model came the additional findings for longer wavelengths, which might be considered even more surprising. Hence there was also substantial modification of the conclusions.

(note, this journal/editor uses the term "referee" instead of "reviewer," and so I will try to adapt to this)

S.6.5.1 Referee #1

Report of the First Referee -- EU12156/Cosgrove

This is a long and confusing paper on a one-dimensional steady-state model of ionospheric coupling using an electromagnetic transmission line model. While it is generally an improvement to use the full Maxwell's equations rather than the electrostatic equations, the calculations presented here are not well described or motivated and produce rather confusing results.

In keeping with the pattern established by referees of earlier versions, this summary does not acknowledge the central results of the paper. Only the single word "confusing" is provided. The referee's additional comments below also make no mention of the results, or of the important Figures 12-15 and their discussion in the Model Results section of the paper. A few of the earlier figures are cited as "confusing," but these are not the figures that contain the main results, and anyway the confusion is easily cleared up. Although the results are summarized in the Abstract, it is still usual for referees to summarize them for the editor, say something about their importance, and confirm that the body of the paper contains them. It is usual for this material to appear in a review regardless of what the referee has to say about the methodology.

And also the referee has not indicated any errors in the methodology. The referee has indicated some confusion, and there is one specific area indicated below. However, the referee's confusion appears to be associated with not having read the relevant paragraph in the paper (and there was also a reference in the Abstract). That paragraph is quoted in the specific response below. Together with the referee's apparent

failure to read the Model Results section, there is a strong indication that the referee has not read enough of the paper to write the review they have written. Other indications of this may be found below.

After failing to report the results, the referee says that they are “confusing.” So it seems that what the referee actually means is that they did not expect these results, so much so that they will not repeat them. The referee also says that the calculation is not well “motivated.” The unexpected results are the motivation for the calculation. But the reviewer simply refuses to engage with the material.

It is not accurate to characterize this new calculation as “one dimensional.” Actually, the model calculates the Fourier components of a three-dimensional signal propagating in a vertically stratified ionosphere. After compiling the Fourier components we can do the inverse Fourier transform to the spatial domain, and describe a three-dimensional signal. Describing such a three-dimensional signal with a finite-difference model would require a super computer, whereas this model can be run on an ordinary personal computer.

In addition, time-dependent models of the ionosphere exist that are more complete than this model. The transmission line approach is similar to that employed by Mallinckrodt and Carlson in 1978 (ref 7), but has been largely replaced by finite difference modeling of the equations (e.g., refs 27, 29, 30, 32, 37-40). Thus, it is hard to think of this work as an advance in the field.

The referee has compared the model with certain “time-dependent” and “finite difference” models, although the model presented in the paper is a frequency-domain model that does not require finite-differencing. Time domain models are not appropriate for the purposes of the paper. It is well known that admittance is defined in the frequency domain, and so a frequency-domain calculation is far more appropriate. The Introduction and Background sections of the final, 2022 paper explain why this is the case, and so I will not duplicate that explanation here.

But I do have to point out the basic fallacy in arguing that since we have one kind of calculation, we don’t want to know anything about other kinds of calculations. In scientific research, providing an alternative kind of calculation is always an “advance” of the field. And in this case the proof is in the pudding, since this work contains (for example) the unexpected result that the ionospheric conductance can be very different from the field line integrated conductivity. No time-domain model has ever even tested this question, and this serves as evidence that they are not appropriate for the purpose. But for some reason the referee has not told the editor about the results in the paper.

In particular, it is confusing to be considering various wave modes in a model without frequency dependence. The Alfvén wave and the whistler mode wave occupy very different regimes in frequency, which does not seem to be considered in this model.

This is not a correct account of what is in the paper. The model has frequency dependence, and the frequencies are chosen in accordance with typical ionospheric scale sizes and drift velocities. This is mentioned in the abstract as “based on characteristic ranges of spatial and temporal scale,” and then described fully in Section VA, where for example is the sentence,

“Given knowledge of reasonable wind velocities and a choice for the transverse scale-sizes of interest within the dynamo (i.e., in the direction along the boundary), the frequencies that must be matched by the wave modes are thus determined.”

Concerning the referee’s statement about the Whistler and Alfvén waves occupying different frequency regimes, there is no existing research that allows the referee to judge this matter. The existing dispersion relations for waves are not valid in the E region ionosphere, because they do not fully include the collision terms in the 5-moment equations. This is the case for all the published dispersion relations of which I am aware (excepting [Cosgrove 2016]), and the referee has not supplied a reference.

The results are also rather confusing. For example, in figures 8-10, the plots seem to show parallel wavelengths in excess of 1000 km at altitudes of 100-150 km, even though the ionosphere is strongly inhomogeneous on such scales.

First, the “results” in figures 8-10 are not the main results of the paper, they are just some intermediate plots and secondary results.

Anyway, there is nothing confusing or strange about this. Inhomogeneity does not constrain the local wavelength. The wavelength at a given altitude depends only on the local ionospheric parameters at that

altitude, like the density and collision-frequency and etc. The model handles the vertical inhomogeneity by piecing together many short pieces of waves, where the properties of the waves, including wavelength, change with altitude. This is how transmission line theory works.

And by the way, over most of that altitude range the wavelength for both modes is less than 1000 km, and generally much less. Perhaps the referee should look at the figures again.

It is difficult to reconcile the results of the model to any observable quantities. For example, I would have expected plots of the calculated electric and magnetic field perturbations as a function of altitude, but such results are not presented.

This statement is not correct. It appears that the referee has not looked at the figures in the section “Model Results,” which appears right before the concluding section. Figure 14e shows plots of electric and magnetic field versus altitude. But the main observable studied in the paper is the ionospheric input admittance, the real part of which is the ionospheric conductance. Figures 13-15 all contain plots of the ionospheric conductance, comparing it to the field line integrated conductivity. The ionospheric conductance is an important parameter determining the inner boundary condition for global MHD models of the magnetosphere. So while I admit that this parameter is difficult to measure directly, it is heavily relied on for global modeling, where it is calculated electrostatically, as the field line integrated conductivity. This paper shows that this electrostatic calculation is unreliable.

As one final point, "Poisson" is misspelled as "Poison" through the paper.

This statement is not correct. In searching the paper I find one instance of “Poison” and five instances of “Poisson.” It does not seem that the reviewer has read much of the paper. This is a specious claim, and one wonders what is motivating the referee to be so hostile. Does the referee have a conflict of interest?

S.6.5.2 Referee #2

Report of the Second Referee -- EU12156 Cosgrove

This manuscript presents the development of a 1D, electromagnetic ionosphere model using the 5-moment, two fluid equations and based on the concept of stacked transmission lines driven by a source outside the ionosphere. The model itself is interesting; however, the presentation in the manuscript is both hard to follow and steeped with unnecessary re-derivations of well known results, and it is unclear why the model, and the development of the model, is not rooted in observational data.

The referee does not report the results to the editor. There is an insinuation that the results are “well known,” but the results discussed in this regard by the referee (below) are not the central results of the paper; and anyway the referee does not provide a reference, and so appears to be referring to results that are not valid in the E region ionosphere. The results claimed in the Abstract, which the referee does not acknowledge, are contained in Figures 12-15 of the Model Results section. It is usual for this material to appear in a review regardless of what the referee has to say about the methodology.

And with this referee it is quite clear that they are not suggesting any errors in the methodology (which is summarized in the Abstract). The referee does say that the methodology is “hard to follow,” but they do not mention any specific areas where they had difficulty. Instead, they say that new methodology should not be introduced, that the results can be derived in a different way. But even if the results could be derived in a different way, this is not an appropriate criticism of the paper; the referee should be judging whether the methodology is correct, and if the methodology is new that is a good thing.

The referee suggests that the paper contains “re-derivations.” However, I do not think this is the case, and the referee has not supplied a reference. The ionospheric conductance is mostly in the E region of the ionosphere, including the lower E region. Analyzing this region requires keeping all the collision terms in the 5-moment equations, and I do not know of any reference that contains the needed results. Since the referee does not mention the issue of the E region collision frequencies anywhere in the review, I suspect they have not considered it, and that there is in fact no reference available. It is hard to imagine how the ionospheric community could have persisted in relying completely on electrostatic theory if such a reference

existed, since that reference would have to show the importance of electromagnetic waves in the ionosphere.

Also, the derivation given in the paper includes quite a bit of analysis of potential sources of error relevant to the model, and it seems unlikely that this material would have been covered by other research that did not having the specific goal of developing the model. The referee has complained about the length of the derivation, but the alternative is a model that is less rigorous and therefore less defensible. Although I would like to believe that the referee's failure to acknowledge the main results was not intentional, the unexpected nature of these results require that the paper be rigorous and complete. Including detail allows the diligent reader to understand the derivation.

With respect to the comment about observational data, my reply follows just below.

Below are detailed several major points that, if well addressed, would significantly improve the manuscript. They are presented in no particular order.

1) The ionosphere is a well observed system, so why not use the observations to both constrain and test the model?

When a calculation employs simplifications or approximations to an accepted physical theory, the simplifications or approximations can be tested theoretically by performing a more complete calculation based on the same accepted physical theory. This kind of a test provides insight beyond that provided by an experimental test, because the reason for any discrepancy can be identified as the simplification or approximation that was removed. In addition, what is possible in the ionosphere is observational testing, not experimental testing, where the difference lies in the ability to rigorously analyze the errors. Because observational testing does not allow for rigorous error analysis, it is subject to a confirmation bias. Hence, theoretical testing of the approximations should always be done first, when possible, with observational testing coming afterward.

In particular, the purpose of the paper is to test whether the simplifications that lead to electrostatic theory are appropriate for calculating the ionospheric conductance, given vertical profiles for the local ionospheric parameters. (The ionospheric conductance is the real part of the input admittance seen from the top of the ionosphere.) It is possible that we need to use a more complete form of our accepted physical theory, which is electromagnetics. The model is meant to supply this more complete form, for testing, and to form the basis for a replacement if one is found necessary (which it is).

It is possible that the referee was confused by the use of the term "model," given that there are such things as "assimilative models" and "empirical models," which involve data. Assimilative models are formed by combining the best possible theoretical model with data, and should never be based on inapplicable theory. Getting the theory as correct as possible is the first step, and that is the goal of the paper.

Finally, it is naive to suggest that the ionosphere is a "well observed system." The E region ionosphere, where is most of the ionospheric conductivity, is quite inaccessible. The ionospheric community works very hard to collect what data it can, but the challenges are great. Satellites can survive only for a very short time in the E region, and so do not go there except to die. Incoherent scatter radar cannot measure electric field in the E region, except by assuming perfect mapping from the F region, which is exactly the assumption being tested in this work. Lidar has so far been altitude limited such that it can say little about the E region. Green line imagers provide intriguing E-region observation that are not resolved in altitude. TEC measurements are dominated by the topside of the F region. Imaging coherent scatter radar sees backscatter only when irregularities are present. Ionosondes are mostly limited to vertical density information (although there exist advanced systems that are able to obtain certain horizontal information). Rockets can include a nice suite of instruments, but do not stay aloft very long, and the instruments are very hard to reuse. The preceding should not be read as a criticism of the ionospheric community! The point is that the E region ionosphere is very difficult to access and definitive experiments are not, at present, possible.

See further comments below on whether "electrostatic theory" is the best term to use.

A significant portion of the manuscript is spent deriving the wave modes of the 5-moment mode and determining whether the various modes can propagate in the ionosphere, only to re-discover that only the Alfvén and whistler modes can propagate. Why not leverage known research that these are the two relevant modes and simply focus on them from the beginning?

This has already been answered. I am not aware of any results for waves in the 5-moment equations that do not make approximations with respect to the collision frequency terms, and which are therefore not

valid in the E region. Since the E region and collisions in general are critical to the ionospheric conductance, approximations with respect to the collision terms would not be appropriate for this study. The referee has suggested there is “known research,” but has not supplied a reference. Such a reference would imply electromagnetic effects in the ionosphere, and so the existence of such a reference would be inconsistent with the fact that electrostatic theory is well-accepted in the ionosphere.

Also, the paper does not find that “only the Alfvén and whistler modes can propagate” in the ionosphere. Two additional propagating modes are found. These modes are omitted from the model because they have very short dissipation scale lengths and minimal coupling to the Alfvén and whistler modes. If included, they would only serve to reduce the agreement with electrostatic theory. This is explained in Section VC. However, one of these modes has characteristics showing that it may be involved in certain anomalous ionospheric observations from the equatorial region. So the methodology described in the paper opens up new opportunities for studying collisional waves in the ionosphere.

Also, it is stated in the manuscript that “It is difficult to know where the model stands with respect to observational studies, since it is really necessary to evaluate each observational campaign in light of the model expectations for the particular event or statistical sampling of events.” Of course it is true that this model or any realistic model will produce different results for each event; that is the entire point of producing an accurate model, after all. Therefore, a particular event should be chosen as a baseline for comparison. As it stands, this paper makes no direct contact with any observation, making it impossible to judge the accuracy of the model. The end goal of this model is to be incorporated into the CCMC and InGEO models for public use, but the zeroth order test for inclusion in these global models is that the ionosphere model reproduce, at least, basic observations.

First, the “end goal” was meant as a long-term goal after additional development, which is why it was only mentioned in the second to last paragraph of the paper. It is not appropriate to criticize a paper for failure to achieve *future* goals. The immediate goal is to show that an electromagnetic calculation of the ionospheric conductance gives, in some cases, very different results from the approximate electrostatic calculation that is used in current practice. This is a purely theoretical result that is important, because it strongly suggests that the current theoretical approach is not reliable. It does this by showing that a more complete theory (electromagnetic versus electrostatic) gives very different results. Observations are not required to derive this kind of result, which is lucky because contrary to the referee’s assertion, the needed observations do not exist. Satellites are in re-entry at E-region altitudes. There is no way to obtain the simultaneous vertical and horizontal resolution that is needed, and in fact, electrostatic theory is often used to help the process along with regularization [e.g., Nicolls, Cosgrove, and Bahcivan, JGR, 2014]. We have been relying on the electrostatic calculation without good observational *or* theoretical support. But the theoretical test is possible, and is what this paper provides for the first time.

Second, I don’t agree with the referee’s statement that there has to be observational validation before a model can be included in CCMC, and definitely not for InGeo. If there is a theoretical demonstration that the electrostatic calculation of conductance is problematic, researchers need access to the alternative theory. Otherwise, observational testing is not even possible, except by those who work directly with me. In the interest of advancing science, models of all kinds should be shared, not kept private.

Third, the referee’s comment that the “paper makes no direct contact with any observation” is misleading. The model calculates many observables. The most important one is the ionospheric conductance, which can (in principle) be measured by a satellite constellation at the top of the ionosphere [e.g., *Burke et al.*, 2017], and determines the inner boundary condition needed for global MHD modeling. But the model also calculates altitude profiles for electric field, magnetic field, ion velocity, electron velocity, ion density, electron density, ion temperature, and electron temperature. The referee only means that applications to specific observed events are left to future research.

2) Wave modes of the 5-moment system, naming conventions, and descriptions. As noted above, a considerable portion of the manuscript is spent deriving the wave modes of the 5-moment, two fluid system; however, this is a well studied system of equations, whose wave modes are also well known. So, why spend so much time re-deriving them?

This has already been answered. I do not know of any such results and the referee has not supplied a reference. The issue is a lack of full inclusion of the collision frequency terms in the 5-moment equations.

To my knowledge, the results I have given here are the only ones that fully include these collision terms (excepting [Cosgrove 2016]). And this full inclusion is necessary to treat the E region, which is essential to this work.

Importantly, why after re-deriving known results are different naming conventions employed, i.e., why is contact not made with existing literature for ease of comparison and establishing a common language?

Specifically, why “create” two modes, thermal and ion (acoustic mode/short wavelength limit of the MHD slow mode), rather than refer to them by their conventional names? Also, the Alfvén mode seems to be incorrectly labelled, as detailed below.

This is about what are the best names to use for the waves found in the analysis. To my knowledge “ion acoustic mode” is a standard name, which I shortened to “ion mode,” as stated on page 13, and which is standard practice in the ionospheric community. Is the referee wishing that I retain the word “acoustic” throughout the paper? I can certainly do that, but was hoping to avoid using a two-word name.

Also, it is not clear what name the referee is suggesting I use for what I called the “thermal mode.” In my understanding there are three MHD modes plus a non-propagating entropy mode. Perhaps the latter is the thermal mode, which can propagate when collisions are included? The referee has not supplied any references and so their assertion of waves being “well known” with “conventional” names is not convincing. What is well known is that there is a literal zoo of names for wave modes, and in many cases the names are associated with the simplifications that were used to derive them. Since I do not use these simplifications the associations are not necessarily clear (more below).

The names I have chosen are ones I think will be comfortable for the ionospheric community, but may not be so comfortable for researchers from other communities. There does not seem to be any way to avoid this compromise.

In the comment about the Alfvén mode, the referee did not mention any specific figures or text, but to the extent the comment is understandable it is addressed below. Also, I have additional reason for not using the MHD naming scheme that I will save for below.

The wave modes derived seem incorrect, although this is difficult to evaluate because the dispersion relations of the modes are not presented in a manner that is easy to interpret. The whistler wave lies on the fast magnetosonic dispersion surface and transitions from the fast mode at large, MHD, scales to the whistler mode for scales $k_{\perp} d_i$ and/or $k_{\parallel} d_i \gg 1$, where d_i is the ion inertial length. Similarly, in the 5-moment system, the large-scale, shear Alfvén dispersion surface transitions to the Alfvén ion cyclotron mode for $k_{\parallel} d_i \gg 1$ but $k_{\perp} d_i \lesssim 1$, or the kinetic Alfvén wave for $k_{\perp} d_i \gg 1$, which can then couple to the first ion Bernstein mode if $k_{\perp} d_i > 1$ and $k_{\parallel} d_i > 1$, and eventually becomes electrostatic for scales $d_e \sim 1$. If you are in the limit that the Alfvén speed is larger than the electron thermal speed, i.e., electron beta is less than the mass ratio, then rather than becoming a kinetic Alfvén wave, the large-scale Alfvén wave transition to an inertial Alfvén wave. It is also possible, for $\beta < 1$ but not mass ratio small, to have combined aspects of the kinetic Alfvén and inertial Alfvén wave. Given these facts, it is entirely unclear to me why the whistler wave and shear Alfvén wave are discussed as being simultaneously relevant to the system, since if the whistler wave is relevant, the scale range of interest must lie in the ion cyclotron, kinetic Alfvén wave, or inertial Alfvén wave range, none of which have simple linear dispersion relations.

First, I note that the referee has given a very complex recipe for sorting the modes and their properties. All of this complexity is eliminated by the methodology adopted in this paper.

And second, there is still the same issue as before. To my knowledge, the results I have given here are the only ones that fully include the collision frequency terms in the 5-moment equations; and these terms are critical in the E-region ionosphere, where the neutral collision frequencies are very high. So if the modes seem different that is not relevant. The explanation is that fully including the collision frequency terms makes a big difference, at least in the E region. As far as the linear/non-linear comment is concerned, the dispersion relations found in the paper are not limited to linear ones, as is evident from Figure 8 (for example). The paper also explains that the 5-moment equations are fluid equations and so do not include kinetic effects, which is sufficient to ensure that the treatment is more general than electrostatic theory, since the latter doesn’t include kinetic effects either.

There is also a more fundamental issue here about what is meant by “dispersion relation” and “wave.” Formally, a system of 16 equations-of-motion supports 16 eigenmodes, where a “wave” involves two of these

modes, because the direction of propagation can be reversed. There is a single dispersion relation corresponding to these 16 equations, which will be a polynomial having 16 roots, one for each mode. (The polynomial comes from the eigenvalue problem for the equations of motion, as described in Section III of the paper.) We can imagine solving the single polynomial dispersion relation for the roots where, in analogy with the quadratic equation, we will obtain a solution involving square and higher roots with \pm signs. There will be 16 possible permutations for the \pm signs, and each permutation can be viewed as producing a sub-dispersion relation for a single mode. Contrast this picture with what the referee is describing: when the referee refers to a “dispersion relation” for a “wave,” they are actually referring to a limited portion of one of these sub-dispersion relations, what might be called a “dispersion branch,” as now explained.

To my knowledge, no one has ever written-out the full analytical solution for the (single) dispersion relation of the (collisional) electromagnetic 5-moment equations, with all the square and higher roots and \pm signs. What is normally done instead is to employ various physical assumptions to approximate the sub-dispersion relations over limited regions, resulting in what I call dispersion branches; these are waves as categorized by physical type. The different dispersion branches are one way to define different kinds of waves, and result in the well known “zoo of waves” with a complex relationship among them (hence the referee’s description above). Under this definition, a term like “whistler wave” may only be applicable over a certain range of altitude (for example). This approach is useful in that it facilitates a physical understanding of wavelike disturbances that may be detected in data. But in a case where it is desired to form a continuous wave-description over a range of physical conditions, such as over a range of collision frequencies (range of altitudes, for the ionosphere), the approximations will breakdown in certain areas. So we cannot use these (approximate) dispersion branches to form a model that is reliable and accurate over the full range of ionospheric altitudes.

Instead, the present paper uses standard matrix analysis tools to solve for all 16 roots exactly (numerically), so that all the terms in the 5-moment equations can be retained, including all collision terms over all altitudes. What are normally considered different wave branches may be fused together over altitude, because the approximations that separate them are not used. This is described in some detail in the paper. The referee is apparently objecting to this and requiring instead that I use the many approximate wave expressions (dispersion branches). Attempting to follow the referee’s suggestion would not result in a satisfactory model, because the approximations could never be defended over the full height of the ionosphere, owing to the wide range of collision frequencies that exist; trying to piece together the many approximate dispersion branches would be a nightmare; there is no one-to-one map between the physically-defined waves and the more formally-defined waves in the paper. And in fact, I do not believe that there exist any of the approximate results that are applicable to the high-collision-frequencies of the E region ionosphere; there are probably new “collisional” dispersion branches that have not been previously studied, but which are included in the model of the present paper.

The exploration of which of the electromagnetic modes has electrostatic counterparts in various limits is also strange, and I do not understand why it is done; however, this is again well explored territory in various wave textbooks and published papers. For instance, it is stated that “We find that electrostatic waves are good approximations for electromagnetic waves when the transverse wavelength is less than about 100 m.” 100 m is approximately the electron inertial length, based on a density of $\sim 10^9 \text{ m}^{-3}$ used in the manuscript. Scales below the electron inertial length for the Alfvén dispersion branch within the 5-moment model are electrostatic; therefore, the statement in the manuscript and, very lengthy, derivation of this result were obvious from the outset based on the physics contained in the model. Note that for a more realistic density of 10^{11} , this scale becomes $\sim 10\text{m}$, significantly altering the conclusions in the manuscript, which could be easily ameliorated by using dimensionless units, i.e., the electrostatic transition scale for the Alfvén branch is always d_e in the 5-moment model. Note also that the fact that the fast/whistler branch does not have an electrostatic counterpart is well known. The fast mode branch, when followed from large to small scales at fixed propagation angle, transitions from fast to whistler to upper hybrid to R wave, all of which are fully electromagnetic.

The referee asserts that it is well known that the waves are electromagnetic, at least above a few hundred meters in scale. How can we reconcile this with the fact that electrostatic theory is considered completely reliable in the ionosphere? Either ionospheric scientists are completely ignorant of the results the referee asserts, or the referee is in error. So this is yet again the same issue: given that the referee has not supplied a

reference, and does not mention collision frequency, the most likely explanation is that the referee is referring to results that do not fully include the collision frequency terms. The collisional effects are very important in the E region, and results may be quite different if they aren't fully included.

The calculations in this work *do* fully include the collision frequency terms, but require a numerical computation of the eigenvalues/eigenvectors, and so it is difficult to evaluate if the electron inertial length is always the transition scale. Given the ionospheric communities total reliance on electrostatic theory, this community apparently believes that collisional effects greatly increase the scale at which electromagnetic effects become important.

The referee has discussed the transition from the fast mode to the whistler mode as associated with changes in scale. But in the paper is found an apparently similar mode transition associated with changes in *collision frequency*, with transverse scale held constant. So the collisional effects are very important, and given that they have been used as part of the justification for electrostatic theory in the ionosphere, it is necessary to re-examine the electromagnetic nature of the waves with collisions fully included. Ionospheric models are almost exclusively based on either electrostatic waves or full electrostatic theory, and so apparently have assumed that collisional effects eliminate the electromagnetic nature that the referee is referring to. We need to know if these models are reliable. The referee's statement that the waves are electromagnetic implies that they believe these models are not reliable, which reinforces the need for the present paper.

Also, the referee's comment concerns only secondary results of the paper that come essentially for free, from the formalism developed for the central question of the ionospheric conductance. So the comment concerning a "very lengthy derivation" is inapplicable. When secondary results are easily obtained, they are presented, but there is no room to pursue them further. Also, the length of the derivation should not be an issue on which the paper is evaluated. What matters is the correctness of the derivation, and proving correctness requires detail.

The above points could be significantly clarified if rather than the lengthy derivations given in the paper, a table supplying and summarizing which modes exist or are evanescent at each altitude, together with their properties, e.g., wavelength range, frequency, and the parameters of the ionosphere, e.g., plasma beta, density, ion and electron temperature, etc, at that altitude. Importantly, the wave properties should be given in normalized units, e.g., $k_{\perp} d_i$ and ω / Ω_{ci} , where Ω_{ci} is the ion cyclotron frequency, because the normalized quantities determine the universal physics of the waves; whereas, an Alfvén wave with wavelength of, for instance, 1000 km has vastly different meaning in the ionosphere vs a magnetar magnetosphere or the solar wind.

Note that the referees list of parameters does not include collision frequency. So it's the same issue: I do not know of any derivations in the literature that fully include collision frequency, and the way I manage to include it involves a numerical calculation of the eigenvectors/eigenvalues. In this case, it is not clear what the natural scalings should be. One likely change is the normalization of frequency, which should probably include a collision frequency contribution (and not just Ω_{ci} , as the referee suggests). I know this from the analytical derivation of a collisional dispersion relation that I gave in my 2016 paper. Trying to figure out a universal normalization within this semi-numerical scheme is not practical, at least not at this time. And it is not needed to derive the central results of the paper (which the referee has omitted from their report).

The idea that the model could be based on the existing approximate dispersion branches (for the zoo of waves) is not tenable, as already argued above. Instead, the paper solves the equations of motion in a rigorous manner, and derives the model from the solution. Using a rigorous solution makes the model more reliable, which is extremely important given that the results are apparently so unexpected that both referees have omitted them from their reports.

3) It is very difficult to follow what assumption are employed in different portions of the manuscript. For instance, density profiles and other parameter profiles are given in figure A.1, but then an array of various constant densities are stated throughout the manuscript for computing quantities and producing figures, but the physical behavior in the figures associated with the constant densities appears to be due to the density profile shown in figure A.1.

The referee states "the physical behavior in the figures associated with the constant densities appears to be due to the density profile shown in figure A.1." The vertical character the referee is seeing is caused

by the collision frequency profiles, not density, which again leads me to believe that the referee has in mind results that do not incorporate collision frequency. The referee is not familiar with the effects of the neutral collisions on waves, because these are new results. A constant vertical profile has been used for plasma density so that these new results will not be obscured by plasma density effects.

The density is given in the caption of every figure, and it is stated repeatedly that they are constant vertical profiles. The only exception is one trace in Figure 12C (green trace), as indicated in the legend and caption and text. The referee does not say which figures they are referring to, and so it is hard to know where additional clarification is needed. Given that the density is stated in every figure caption, there is no general inadequacy that I can discern. However, I have added notations such as “at all altitudes,” so that the density call-outs in the captions will be even more clear.

Related to figure A.1, some of the data in the figure is stated to be “derived from Sondrestrom incoherent scatter data.” Is it previously published data? Is it averaged over some time period? What is the date and time of the observation(s)? Also, why use textbook data from 1978, reference 51, for estimating the collision frequency in the same figure? There are surely newer, more accurate measurements of ionospheric density and temperature from which you could calculate the collision frequencies.

The Sondrestrom data is only used in one trace of one figure (Figure 12C, the green trace), for purposes of comparison to something more realistic than the constant profiles used everywhere else (for the reasons just explained). So this data is essentially irrelevant to the results and does not merit such a detailed pedigree. Actually, the neutral collision frequencies do not depend on the plasma density, but they do depend critically on the neutral density and composition, which varies quite a bit and is also *very* difficult to measure in the ionosphere. For this reason, representative neutral collision-frequency profiles are all that is really possible. However, they are also all that is needed to demonstrate the behavior of the model; we are not trying to model a specific event at this time. Also, the paper describes the reasons for the choice and why one other alternative was not used, while showing that it would give similar results. Also, the referee does not reference any newer results that would be superior for the purpose, and merely says “surely” there is one.

4) As noted in point 1 above, one of the goals of this model is to be implemented in global modeling codes such as the CCMC and InGeo, but I do not understand how the model as given in the current manuscript could be implemented. Generally, global models need to compute the parallel current and perpendicular electric field at the ionosphere boundary; however, the ionosphere model in the manuscript is based on waves propagating in the ionosphere driven by a harmonic source. The source seems disconnected from what magnetosphere models would supply to the ionosphere model. Additionally, magnetosphere models rarely go to altitudes lower than $\sim 1-2 R_{\text{Earth}}$, which is an order of magnitude above what is considered in the current manuscript.

The paper presents results for the ionospheric input admittance, which is the ratio of the parallel current to the divergence of perpendicular electric field at the ionospheric boundary, and is the quantity used by the global models. This quantity is plotted three different ways in the concluding figure (Figure 15, real part), and is also plotted in Figure 14 and Figure 13. The definition of the input admittance was given in equation (1).

The way that the input admittance can be calculated from a wave theory is thoroughly covered in the paper, with the main concepts being presented in Section II. For example, at the bottom of page 3 there are the sentences,

“The input admittance associated with a single wave propagating away is commonly referred to as the characteristic admittance of the wave, Y_0 . It is this quantity that enters into the well-known TL expression for the input admittance to a transmission line terminated by a load admittance Y_L ” (the equation follows)

I would suggest that the referee reread Section II. And also the referee should reread the Introduction, where it is explained that transmission line (TL) theory is specifically appropriate for calculating input admittance, and other circuit quantities.

As far as applying the conductance model to global magnetospheric modeling, there is a dependence on wavelength that would have to be accounted for. The paper derives the Fourier components of the

conductance, and these would have to be combined to model a particular disturbance. (Although, each Fourier component can be viewed as representing the behavior at a particular scale.) This is discussed in the concluding section. However, as mentioned above, deployment to CCMC or InGeo is an “end goal” and we are not there yet. The purpose of mentioning this goal was to show the potential for replacing electrostatic theory with this model, as opposed to just showing the limitations of electrostatic theory.

As far as the altitude of lower boundary for magnetospheric models, this problem is well known and the accommodations all involve using in some way the ionospheric conductance (real part of the input admittance), which is what is provided by the model. (Actually, the model provides both the real and imaginary parts, but it appears the imaginary parts are generally small, so far.)

The ionosphere model as currently described also has severe limitations, 100-1000km, on the transverse wavelengths of modes considered. A magnetosphere model to which this ionosphere model would be coupled would inject a broad spectrum of modes, far exceeding the limited range the current ionosphere model can handle. Thus, at best, the ionosphere model as described needs significant improvement before it can be employed as part of a global model.

This is why the main purpose of the paper is to show that an electromagnetic calculation of the ionospheric conductance gives, in some cases, very different results from the approximate electrostatic calculation that is used in current practice. This provides the motivation to further develop the model.

5) There are many other, lesser issues with the manuscript that I am reluctant to fully enumerate in light of significant criticisms noted above, e.g., proper historical references for the 5-moment model; multiple definitions of what it means to be electrostatic, some of which are incorrect (formally, it only means partial $B/\partial t = 0$ or $\text{curl } E = 0$, not a fully steady-state electromagnetic system as the first sentence of the manuscript states); the first reference of section III is missing; red versus blue color coding in figure 6, etc. . .

The first reference of Section III is the reference for the 5-moment equations; I am sorry that it was broken. It was meant to be the textbook by Schunk and Nagy. Will that be sufficient?

The ionospheric conductivity is calculated by setting all time derivatives to zero. The conductance is calculated (electrostatically) by integrating this conductivity along the geomagnetic field. This can be discovered, for example, in the textbook by Kelley (1989) that is referenced in the paper. (It is possible to have a frequency dependent version, but in practice the frequency is always set to zero, which is equivalent to setting the time derivatives to zero.) The Farley, 1959, reference describes the underlying methodology, which ionospheric physicists call electrostatic theory, and which proceeds by setting all time derivatives to zero. Also, looking at the classic electromagnetics textbook by Jackson, I find as the first line of the first electrostatics chapter, “We begin our discussion of electrodynamics with the subject of electrostatics—phenomena involving time-independent distributions of charge and fields.” So the standard usage of the term “electrostatic theory” is for a theory of time-independent systems, and in physics they must arise as the steady state of a time-evolving system. This all supports the definition I have given for “electrostatic theory.”

In the last paragraph of the Introduction I explained the distinction between this and the methodology I think the referee is referring to, which is commonly called “electrostatic waves” by ionospheric physicists. Apparently the referee did not read this paragraph. This comment by the referee causes me to wonder if they understood the purpose of the paper, which is to test the former “electrostatic theory,” the one that is used to justify using the field line integrated conductivity for the ionospheric input conductance. If the referee did not understand this than I can see why they would have trouble understanding the results in the paper. This is something I could clarify in the Introduction, except that the referee has not offered enough detail to enable me to understand where they became confused. I thought that I had covered this quite well, for example in the second paragraph of the paper there appears,

“To narrow the problem to one that is tractable, we focus on modeling the “ionospheric conductance” [e.g., 10, 11] for a vertically stratified ionosphere. . . which is meant to represent the input admittance to the ionosphere as seen from the magnetosphere Under electrostatic theory it is derived by integrating the (zero frequency) ionospheric conductivity along the geomagnetic field. Dropping the assumption that it is purely real, and dropping the assumption

that it can be derived from electrostatic theory, we arrive at an important problem that is well suited to TL modeling, that of deriving the ionospheric input admittance.”

S.6.5.3 Referee #3

Report of the Third Referee -- EU12156/Cosgrove

In this manuscript, the author develops a model of ‘ionospheric conductance’ via novel combination of Transmission Line theory and electromagnetic 5-moment fluid equations. The ionosphere is modeled as a stacked layer of transmission lines, and the transmission lines are taken to support waves allowed within the framework of the 5-moment fluid equations. Development of the methodology is, to the referee’s knowledge, novel, and thus a major strength of the work. In addition to the methodological advancement, the work has applicational importance, with the potential to improve numerical simulations which employ models of ionospheric conductance based on electrostatic theory. The work is interesting, but the referee also thinks the presentation can be streamlined, and clarified; below are several suggestions/questions toward this end:

1. It is the referee’s opinion that clarity will improve if Section III is distilled (to the extent possible) to focus on the steps in going from Eq. 7 to Eqs. 12–14. For example, discussion of the homogeneous solution before focusing on solution to the full driven problem may provide physical insight, but it also adds, perhaps, inessential discussion with respect to the results that are needed in Section IV. Clarity of Section IV would benefit from a similar streamlining (i.e., shortening to focus on the essential steps in the derivation needed to establish the model).

Even though other referees have made similar comments, I do not wish to remove the material that provides physical insight. And given that the correctness of the work is apparently being doubted in indirect and unstated ways, I feel the need to retain as much rigor as possible also. So in the final 2022 paper I have attempted to organize the material by providing the reader with a bold-face labeling of blocs of text, so that they can better choose what they wish to read and what they may wish to skip. Hence, the main derivation begins with an intuitive approach under the header “The Intuitive Derivation of the Steady-State Solution,” and then after this continues with the rigorous derivation under the header “Validating the Steady-State Solution.” The reader who wants a user-level understanding of the model does not need to read the second of these, which would be primarily for the reader wanting to advance or further validate the model.

2. The author mentions problems evaluating the model for transverse wavelengths outside the range 100—1000 km; certainly numerical issues can creep into solvers before an error is thrown, so how robust, with respect to numerical precision, are the results within this range?

The question of numerical accuracy is discussed at the end of Section 7.4 of the final 2022 paper. With respect to whether the resonance is real, the issue is in the accuracy of the parallel wavelength. All indications are that the parallel wavelength is very accurate, and certainly sufficient for prediction of the resonance.

With respect to the reflection that is keeping the signal from penetrating, the issue is whether sufficiently small changes can be resolved in the polarization vectors, so that the reflection is accurately calculated. Since we see this effect also when only the Alfvén wave is used in the model, it is informative to first consider this simpler case. We find that plotting the components of the polarization vector versus altitude reveals a smooth change without noise, and so it appears that the changes in the polarization vectors are sufficiently resolved. This should also validate the absolute-accuracy of the polarization vectors, to the extent that there is no bias in the eigenvalue/eigenvector calculation (which seems unlikely since it is basically numerical root finding). Also, the eigenvalues/eigenvectors are checked by multiplying the eigenvector by the matrix (H_5), and comparing the result to the eigenvector multiplied to the eigenvalue. The agreement is typically to 15 decimal places.

The accuracy is equally good for both modes. However, when both modes are present and they become nearly degenerate (which happens), there is an additional question of whether the modes are sufficiently differentiated, so that the mode-mixing is accurate. But this only affects the two mode

case, and then only when they become nearly degenerate. So this doesn't affect the basic conclusions.

Please see Section 7.4 for additional discussion, including of why the range has been limited to 100-1000 km transverse wavelength.

3. I am curious about the sharp features in Fig. 15 a, around altitude 125 km (the feature is especially pronounced for the dark yellow curve for density 8×10^{-3}). According to Fig. 10 c, the parameters are evidently within the range of validity for the various linear approximations of the theory, so is the feature numerical in nature, or a physical prediction of the model?

The final 2022 paper includes considerable discussion of the electric field cutoff (Section 7.3), and of the spiky or kinky features (Section 7.4). It appears that they are a real prediction, although they are probably not being fully resolved. The explanation for these features appears to be that the matrix H_5 is degenerate or nearly degenerate at some E region altitude, with the Alfvén and Whistler waves becoming nearly parallel to one another. This is definitely an area where further research should be performed. However, the kinky features go away when only the Alfvén wave is used in the model, while all the other unexpected features remain (such as the resonance and the greatly reduced conductance). So it seems clear that the kinky features are not related to the main results.

It should be noted that this is the kind of feature that may not be contained in the finite-difference, time-domain models that are also sometimes used for the ionosphere, because of the MHD simplifications they employ (to eliminate the radio-frequency modes), and also because their altitude resolution is limited.

4. For transverse wavelengths greater than 100 km, what does the equivalent version of Fig. 10 c look like? Since the model is explored for transverse wavelengths in the range 100—1000 km, demonstrating validity of linear approximations over this full range will improve robustness of presented results.

Since validating the integral approximations seemed to be very important, I have now developed a more rigorous approach to validation. As a result, figures like Figure 10c are not used in the final 2022 paper. Instead, I am now doing numerical integrations for selected conditions and extracting the critical components for comparison to the analytical solution. The results are reported in Section 4 of the final 2022 paper, and elaborated on in Section S.5 of this Supplementary Information. The results have given me a very high degree of confidence in the critical parallel-wavelength parameter. They have also given me high confidence in the polarization vectors, although there are some inconclusive results near 100 km in altitude. The latter is not likely to have an effect, because the model is not very sensitive to changes in that area. The lack of sensitivity is probably because the energy is not getting down that low in altitude. If the source were instead placed in the lower E-region (to evaluate other physical questions), the issue may become more important. Hence, this issue is deserving of further research.

5. Is it possible that the approximations in Fig. 10 c are an overestimate, given that modes other than Whistler and Alfvén are assumed to not dissipate energy? If this is an overestimate, does it have any meaningful impact on conductance computed via the model?

I'm not sure I understand the question. It is possible that the answer to the previous question addresses this one also. On the other hand, if the issue is the effect of omitting the Ion and Thermal modes, then I think the referee is correct that omitting them will tend to overestimate the conductance. The signal would tend to be dissipated by coupling into those modes, and so would not penetrate as deeply. The conductivity at lower altitudes would not make as much of a contribution to the conductance. However, this is based on intuition and needs testing.

6. Can a limit be taken in the model to recover exactly (to machine precision) known results from the electrostatic theory? Even if the electrostatic results are provably wrong (assuming the presented model is a better one), this agreement may help to reduce any doubt with respect to numerical precision within the asserted range of numerical validity, i.e. transverse wavelengths 100—1000 km.

It does not appear that the waves have the right properties to reproduce electrostatic theory exactly under any conditions I have been able to uncover. However, for purposes of validating the other aspects of the model (other than the absolute-accuracy of the eigenvectors/eigenvalues), I have included a

section in the final 2022 paper where the waves are artificially modified to have the properties that were identified in Section 3. Doing this results in an exact reproduction of electrostatic theory (column a of Figure 3). This shows that the model is working as intended. It also validates the conditions for electrostatic theory that were derived in Section 3 (and also the additional conditions when two modes are present, from equation 21). The issues of resolution and numerical precision are discussed in Section 7.4 of the final 2022 paper.

7. For transparency, reproducibility, and for the benefit of other researchers who might like to use such a model, the referee encourages the author to make the implementation open-source and publicly available (if at all possible).

I absolutely agree, that is the plan! Although since funding is lacking, if anybody thinks they might like to help with this please feel free to contact me.

S.6.5.4 Referee #4

Report of the Fourth Referee -- EU12156/Cosgrove

I have struggled with this paper. And some of my assessments are given as "maybe" because of my lack of familiarity with the scope of Physical Review E (PRE) articles. Looking at the Journal website I would think that the article is out of scope for PRE - but I consider that to ultimately be an Editor decision. I am somewhat surprised that the paper has not been submitted to journals that are more geophysics/space physics in scope as the subject matter is firmly in the area of space plasma physics. The topic of the paper is wave propagation through the collisional ionosphere, taking into account the variation of collision frequencies and plasma parameters as a function of height.

I was hoping this journal might be able to find referees who would not be subject to the groupthink that seems to be dominating the reviews of this article.

I consider the paper to be correct in the governing equations used to generate the wave-propagation solutions. But I do not consider the work to be particularly new, at least in terms of the physics. What may be new is the methodology used to find solutions of the 16-variable coupled equations. But the results are not particularly new either. The author appears to be unaware of work that has been done in this area over the years. I concur with the author that only recently have models that use a thick, i.e., height resolved, ionosphere been developed. But at the same time it is not at all clear that the thin ionosphere models are in serious error for low enough frequency and long enough vertical wavelength. In essence this is similar to asking when a WKB approach should be used for wave propagation instead of a Snell's Law approach.

The referee says that they consider the methodology to be correct! But the referee does not tell the editor about the main results claimed in the paper. The results are simply omitted, and some of the subsidiary results are discussed in their stead (below).

In fact, the referee makes the statement "...it is not at all clear that the thin ionosphere models are in serious error..." which is in direct contradiction to the results in the paper (the results that they did not report to the editor). It is not possible that the referee could have missed these results because the first sentence of the Abstract finishes "computing the total conductance for a vertically stratified ionosphere, which we compare to the field line integrated conductivity, finding significant differences." And the referee's inclusion of the qualification "for low enough frequency and long enough vertical wavelength" does not excuse them because (a) the sentence still contradicts the results in the paper; (b) the Abstract specifically references "effects from short parallel wavelengths"; and (c) even were it not for (a) and (b) the sentence would still be highly misleading.

The referee began their review by writing "I have struggled with this paper." I can only guess that the referee is having a very hard time dealing with results that seem to contradict what they have believed for years, but where they can find no way to criticize the methodology. Rather than thinking that they are being deliberately misleading, I would prefer to believe that the referee is experiencing a short-circuiting of the brain that is causing them to be uncharacteristically nonsensical. Their language certainly does not seem hostile, so this seems likely.

This could be considered a minor issue, but the author does not appear to be knowledgeable about the low frequency wave modes in a magnetized plasma. In space plasma physics these have been called the fast, shear, and slow modes. The fast mode is the same as the mode identified by the author as the whistler wave, whereas the shear mode is called the Alfvén wave in the paper. This mode is sometimes called the Alfvén mode. The slow mode is the mode that corresponds to sound waves, and this mode may be related to one of the modes identified by the author for waves below the ionospheric density peak.

I am certainly familiar with the MHD wave modes! I have been working in this field for over 20 years and have read many articles and books. What the referee is reacting to is the choice of names for the modes, which are well in accord with the terminology used in ionospheric science, but which differ from the terminology used in magnetospheric science. In ionospheric science the term “ion acoustic wave” or “ion wave” is used to denote the mode associated with incoherent scatter radar; the term “whistler wave” is used for very low frequency waves from the ionosphere and atmosphere that are often detected on the ground; and the term “Alfvén wave” is used to denote the waves associated with the MI coupling interaction. There is a rough correspondence to the MHD “slow mode,” “fast mode,” and “shear mode,” but I would not want to mislead the reader into thinking they are the same.

One well known difference is that the usual whistler wave is derived using a high frequency approximation, whereas the MHD fast mode is derived in a low frequency approximation [e.g., *Stix*, 1992]. In particular, I chose the name “Whistler” instead of “fast mode” because in Cosgrove [2016] it was found that in the E region where these waves are able to propagate, they agreed better with the standard dispersion relation for the whistler wave than with the standard dispersion relation for the fast mode wave, using the dispersion relations from *Stix*, [1992]. In general I prefer the ionospheric terminology for this paper because using it implies that collisions are included in the calculations, whereas MHD waves are generally non-collisional, which makes them invalid in the ionosphere. The identification of waves is well known to result in a zoo of names and it is not possible to make everyone happy.

Finally, this is all a distraction. The purpose of the article is to compute the ionospheric conductance and electric field mapping. The purpose is not to study the relationship of the waves in the ionosphere with the MHD waves. While it seems likely that the MHD results would mirror results in the ionosphere in many ways, these results do not include collisions and so cannot be applied in this work. While it is interesting to make these comparisons, such comparisons are not the topic of this article, and are certainly not as important as the actual topic (which the referee did not tell the editor about).

I have provided detailed comments in the files appended below. Not knowing the author’s preferences, I have included a version of the comments where the files are embedded in the PDF as “pop-ups” (EU12156_with_embedded_comments.pdf). The second version lists the comments separately (Summary of Comments on EU12156.pdf). The author will notice that I have not provided detailed comments on some of the more technical sections (specifically the discussion on methods to solve the set of equations). I must confess that I did not find those sections particularly useful, but I am willing to accept that that could be a failing on my part.

Replies to the detailed comments are below. I appreciate that this referee is more polite than some of the previous ones. But the fact remains that the referee has not told the editor about the results in the paper.

But I also question the usefulness of the model for inclusion in other models, such as models that couple the magnetosphere to the ionosphere and neutral atmosphere. The author includes comments in the concluding remarks discussing the incorporation of the model in other coupled models as a future objective.

The ionospheric conductance is used by (almost?) all global MHD models. This paper finds that the current method of calculation is highly inaccurate, and provides a more rigorous replacement.

The model is essentially 1-dimensional (height variation). It was not clear how the model could be modified for 2-D or 3-D implementation.

This is a mischaracterization, the model calculates the Fourier components of a 3D signal in the ionosphere. It is therefore a 3D solution for small perturbations of an *initially* one-dimensional ionosphere. While it is true that extending the background ionosphere to higher dimensionality would be difficult, the normal way that conductance is calculated, as the field line integrated conductivity, also assumes a one-dimensional background ionosphere.

Why wouldn't a simple finite difference implementation on a 2-D or 3-D grid be sufficient? What makes the author's methodology for solving the coupled equations particularly useful?

"Simple" and "Sufficient" are odd choices of words, since those models are much more difficult to implement, require much more computing power, and involve much more numerical error. The reasons the method is more appropriate for the goals of the paper have been described in the Introduction and Background sections of the latest 2022 paper, and I will not repeat them here. However, the fact that "finite difference" methods have not been used to evaluate the ionospheric conductance (in any reference I can find, after many comments by many referees) is a pretty strong indicator that they are not appropriate for the problem.

Why is it superior to other methods?

The method is not "superior," it is different, with different strengths and weaknesses. It is a more analytical method that is especially useful for steady-state quantities like the ionospheric conductance. It provides more physical understanding with more clarity in the approximations, but is not as flexible as the numerical simulations with respect to geometry. Finding agreement between these two approaches is the way that the field can be advanced. And again, the reasons the method is more appropriate for the goals of the paper have been described in the Introduction and Background sections of the latest 2022 paper, and I will not repeat all of them here.

Detailed Comments from the Markup:

In my understanding the electrostatic approximation does not mean steady state. It means that the magnetic field is non time-varying, or varying so slowly that it can be ignored, and consequently only Gauss's law and charge conservation are required to investigate the variability of the electric field. The electric field can itself be time-varying. A simple example is plasma oscillation. This mode is purely electrostatic, but not time-stationary.

By "steady state" I do not mean no oscillation, I mean the condition after the source has turned on and been on for a long time. More specifically, I use the term "steady state" in the context of a solution found using the Laplace transform, where there is a transient response that can be discarded. What remains is commonly termed the "steady-state solution," although it may be an oscillatory solution, if the source that turned on was a harmonic source. This is the solution used in transmission line theory, such as the solution found in equation (12), which oscillates purely at frequency ω_0 . But this does not mean that the magnetic field can be ignored.

I draw the author's attention to Tu et al. (2014), Inductive-dynamic magnetosphere-ionosphere coupling via MHD waves, *J. Geophys. Res. Space Physics*, 119, 530–547, doi:10.1002/2013JA018982 who present a fully electromagnetic model of wave propagation through the height-resolved ionosphere. The results in that paper should be compared with those presented here.

I had been aware of that reference, but did not consider it very important since there was no field-aligned current in that model. What I did miss was their later works, but anyway their later works also did not include calculation of the ionospheric conductance, and so were not any more relevant than the earlier time-domain simulations that I did reference. As discussed in Sections 1 and 2, there are a number of issues with time-domain simulations that make them not so useful for the ionospheric conductance. So there are no comparisons to be made with any of the time domain simulations of which I am aware, so far.

Again, I think a clarification about what the author means by electrostatic might be in order. It is really a long wavelength approximation, so that the ionosphere appears to be a thin shell, and the reflection and transmission properties of the ionosphere are determined using height-integrated conductivities.

The first paragraph of the Introduction contains the words "...testing electrostatic theory which, when applicable, arises from the long-wavelength limit of TL theory." Also, Section 2 (Section 3 in the final 2022 version) was all about developing this idea of the long wavelength limit. Also, the idea of the long-wavelength limit was developed in [Cosgrove 2016], in defining the wave-Pedersen conductivity. So maybe the referee simply forgot to remove their comment after finishing this Section 2?

Also, the referees comment is odd because it seems to suggest that the parallel wavelength is long, without mentioning that the paper specifically finds that the parallel wavelength is NOT long. And it is not that the referee missed this result in the paper, because in their last comment they specifically object to this finding, based on a hand waving argument.

Also, what was meant by the term “electrostatic” was explained in the last paragraph of the Introduction. In the latest 2022 paper that discussion is expanded and appears in the second and third paragraphs of the Introduction. In both versions there was/is substantial effort made to distinguish between two cases, and it was explained that the terms “electrostatic theory” and “electrostatic waves” would be used to differentiate between the two.

I find the author’s use of Alfvén and Whistler wave to be inconsistent with the names assigned to the low frequency waves. In the MHD regime (i.e., for waves with frequencies below the lowest ion cyclotron frequency, assuming a multi ion species plasma) there are three wave modes for a warm plasma. These are known as the fast, shear, and slow modes. See, for example, Russell et al. (2016), Space Physics, Cambridge University Press. The slow mode corresponds to sound waves. The shear mode is sometimes referred to as the Alfvén mode, and this corresponds to bending (or shearing) of magnetic field lines. Assuming that the waves are first order this mode is non-compressive. On the other hand, the fast mode is compressive with the magnetic pressure and plasma pressure perturbations in phase. In a single ion species plasma the fast mode does couple to the whistler mode, although the whistler mode is usually thought of as an electron mode. In a multi ion species plasma the fast mode only couples to the whistler mode for parallel propagation. The presence of multiple ion gyro-resonances and ion-ion hybrid frequencies means that the fast mode does not couple to the whistler mode for non-parallel propagation. See, for example, Figure 13.7 in Russell et al. (2016).

The referee would like me to use the MHD terminology for the waves. Please see my response to the referees earlier remark along these lines. Basically, I do not want to use the MHD terms because MHD waves are generally non-collisional, and a major point of this article is that the collisions change the nature of the waves, and in so doing give rise to conductivity. If I used the usual MHD waves there would be no conductivity!

Another point that was not mentioned yet in responding to this referee (although was thoroughly covered in response to an earlier referee), is that the “waves” in this article are formally defined as eigenvectors, and are equated over the full altitude extent of the ionosphere. The referee is instead thinking about waves defined by making physical approximations, such as the high frequency approximation that ions are immobile, or the low-frequency collisionless MHD approximations. The latter approach may result in many different “kinds” of waves, far more than there are eigenvectors. There is no one-to-one mapping between these two different approaches to defining waves. In the approach of this article, it arises that the physical nature of a wave may change with altitude (changing collision frequency); but if they both correspond to the same eigenvector then I use only one name. An example is the relationship between the whistler and fast mode waves, which were found in [Cosgrove 2016] to correspond to the same eigenvector (using a smaller equation-set, but it also holds for the 5-moment equations). So it is really not appropriate to use the MHD terminology for the “waves” in this article.

I consider that the "wave Pedersen conductivity" is half the "DC" Pedersen conductivity is in fact in agreement with our understanding of wave incidence and reflection, even when using a "thin" ionosphere model. In particular, if the characteristic parameter $\mu_0 \Sigma_p V_{\text{Alfvén}}$ is large, then the incident electric field is almost entirely reflected. [μ_0 is the permeability of free space, Σ_p is the height integrated Pedersen conductivity, and $V_{\text{Alfvén}}$ is the Alfvén speed above the conducting layer.] Furthermore, for this regime, the Incident magnetic field is half the magnetic field just above the conducting layer. The magnetic field of the reflected wave adds to the incident wave field. This appears to be consistent with the results in Figure 4.

The wave-Pedersen conductivity is derived by superposing the incident and reflected waves, that is exactly what it is all about, and it was originally defined in [Cosgrove 2016]. A few paragraphs before where the referee is commenting (on Section 2, which is Section 3 in the final 2022 version), there is the sentence “The arrows in the figure illustrate how the formula is derived, as the superposition of two waves traveling in opposite directions, related by the reflection coefficient at the load, $(Y_0 - Y_L)/(Y_0 + Y_L)$.” The formula

referred is the (slightly generalized) standard transmission line formula, and reading the section one finds that it was used to derive the wave-Pedersen conductivity. In Cosgrove [2016] the wave-Pedersen conductivity was derived by explicitly combining incident and reflected waves, but in this article I wanted to emphasize that these are old and well established ideas.

In the final 2022 version of the article, artificial waves are constructed where the wave-Pedersen conductivity is modified to match the (regular, zero-frequency) Pedersen conductivity. It is shown that the model then reproduces electrostatic theory exactly (if the parallel wavelength and dissipation scale length are also made long). This also shows that the interpretation given in the paper for the “wave-Pedersen conductivity” is correct.

If the author is not going to include the non-linear term then why is it discussed in the next paragraph? Indeed once equation (7) is given I see little of value in the rest of this section. It strikes me as a rather pedantic discussion that essentially leads to the conclusion that the author will use linear perturbation theory when discussing the eigenmodes of the system described by equation (7).

It is important for the article to give a rigorous account of the model derivation, so that there cannot be broadly-stated objections as were made by other referees. Reading some of the other reviews, there appears to be a lack of understanding of certain key points, for example that the DC response is fully included in this approach. In addition, I feel it is important to develop an intuitive understanding of the physics, and so I believe all the development is very worthwhile. The patient reader will be rewarded if they read this material carefully. I agree that this is known material that could be considered pedantic, but there is a reason we learned all this stuff in school. It is very powerful!

Figure 6 has some value, but I would strongly encourage a different normalization scheme, given the already existing knowledge of the wave modes expected for the ionosphere (the fast, shear, and slow modes as mentioned earlier). In particular, the electron velocities should be normalized to the Alfvén speed. This is essentially the normalization used for the ion velocities, the normalized ion velocity = $(c/V_{\text{Alfvén}}) \cdot \text{ion velocity} \cdot B$, where B is the ambient magnetic field strength. The reason for doing this is so that the reader can see if there is any difference in the ion and electron velocities, as it is that difference that gives the current density in the plasma. The electric fields should also be renormalized by $c/V_{\text{Alfvén}}$. For the shear mode this would ensure that the electric and magnetic fields are plotted on a scale that makes them comparable. I further note that the Whistler mode appears to have the properties I would expect for the fast mode. The density, pressure, and parallel component of the magnetic field perturbation are all in phase. Finally, in Figure 6 the thermal mode appears to have the characteristics of what I might expect for the slow mode, being mainly a pressure perturbation. I do acknowledge that this could also be the ion mode. Perhaps the high collision frequencies have separated the ion and electron motion. This is may be a point worth making, especially since the stem plot is drawn for 120 km altitude, i.e. the bottomside ionosphere.

These comments by the referee are potentially valuable, as finding a good normalization for the waves was a challenge. The referee is recommending normalization by the ideal Alfvén wave properties, which for the Alfvén wave would allow for assessing how close to ideal it is. This might be a good choice, although testing would be required, and I note that the same normalization must be applied to all the modes (if the figure is to serve its purpose of comparing the different modes).

However, the referee does not seem to appreciate how much collisions will affect the modes in the E region, and continues to insist that the modes be thought of simply as the ideal, collisionless MHD modes. The relationship between whistler mode, fast mode, and the single eigenvector they both correspond to was investigated in Cosgrove [2016]. It was found that the fully-collisional eigenvector corresponds better to the whistler wave, which is why that name was chosen. Also, the relationship of the collisionless, shear Alfvén mode to the fully-collisional eigenvector was investigated in Table 2 of Cosgrove [2016], and profound differences were found.

Regardless, the referee is going down the path of trying to understand the relationship of the fully-collisional eigenvectors to the physically defined, collisionless MHD waves. This is no doubt interesting to them, but is not the topic of the article! I want to discourage distractions like this. The point of the article is to give a rigorous electromagnetic derivation of the ionospheric conductance, and associated electric field “mapping.” Therefore I have removed Figure 6 from the final 2022 version.

I strongly recommend that the author refer to the "slow" Alfvén wave as the shear mode. In classical MHD wave theory the slow mode is the sound wave for a plasma where the thermal pressure is much less than the magnetic pressure (i.e., sound speed \ll Alfvén speed).

I did make a mistake in the sentence commented on, the word “slow” should have been “shear.” The slow mode is the one that corresponds to the ion-acoustic wave, and the shear mode to the Alfvén wave, in the ionospheric terminology. This is the sentence where it was explained that what I called the Whistler wave could also have been called the fast-Alfvén wave (referee calls it just “fast mode”), and the latter would make more sense at higher altitudes. Figure 7 was included specifically to make this point, although its caption also reads “slow” where it should read “shear” (not sure what happened with that). But since this eigenvector primarily propagates at lower altitudes, where it better matches the whistler wave [Cosgrove 2016], the name “Whistler” was adopted.

Figure 8 and subsequent figures are very difficult to read, with the colors blue, black and green hard to distinguish. It is also not clear to me why the author spends so much time comparing the electrostatic solutions to the electromagnetic. If the author is solving the electromagnetic equations, then the stem plots would indicate how electrostatic the waves are. Again, based on classical MHD wave theory I would expect the fast (Whistler) mode or the shear (Alfvén) mode to generally not have an electrostatic counterpart. The shear mode could become electrostatic for short wavelengths (high wave number) if the wave frequency approaches the ion gyro-frequency.

I am sorry about the lines being hard to distinguish. These are PDF figures that are fully zoomable, but if the referee is color blind that may not help. Although there are many possibilities, I chose to compare the electrostatic and electromagnetic waves through their parallel wavelengths, because if those are different and the electromagnetic one is short (which can be the case!), the electrostatic wave will give a wrong characterization of the ionosphere. A comparison based on the stem plots would say little about the errors that could be produced. I also note that an earlier referee said that the shear mode becomes electrostatic at “Scales below the electron inertial length...,” which seems to me different from a criteria based on the ion gyro-frequency. So it seems this material is not all that well known, even in the collisionless case.

This result is also expected from classical MHD wave theory. At sufficiently high altitudes, where collisions are less important, we can use the standard dispersion relations for the fast and shear mode. For the fast mode the dispersion relation is given by $\omega^2 = k^2 V_{\text{Alfvén}}^2$ assuming a cold plasma. k is the wave number. If we split the wave number into parallel and perpendicular components then $\omega^2 = (k_{\text{perp}}^2 + k_{\text{parl}}^2) V_{\text{Alfvén}}^2$ where k_{perp} is the perpendicular wave number and k_{parl} is the parallel wave number. We note that if k_{perp} is too large, such that $k_{\text{perp}}^2 V_{\text{Alfvén}}^2 > \omega^2$, then k_{parl} must be imaginary, corresponding to an evanescent wave. This condition does not apply to the shear mode, which has the dispersion relation $\omega^2 = k_{\text{parl}}^2 V_{\text{Alfvén}}^2$. This dispersion relation is independent of k_{perp} , and so we expect to have a propagating shear-mode wave regardless of the perpendicular wave number.

It’s true that many of the results for the collisional ionospheric waves mirror the results for the collisionless MHD waves. But making a study of this relationship is another topic that is outside the scope of this work. It was explained near the end of Section III (Section 4 in the final 2022 version) that the Whistler wave requires a quadratic integral approximation, which results in a quadratic dispersion relation, and is associated with a low frequency cutoff. This is the point the referee is making and the existing discussion is deemed sufficient.

I again want to point out the conflation of two different uses of the adjective electrostatic. In the context of wave theory electrostatic does indeed mean ignoring $\text{curl } \mathbf{E}$. But in the context of Pedersen and Hall conductivities the time variation is ignored in the ion and electron momentum equation. Clearly waves are the mean by which information is transmitted from region of the magnetosphere to the other, and indeed Alfvén (i.e. MHD) waves are the primary means by which the electric fields and currents adjust. I do not disagree that a fully electromagnetic wave theory is required. But these have been existence for several years (again, I refer to Tu et al. (2014) as an example).

It appears that the referee did not read the last paragraph of the Introduction section (Section I), where this distinction was clearly made and it was stated that the terms “electrostatic theory” and “electrostatic

waves” would be used to make the distinction in the remainder. For example that paragraph contains the line “The validity of this electrostatic-wave theory is a distinct question from that of the full electrostatic theory, which does not include wavelike effects.” So there is no conflation of terms, it is just that the referee did not read all of Section I (Introduction).

I am glad that the referee now agrees that a fully electromagnetic treatment is required, because their earlier comments seemed to be in denial, and they did not tell the editor about the main results in the paper.

The fact that other kinds of electromagnetic models exist is irrelevant, because different kinds of models have different strengths and weaknesses.

Because the stem plot in Figure 6 does not show the electric field I am not sure that I concur with this conclusion. Faraday’s law suggests that if the vertical scale is 100 km and the electric field is 10 mV/m, then the magnetic field changes by ~ 600 nT/s for a wave of 100 nT/s if the 100 km is an evanescence scale.

This comment was applied to the last line of the paper, which read “The electrical thickness is the amount of phase rotation for a signal traversing the ionosphere, and we find that it often exceeds 90° , meaning a complete failure of electric field mapping, even for transverse wavelengths as large as 100 km.” Figure 6 is irrelevant to this finding; it has nothing to do with wavelength. And if the reviewer thinks they can use it to evaluate whether the waves are correct, they cannot, because they do not have any results for collisional waves that could be compared. The salient figure is Figure 12 (Figure 2 in the final 2022 version), where was demonstrated the integration of the wavevector over altitude, to get the phase rotation.

The referee should have reported the findings in the article to the editor, such as the contents of this last line. This is especially true given that the referee did not find any problems with the methodology. Instead, it appears the referee has relied on a hand-waving argument to convince themselves that they didn’t even need to tell the editor what results the article claimed. This is a typical feature of group think, where highly simplistic arguments are deemed sufficient to uphold the existing paradigm, even over arguments that are much more rigorous.

S.6.5.5 Decision Letter from Phys. Rev. E

From: pre@aps.org
Subject: Your_manuscript EU12156 Cosgrove
Date: XXXX XX, XXXX at 6:35:46 PM PST
To: russell.cosgrove@me.com
Reply-To: pre@aps.org

Re: EU12156
Electromagnetic ionosphere: A model
by Russell B. Cosgrove

Dear Dr. Cosgrove,

The above manuscript has been reviewed by two of our referees. Comments from the reports appear below. The Physical Review editors wish to accept only papers that, in addition to being scientifically sound, are important to the field and contain significant new results in physics. Given the appended comments, we judge that these acceptance criteria are not met.

We regret that consequently we cannot accept the paper for publication in the Physical Review.

Yours sincerely,

XXXXXX
Associate Editor Physical Review E
Email: pre@aps.org
<https://journals.aps.org/pre/>

P.S. We regret the delay in obtaining these reports.

Three out of the four referees failed to tell the editor about the results in the paper. None of the referees told the editor that anything was wrong with the methodology. In fact one of them specifically said “I

consider the paper to be correct in the governing equations used to generate the wave-propagation solutions. But I do not consider the work to be particularly new, at least in terms of the physics.”, and then did not tell the editor what results the article claimed. Referees are supposed to tell the editor what results a paper claims, and then separately evaluate the methodology. The referees have not done their job, and have instead acted as gate keepers for a potentially wrong electrostatic paradigm.

S.6.6 Reviews of “An Electromagnetic Calculation of Ionospheric Conductance that seems to Override the Field Line Integrated Conductivity,” submitted to JGR in 2022. This was the fifth version of the final 2022 paper.

This version was very similar to the version submitted to Phys. Rev. E. The main difference was that this version added modeling results using artificially modified wave modes, which showed that the model would exactly reproduce electrostatic theory if the identified criteria were satisfied. These criteria were identified in the section on the gedanken experiment. Also, the description of what was meant by “electrostatic theory,” and the differentiation from “electrostatic waves” was moved to the second paragraph in the Introduction. It had previously been in the last paragraph of the Introduction, and some of the reviewers had failed to discover it there.

S.6.6.1 Reviewer #1

Reviewer #1 Evaluations:

Recommendation (Required): Reject

Significant: No, the paper is not a significant advance or contribution.

Supported: No

Referencing: Mostly yes, but some additions are necessary.

Quality: The organization of the manuscript and presentation of the data and results need some improvement.

Data: No

Accurate Key Points: No

Reviewer #1 (Formal Review for Authors (shown to authors)):

This manuscript is to calculate ionospheric conductance using electromagnetic solutions for collisional plasma. The transmission line theory is applied to extend the calculation to stratified ionosphere. The major conclusion is that an electromagnetic wave description is required, as already advocated by a number of previous studies from prospects of physical processes and sophisticated numerical simulations. This study, in my opinion, did not significantly contribute to advance our understanding of the ionosphere-thermosphere dynamics for the reasons stated below. Therefore, I do not recommend its publication in JGR Space physics.

The reviewer does not report the main results of the paper to the editor, which are that the ionospheric conductance is different from the field line integrated conductivity, and the electric field does not map through the ionosphere. The referee suggests that certain “prospects of physical processes and sophisticated numerical simulations” have already found the results in the article, whereas in fact there are no comparable results anywhere I can find. The reviewer does not give any references to back up their claim.

1. Transmission line (TL) theory is widely used for modeling signal transmission along the specified path and often helpful to provide physical insights to the process of interest. However, research in ionospheric physics have long passed the stage that our understanding of the system relies on simple concept of input-admittance. One serious drawback of the TL theory is that the signal can only propagate along the "line", even the transverse scale may be taken into consideration. In other words, oblique transmission is not allowed. In fact, the wave transmission in the ionosphere is 3-D. The author cited Tu et al, 2014 to indicate that the electromagnetic modeling of the ionosphere is one-dimensional without considering transverse-scale dependence. This is not true, because later studies are 2-D electromagnetic simulations (Tu and Song, A two-dimensional global simulation study of inductive- dynamic magnetosphere ionosphere coupling, JGR Space Physics, 121, doi:10.1002/2016JA023393, 2016; Tu and Song, On the momentum transfer from polar to equatorial ionosphere, Space Physics, 124, doi:10.1029/2019JA026760, 2019). There are also other 2-D

even 3-D electromagnetic studies (e.g., Lysak, et al, Modeling of the ionospheric Alfvén resonator in dipolar geometry, JGR Space Physics, 118, 1514-1528, doi:10.1002/jgra.50090, and references therein), although these studies do not explicitly include plasma and neutral dynamics.

The reviewer is not correct about the limitations of the analysis in the article. The signal is not limited to propagation “along a line,” and “oblique transmission” is fully supported. The article in fact describes the propagation of three-dimensional perturbations of a vertically stratified ionosphere, with no limitations as to the direction of the wavevector or the Poynting vector. Also what was said about [Tu et al., 2014] in the paper is correct, that article contains a completely one-dimensional analysis that does not include any transverse scale-size dependence. It is true that the article failed to reference the later Tu and Song studies that were higher dimensional, but it did reference other similar two- and three-dimensional electromagnetic simulation studies that were done earlier, including the Lysak study specifically mentioned by the reviewer. However, NONE of these studies reported results for the ionospheric conductance, and the reviewer has not referenced any such results. Before receiving so many reviews of the various versions of this article I kept thinking maybe I was missing something in the earlier studies, but that now seems highly unlikely.

2. Our studies of the ionosphere-thermosphere now are using system approach and focus on self-consistency. Both the plasma and neutrals dynamics must be considered to provide a faithful description of the coupled system. The TL theory used in the manuscript does not include neutral dynamics, and plasma dynamics is not considered explicitly either.

What the referee said about “plasma dynamics is not considered explicitly” is not correct. Other than kinetic effects, the plasma dynamics is fully included in the analysis, with the exception of nonlinear terms, which terms are also not included in electrostatic theory. And the neutral dynamics is also not included in electrostatic theory. So testing electrostatic theory does not require inclusion of either neutral dynamics or nonlinear terms. The physical justification for omitting neutral dynamics is that the electrostatic state should arise over much shorter time scales than is possible for any neutral response. The physical justification for omitting the nonlinear terms is that they are negligible for sufficiently small-amplitude signals, and it is useful to have an amplitude independent characterization of the system; this is the basic recipe for circuit theory and the definition of admittance depends upon it.

3. In electromagnetic modeling of the magnetosphere-ionosphere-thermosphere system, conductance is actually not necessary and is a by-product. Conductance is needed in electrostatic theory to connect electrical current density and electric field. Then from divergence-free of the current density, the electric potential equation (Poisson equation) is obtained and used to calculate electric field. In the electromagnetic approach, Maxwell’s equations are solved to determined electric field and perturbation magnetic field. Plasma and neutral parameters are governed by plasma and neutral transport equations. The current density is actually not necessary either, which is merely a quantity to describe difference between the electron velocity and ion bulk velocity.

The referee implies that the ionospheric conductance is not important (and a similar statement was made in the first paragraph). This assertion is something of a joke, since in addition to being the standard quantity used to determine the inner boundary condition for global MHD modeling, the ionospheric conductance is ubiquitous in conversations of space physics. The ionospheric conductance is a fundamental concept in MI coupling. But the calculation in the article does not only produce the ionospheric conductance, it also gives all the other field quantities as well, resolved in three dimensions. More specifically, the Fourier components are derived, and these can be assembled to describe an arbitrary three-dimensional disturbance. At present, when only a few have yet been calculated, they can be used to describe the scale-size dependence of the ionospheric response.

S.6.6.2 Decision Letter from JGR

From: jgr-spacephysics@agu.org
Subject: 2022JA030862 (Editor - XXXX): Decision Letter
Date: XXXX XX, XXXX at 12:36PM
To: russell.cosgrove@me.com

Cc: russell.cosgrove@ucf.edu

Dear Dr. Cosgrove:

Thank you for submitting your manuscript to Journal of Geophysical Research - Space Physics. as you suggested, I sent the manuscript to two leading experts on the topic. one of them declined to review and the other recommended to reject. I also take a careful reading of the manuscript and agree with the referee. in magnetosphere-ionosphere coupling, the electric engineering approach has already run its course. now people agree that the momentum transfer between plasma and neutrals are crucial to understand many phenomena. in your derivation, many weak points can be found, mostly due to invalid approximations. you may argue they are not wrong, but they are clearly not state-of-the-art as required by the JGR-Space Physics. I am declining your manuscript for publication in Journal of Geophysical Research - Space Physics.

I am enclosing the reviews, which you may find helpful if you decide to revise your manuscript and submit to another journal. I am sorry that I cannot be more encouraging at this time.

Thank you for your interest in Space Physics.

Sincerely,

XXXX

Editor

Journal of Geophysical Research - Space Physics

The editor does not say anything specific in their appraisal. There are general expressions of negativity, but there is nothing that gives any insight into anything that might be wrong.

In science, we use whatever methods give results, just so long as the method is valid. A method has not “run its course” when it is still producing new and important results. There are essentially no other papers that give electromagnetic results for the ionospheric conductance. Although there is a lot more discussion in Sections 1 and 2 of the final 2022 paper, this alone is proof that the methods in the paper are “state of the art,” to the extent that is a valid metric. And having a variety of different methods available is a good thing.

S.6.7 Response to Reviews Concluded

Beginning with the 2016 article where the concepts were first introduced there have been 12 reviews of this work, with 5 being essentially positive. Of the reviews that were against, not a single one told the editor about the results found in the paper, and not a single one identified any specific problem with the methodology. No doubt a few of these reviewers were simply not in a position to understand the point of the article, and for some reason did not realize that. But it is difficult to explain the whole phenomenon in this way. Thus, it seems necessary to conclude that groupthink is preventing the article from being published. This a situation where self publication is appropriate. This is a thoroughly peer-reviewed article where the reader may evaluate the reviews for themselves.

The article presents what might be described as the canonical electromagnetic calculation of the ionospheric conductance, and of electric field mapping, etc. The methods are standard physics methods, which have not yet been applied to ionospheric science. I can find only one other article that compares an electromagnetic calculation of conductance to the field line integrated conductivity, and that article employs a boundary value calculation, the unreliability of which was one of the major points of the Cosgrove [2016] article. When a standard physics calculation provides clear results, that fact needs to be known by the research community. This is especially true when the results contradict a long-standing paradigm, where that paradigm is not well supported by the published mathematical analysis.

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